

1 Supplement of
2 **Operational chemical weather forecasting with the ECCC online**
3 **Regional Air Quality Deterministic Prediction System version**
4 **023 (RAQDPS023) - Part 2: Multi-year prospective and**
5 **retrospective performance evaluation**

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49 **S2 Methodology**

50 **S2.2 Input emissions**

51 Four year-specific annual anthropogenic national emission inventories were extracted for the 2013–2016
52 period for Canada from the ECCC TREND16 emissions trend data set. The TREND16 data set consists of
53 a set of annual anthropogenic national emission inventories for Canada for the period 2000-2016 saved in
54 a format ready for input to the Sparse Matrix Operator Kernel (SMOKE) emissions processing system
55 (<https://www.cmascenter.org/smoke/>). This data set was developed based on the version of the Canadian
56 Air Pollutant Emissions Inventory (APEI) released in 2018 (ECCC, 2018). The 2018 APEI contained
57 comprehensive, consistent, and detailed estimates of Canadian annual anthropogenic emissions of seven
58 criteria air pollutants (SO₂, NO_x, CO, VOC, NH₃, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀) reported by province or territory and
59 by emissions source type for each year of the 27-year period from 1990 to 2016. Both bottom-up and top-
60 down emissions estimation approaches were employed to compile it. Annual emissions values of large
61 point sources were obtained from the multi-year facility-level emissions data reported by individual
62 industrial, commercial, and institutional facilities to the ECCC National Pollutant Release Inventory (NPRI,
63 2017) (i.e., bottom-up estimates), while annual emissions values for area sources and for on-road and off-
64 road mobile sources were calculated by ECCC for each province and territory based on emissions factors
65 and consistent time series of source-specific activity data (i.e., top-down estimates). For most emissions
66 sectors, the methodologies used to estimate Canadian emissions were consistent with either those used to
67 estimate corresponding U.S. emissions (U.S. EPA, 1995) or those recommended in the European emission
68 inventory guidebook (EMEP/EEA, 2013), with the proviso that these methods were often further adjusted
69 by ECCC to reflect Canadian climate, fuels, technologies, and practices. The transformation of the 2018
70 APEI emissions trend data set into the SMOKE-ready TREND16 data set then required the mapping of
71 internal ECCC emissions sector codes to U.S. EPA Source Classification Codes (SCCs), record
72 reformatting, the addition of ancillary information (e.g., smokestack heights and diameters, facility
73 operating schedules, GIS shapefiles for preparation of gridded spatial surrogate fields, chemistry-
74 mechanism-specific VOC speciation profiles, and temporal cross-reference files), and transportation-
75 fraction-based reduction of PM emissions from fugitive sources to account for near-source removal (cf.
76 Sassi et al., 2021; Moran et al., 2026).

77 Four year-specific annual anthropogenic national emission inventories for the 2013–2016 period for the
78 U.S. were extracted from the U.S. EPA EQUATES (Epa’s air QUALity Time Series) national emissions
79 trend data set. The EQUATES data set consists of a SMOKE-ready set of annual anthropogenic national
80 emissions inventories and annual wildfire emissions inventories for the 18-year period from 2002 to 2019

81 (Foley et al., 2023; <https://www.epa.gov/cmaq/equates>). Each of these 18 year-specific annual inventories
82 contains emissions of seven criteria air pollutants (SO₂, NO_x, CO, VOC, NH₃, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) reported at the
83 county level by SCC and grouped into 18 files corresponding to 18 broad source categories. Where
84 possible, year-specific annual emissions were estimated by the EPA using consistent input data and
85 estimation methods across this period, including for emissions from the mobile, wildfire, and oil and gas
86 sectors. For other source sectors such as paved and unpaved road dust, airports, railroads, and residential
87 wood combustion, emissions were estimated by scaling emissions from the 2017 U.S. National Emissions
88 Inventory (NEI) with year-specific scaling factors based on activity data and/or source control information
89 (Foley et al., 2023). The standard EQUATES data set focuses on the 48 contiguous U.S. states, but it was
90 augmented for the present study by the U.S. EPA with emissions for Alaska.

91 The EQUATES data set also includes a SMOKE-ready set of annual anthropogenic national emissions
92 inventories and annual wildfire emissions inventory files for 2002-2019 for Mexico for the same seven
93 criteria air pollutants but reported at the county level by SCC. On-road emissions were estimated for
94 Mexico using a version of the MOtor Vehicle Emission Simulator (MOVES) on-road emissions-factor
95 model tailored for Mexico. All point, area, and off-road mobile emissions were based on the 2016 Mexican
96 NEI provided by Mexico's SEMARNAT (Secretariat of Environment and Natural Resources) agency.
97 Sector-specific scaling factors for 2002-2013 for Mexico were obtained from the Community Emissions
98 Data System (CEDS) global emissions trend data set (Hoesly et al., 2018; Foley et al., 2023) while 2014
99 and 2015 annual emissions were assumed to be the same as 2016.

100 Emissions processing is a very data-driven task. The SMOKE emissions processing system relies on a
101 number of ancillary files to specify how spatial allocation, temporal allocation, and chemical speciation
102 will be performed for each emissions source type. One group of ancillary files contains gridded spatial
103 surrogate fields, monthly, weekly, and diurnal temporal profiles, and NO_x, VOC, and PM chemical
104 speciation profiles. A second group consists of the cross-reference tables that link U.S. EPA Source
105 Classification Codes to these spatial surrogate fields and temporal and chemical profiles to allow different
106 treatments of emissions from different source sectors.

107 The spatial allocation or gridding of emissions reported by jurisdiction to the 10-km model grid (e.g.,
108 **Fig. 13**) was performed using 61 spatial surrogate fields for Canada (Sassi et al., 2021), 53 spatial surrogate
109 fields for the U.S. (Foley et al., 2023), and 15 spatial surrogate fields for Mexico (Foley et al., 2023). The
110 spatial surrogate fields that were used are not year-specific with the one exception of the U.S. oil and gas
111 sector, for which year-specific spatial surrogates were provided by the U.S. EPA to account for rapid
112 changes in this sector. Temporal allocation of annual emissions to specific days and hours was performed

113 with 86 month-of-year, 24 day-of-week, and 30 hour-of-day temporal profiles for Canada (Sassi et al.,
114 2021), 18,438 monthly, 11,736 weekly, and 18,997 diurnal temporal profiles for the U.S. (Foley et al.,
115 2023), and 161 monthly, 15 weekly, and 48 diurnal temporal profiles for Mexico (Foley et al., 2023).
116 Chemical speciation of three of the seven criteria air pollutants in the inventories (NO_x , VOC, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$) to 14
117 GEM-MACH emitted gas-phase species and 12 emitted particle chemical-component-size-bin species was
118 carried out using sector-specific speciation profiles from the SPECIATE5.1 chemical profile library
119 (<https://www.epa.gov/air-emissions-modeling/speciate-4>), whereas SO_2 , CO, and NH_3 emissions mapped
120 directly to individual GEM-MACH gas-phase species (Moran et al., 2026). $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} emissions
121 values in the SMOKE-generated emission files were also decreased after SMOKE processing by means of
122 a land-use-based transportable fraction to account for near-source removal by settling and impaction within
123 each model grid cell (Pace, 2005; Pouliot et al., 2011; Moran et al., 2026). In addition, a meteorological-
124 modulation parameterization to reduce fugitive $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ emissions in the presence of snow cover or wet
125 surfaces during or after precipitation was applied at each time step during the RAQDPS023 simulation
126 (Moran et al., 2026).

127 **S2.3 Air-chemistry and precipitation-chemistry observations**

128 As noted by Demerjian (2000, 2007), multiple U.S. networks make $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass measurements using a
129 variety of instruments. Some instruments follow the U.S. EPA Federal Reference Method (FRM), which
130 specifies the use of filter-based samplers to collect $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ aerosol particles over a 24-hour sampling period
131 followed by gravimetric analysis in a lab (e.g., Noble et al., 2001; Demerjian, 2007). Other instruments
132 apply alternative measurement techniques that have been approved as one of three classes of Federal
133 Equivalent Method (FEM) $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass measurement instruments whose measurements should be
134 comparable to FRM measurements: Class I and II FEM samplers also employ 24-hour sampling intervals
135 while Class III FEM samplers typically make continuous (e.g., hourly) measurements (e.g., Noble et al.,
136 2001). Class III FEM samplers employ such methods as beta attenuation, light scattering, and Tapered
137 Element Oscillating Microbalances (TEOMs) (Noble et al., 2001; Gantt, 2022). Both FRM and FEM
138 instruments are used for regulatory monitoring in the U.S., including compliance monitoring. Other
139 instruments to measure $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass are also available, but these non-FRM/FEM instruments are not used
140 for regulatory purposes. The U.S. EPA's AQS measurement database contains both FRM/FEM and non-
141 FRM/FEM measurements, but the former are called regulatory measurements and are identified by code
142 88101 while the latter are called "Acceptable $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ AQI & Speciation Mass" monitors" and identified by
143 code 88502 (e.g., Zhang et al., 2022).

144 The U.S. EPA operates a national FRM network to monitor compliance with the U.S. National Ambient
145 Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) and to assess $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ exposure. It consists of roughly 1000 samplers, most

146 of which collect 24-hour samples once every three days although some collect samples every day and some
147 once every six days (Demerjian, 2007; Malm et al., 2011). Measurement data from this network are
148 archived in the AQS database (see **Table S2a**). **Figure S6a** shows the locations where these samplers are
149 deployed. Many of the one-in-six-day samplers are co-located with a one-in-three-day sampler. In such
150 cases we have only considered measurements from the one-in-three-day sampler, but we have considered
151 once-in-six-day measurements if they come from a standalone sampler. The two U.S. PM_{2.5} speciation
152 networks, CSN and IMPROVE, and the Canadian NAPS PM_{2.5} speciation network also measure PM_{2.5} total
153 mass as well as PM_{2.5} chemical composition. However, CSN stopped operating its own FRM instruments
154 in 2014 since FRM compliance samplers were co-located with almost all CSN speciation samplers (e.g.,
155 Solomon et al., 2014). However, this does introduce the complication of collating measurements from two
156 networks at each measurement site. IMPROVE also employs integrated gravimetric sampling to measure
157 PM_{2.5} total mass. While these measurements do not meet U.S. EPA requirements for FRM measurements
158 due to non-compliant laboratory environmental conditions (Solomon et al., 2014; Hand et al., 2019), they
159 were still used in this study to assess mass closure. **Figure S6b** shows the locations where these samplers
160 were deployed.

161 The above discussion should help in the interpretation of **Table S2c**, which lists the number of available
162 and complete gravimetric measurements of daily PM_{2.5} total mass and its chemical components for four
163 networks for the 2013–2016 period. The values reported for the AQS network correspond to the U.S. EPA
164 FRM network. No PM_{2.5} measurements are reported in this table for the CSN network because these
165 measurements were obtained from co-located samplers from the U.S. EPA FRM network.

166 **S2.4 Pairing model predictions with measurements**

167 Spatial pairing, though imperfect due to the spatial incommensurability noted in **Sect. 2.4**, is also
168 straightforward. For air-chemistry measurements, bilinear interpolation was used to estimate model values
169 at monitor locations. For precipitation-chemistry measurements, values for the model grid cell in which a
170 measurement station is located were used without any spatial interpolation since precipitation is often
171 fragmented and small-scale. Note that incommensurability is likely to be more of an issue for the spatial
172 pairing of measurements of primary pollutants than secondary pollutants and for measurements in urban
173 areas than in rural areas, that is, conditions for which horizontal subgrid-scale (SGS) gradients are likely to
174 be more pronounced. For this reason, all measurements from roadside monitors have been removed from
175 the AQS and NAPS measurement data sets (based on station metadata) before the pairing step to avoid the
176 obvious representativeness problem relative to a regional-scale model's larger grid cells.
177 Incommensurability also poses a limitation to pairing in the vertical given the large near-surface vertical
178 gradients that can occur for species that are emitted from the Earth's surface or dry deposited to the surface

179 (e.g., Byun and Dennis, 1995). In this study, tracer abundance values for the 20 m thick lowest model layer
180 (Moran et al., 2026) were paired with near-surface measurement values, which assumes implicitly that this
181 layer is well mixed.

182 Chemical pairing is not so straightforward, especially for PM_{2.5} speciation measurements and precipitation-
183 chemistry measurements. For gas-phase species, measurements of NO, NO₂, O₃, HNO₃, HONO, NH₃, SO₂,
184 CO, and isoprene (C₅H₈) pair directly with model species (Moran et al., 2026), and measurements of NO_x
185 can be paired with the sum of model NO (in NO₂ units) and NO₂ predictions. In some cases, networks
186 provide several values for the same species. For example, CAPMoN provides two values for ambient
187 HNO₃, one value from analysis of the nylon filter alone and one value from the sum of the nylon and
188 cellulose filters (to account for breakthrough). The second value was used in this study. Some direct
189 measurements of another model species, ETHE, are also available, but this model species is a lumped VOC
190 species that includes some other VOC species. In addition to ethene the ETHE lumped species also includes
191 isoprene oxidation products such as methacrolein and methyl vinyl ketone needed to implement a
192 condensed isoprene chemistry mechanism used by the Carbon Bond-IV chemistry mechanism (Gery et al.,
193 1988; Stockwell and Lurmann, 1989; Stroud et al., 2008; Moran et al., 2026). The inclusion of these
194 additional species means that the model should overpredict measured ethene (e.g., Kuhn et al., 1998; Stroud
195 et al., 2008), although the contribution of isoprene oxidation products to model ETHE should be smallest
196 in the winter when isoprene emissions are the smallest (**Table S1**).

197 Measurement-model pairing may also require the meteorological conditions associated with reported
198 measurements to be considered. RAQDPS023 predictions of species abundance are in internal units of
199 mass mixing ratios (MMRs) for local meteorological conditions. Some gas-phase measurements are
200 reported as concentrations at a standard temperature and pressure (STP) such as those from CAPMoN, as
201 opposed to concentrations at local conditions, such as those from CASTNET (**Table S2a**). However,
202 CASTNET also provides corresponding ambient temperature and pressure measurements, allowing
203 conversion of reported concentrations to volume mixing ratios (VMRs). If meteorological measurements
204 are not provided, though, model-predicted temperature and pressure can be used to convert measured
205 concentrations to VMRs or predicted MMRs to concentrations. For this study, if measured concentrations
206 were not accompanied by meteorological measurements (e.g., AMoN and NAPS NH₃ measurements in
207 **Tables 4**, **S4A**, **S4S**, and **S8**), then model concentrations were calculated from model MMR, pressure, and
208 temperature values before pairing. Lastly, for those VOC species measurements reported in units of ppbvC,
209 division was performed by the number of carbon atoms for that species to convert to units of ppbv.

210 For PM measurements the presence and abundance of aerosol water is another issue. Studies have found
211 that aerosol water can be the dominant component of PM_{2.5} total mass for relative humidities (RHs)
212 exceeding 70-80% (e.g., Hänel, 1976; McMurry, 2000; Chen et al., 2003; Nguyen et al., 2016), and Tsyro
213 (2005) found the estimated annual mean fraction of water in PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ over Europe to be in the 20%
214 to 35% range. However, some routine PM_{2.5} mass measurements may not reflect aerosol water levels
215 (Nguyen et al., 2016). For example, gravimetric analyses of filter-based daily PM mass concentrations are
216 typically conducted in North America under controlled laboratory conditions with a temperature between
217 15°C and 30°C and a RH between 20% and 40% (e.g., Chow, 1995; Frank, 2006; Dabek-Zlotorzynska et
218 al., 2011; Malm et al., 2011; Hand et al., 2019), which may result in the evaporation of some aerosol water
219 before analysis. Continuous PM_{2.5} measurements made with the TEOM instrument sometimes employ
220 inlets with a heater or dryer to condition incoming air in order to avoid water droplets being sampled, but
221 this conditioning may also reduce the aerosol water component (e.g., Allen et al., 1997; McMurry, 2000).
222 In response, newer continuous PM_{2.5} instruments have been deployed since about 2013 to avoid this
223 negative artefact (e.g., Robichaud et al., 2016; Su et al., 2018; Gantt, 2022). In principle, then, model-
224 predicted PM concentrations that include aerosol water might need to be re-calculated using an equilibrium
225 model for the conditions representative of the gravimetric measurements (e.g., Frank, 2006; Metzger et al.,
226 2016; Widziewicz-Rzońca and Tytła, 2020), although another solution (adopted for RAQDPS023 forecasts
227 and in this study) is simply to neglect the predicted mass of aerosol water for these below-deliquescence
228 RH conditions (e.g., Tsyro, 2005; Kelly and Wexler, 2006; Appel et al., 2008). Note, though, that Frank
229 (2006) found the mass of particle-bound water associated with inorganic ions, which is not subject to
230 evaporation, to be roughly a factor of 0.24 of the sum of PM_{2.5}-SO₄ and PM_{2.5}-NH₄ mass while Dabek-
231 Zlotorzynska et al. (2011) used a factor of 0.32; these estimates thus neglect semi-volatile aerosol water
232 associated with higher humidity conditions. In addition, Malm et al. (2011) found that the amount of
233 particle-bound water varied little by season at urban and suburban stations and was higher than at rural
234 stations, which displayed pronounced variations between winter minima and summer maxima.

235 PM measurements also introduce other complications for pairing. One involves the definition of particle
236 size. Size-resolved PM measurements employ size-selective inlets whose size cuts are based on particle
237 aerodynamic diameter, which is defined as the diameter of a spherical particle with a density of 1 g cm⁻³
238 that behaves similarly to the particle of interest (e.g., Chow, 1995; McMurry, 2000). In practice, however,
239 size-selective inlets may exclude some small particles that should be selected but include larger particles
240 that should not be selected, thus introducing some uncertainty (e.g., Chow, 1995; McMurry, 2000).
241 Chemical transport models (CTMs), on the other hand, use the Stokes (or geometric) diameter to describe
242 particle size, where the Stokes diameter is equal to the aerodynamic diameter divided by the square root of

243 the particle density (e.g., Gonda and Abd El Khalik, 1985; McMurry, 2000; Boutzis et al., 2020). Thus, for
244 an average observed particle density of $1.7 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ (Morawska et al., 1999; Pitz et al., 2003), conversion of
245 Stokes diameter to aerodynamic diameter requires multiplication by a factor of 1.3. This means that in
246 terms of aerodynamic diameter, predicted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ values correspond to measured $\text{PM}_{3.3}$ values. For the
247 evaluation performed in this study, however, only measured $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ values were available, so no explicit
248 adjustment was made to match the aerodynamic diameter used by the measurements with the Stokes
249 diameter used by the model given the coarseness of the RAQDPS023 PM size distribution (i.e., only two
250 size bins). Note, though, that $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} primary emissions are also expressed in terms of aerodynamic
251 diameter (U.S. EPA, 1995), consistent with ambient $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} measurements, so these different
252 definitions of particle diameter may be a minor issue for pairing.

253 Other complications arise from the treatment of the PM carbonaceous component. The RAQDPS023
254 considers three carbonaceous species: EC, POM, and SOM (Moran et al., 2026). POM and SOM both
255 include the mass of organic carbon (OC) plus other constituent elements such as hydrogen, oxygen, and
256 nitrogen that all contribute to organic matter (OM) mass. The three North American $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ speciation
257 networks (CSN, IMPROVE, NAPS), however, employ an analytical technique that only quantifies total
258 organic carbon (TOC) mass from both POM and SOM. In order to estimate total organic matter (TOM)
259 mass from TOC measurements, a single TOM/TOC scaling ratio is normally applied, but the choice of the
260 value of that ratio has been extensively investigated (e.g., Turpin and Lim, 2001; Simon et al., 2011; Philip
261 et al., 2014). Following Hand et al. (2012) a TOM/TOC value of 1.8, representative of an aged aerosol,
262 has been used in this study to convert TOC measurements to TOM values. It should be noted, however,
263 that a number of studies have shown that a single TOM/TOC value is not appropriate to all locations and
264 times, with an observed range from 1.3 to 2.1. Higher values of this ratio were found in the summer and in
265 eastern North America and lower values were found in the winter months and western North America (e.g.,
266 Malm et al., 2011; Simon et al., 2011; Philip et al., 2014; Malm et al., 2020). In addition, since measured
267 TOC does not distinguish between primary and secondary sources, the evaluation of PM carbonaceous
268 component predictions is performed here based on model-predicted TOM values (equal to the sum of POM
269 and SOM). Furthermore, as well as the uncertainty associated with the fixed TOM/TOC value, measured
270 TOC is also known to have both positive and negative artifacts (e.g., Vecchi et al., 2009; Watson et al.,
271 2009; Chow et al., 2010; Cheng et al., 2012; Hand et al., 2012; Chow et al., 2015; Dillner, 2016). Field
272 blanks and backup filters are used by the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ speciation networks to quantify these artifacts (e.g., Dabek-
273 Zlotorzynska et al., 2011; Dillner, 2016). In this study blank-corrected TOC values have been used for the
274 IMPROVE and NAPS networks whereas uncorrected TOC values were used for CSN because corrected

275 values were not available from AQS for 2013-2015. Note that Zhang et al. (2025) recently reviewed the
276 accuracy and precision of CSN $PM_{2.5}$ composition measurements from 2002 to 2022.

277 The CM and SS components of $PM_{2.5}$ predicted by the RAQDPS023 also raise complications for pairing
278 since the $PM_{2.5}$ speciation networks do not measure either component directly. Instead, values must be
279 inferred from other chemical species or elements that are measured directly. The standard IMPROVE
280 formula to estimate CM was used here for all three networks. This formula is based on a weighted sum of
281 concentrations of oxide forms of a subset of measured soil elements, namely aluminum, silicon, calcium,
282 iron, and titanium (e.g., Malm et al., 1994; Wells et al., 2007; Hand et al., 2012, 2017). To estimate sea-
283 salt concentration, elemental sodium was used here as a proxy for the IMPROVE network following Malm
284 et al. (1994). However, the original scaling factor of 2.5 used by Malm et al. (1994), which assumed that
285 sea salt was pure NaCl, was changed to a value of 3.25 based on Table 1 of White (2008). Although other
286 studies have used elemental chlorine measurements from CSN or chlorine ion measurements from
287 IMPROVE to estimate the SS component, these proxies are known to be biased low due to depletion of
288 chloride by the reaction of gaseous nitric acid with sea salt (e.g., White, 2008; Hand et al., 2012; Edwards
289 et al., 2023). And while White (2008) also noted that elemental sodium is poorly detected by IMPROVE's
290 routine X-ray fluorescence analysis, Solomon et al. (2014) suggested that the IMPROVE minimum
291 detection limit (MDL) for elemental sodium had improved by a factor of four between 2006 and 2012. For
292 the CSN and NAPS speciation networks, sodium ion concentrations (not measured by IMPROVE) were
293 used instead of elemental sodium as an SS proxy with a scaling factor of 3.25 (although for the NAPS
294 speciation network Dabek-Zlotorzynska et al. (2011) recommended using the sum of sodium and chlorine
295 ion concentrations, both of which are measured by this network).

296 There is also an inconsistency in the availability of $PM_{2.5}$ - NH_4 measurements across the three $PM_{2.5}$
297 speciation networks since the IMPROVE network, unlike the CSN and NAPS networks, does not measure
298 $PM_{2.5}$ - NH_4 . As a consequence, calculations of $PM_{2.5}$ reconstructed mass (e.g., Malm et al., 2011; Chow et
299 al. 2015; Hand et al., 2019) based on IMPROVE measurements usually estimate NH_4 concentrations from
300 measured $PM_{2.5}$ - SO_4 and $PM_{2.5}$ - NO_3 concentrations by assuming that $PM_{2.5}$ - SO_4 occurs in the form of fully
301 neutralized ammonium sulphate and that $PM_{2.5}$ - NO_3 occurs in the form of ammonium nitrate, although the
302 degree of sulphate neutralization is known to vary spatially and temporally and nitrate can also react with
303 sea salt and soil dust (e.g., West et al., 1999; Lee et al., 2008; Chow et al., 2015; Hand et al., 2019). Malm
304 et al. (2011) have also noted that reported $PM_{2.5}$ - NH_4 values for CSN may be underestimates due to
305 volatilization losses. While recognizing these limitations, the IMPROVE approach has been followed in
306 this study to estimate the $PM_{2.5}$ - NH_4 component for IMPROVE for $PM_{2.5}$ mass reconstruction calculations
307 (e.g., [Table S5S-mr](#)).

308 Some pre-processing is also required to pair measurements from the CAPMoN and NADP precipitation-
309 chemistry networks (**Fig. S6c**) with model predictions of wet concentration and wet deposition of SO_4^- ,
310 NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ ions. The two national precipitation-chemistry networks measure and report mean daily
311 (CAPMoN) or weekly (NADP) wet concentrations and precipitation amounts, and then wet deposition
312 amounts are derived. GEM-MACH, on the other hand, calculates wet deposition and precipitation amounts
313 directly, and then wet concentration values are derived. Routine wet concentration measurements of SO_4^- ,
314 NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ ions include the combined contributions of both gas-phase SO_2 and particle SO_4 , both gas-
315 phase HNO_3 and particle NO_3 , and both gas-phase NH_3 and particle NH_4 . GEM-MACH, by contrast,
316 calculates the wet concentrations of gas-phase SO_2 and particle SO_4 separately, so these two model
317 quantities had to be combined before pairing with measured wet SO_4^- concentration. The predicted wet
318 concentrations of NO_3^- and NH_4^+ ions, on the other hand, include the contributions of both gas-phase HNO_3
319 and particle NO_3 and both gas-phase NH_3 and particle NH_4 , respectively, and hence can be paired directly
320 with measured values. Appel et al. (2011) described similar considerations. Since model precipitation
321 predictions were used to calculate model wet concentration values, it should be noted that model errors in
322 predicting precipitation will also affect predictions of wet concentrations and wet deposition. Other
323 evaluation studies have chosen to use precipitation measurements to remove this source of error for wet
324 deposition (e.g., Appel et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2018, 2019; Benish et al., 2022), but the goal of the present
325 paper was to evaluate model forecasts as an operational system, including precipitation forecasts. Given
326 this goal, precipitation predictions have also been evaluated (**Section 3.1**) but no precipitation-related
327 adjustments have been made to either predicted wet deposition or wet concentrations.

328 Several measurement data screening steps that were applied prior to pairing should also be noted. Many
329 networks provide data validity or quality flags for each reported value. Only data values flagged as “valid”
330 were considered in this study. In the case of the AirNow and NAPS NRT data streams, automatic filtering
331 is performed at ECCC to discard suspect values (**Section 2.3**). For QA/QCed final data sets some AQ
332 measurement networks (e.g., CAPMoN) may flag measurements as below detection level (BDL) but valid
333 and report a value equal to the MDL value. Following the CAPMoN protocol, such reports were treated as
334 valid and assigned a numerical value of two-thirds of the corresponding MDL value (e.g., Sirois and Vet,
335 1999; Sirois et al., 2000; Wetherbee et al., 2010). Reported values of zero were also used if flagged as
336 valid. And as already noted, measurements from near-road monitors in AQS and NAPS network data sets
337 were also excluded (based on station metadata) due to spatial representativeness concerns.

338 Two further data screening steps related to temporal aggregation were imposed on air-chemistry
339 measurements before pairing to ensure that only temporally representative values were considered for an
340 evaluation period. First, the sampling duration of each individual measurement was checked to confirm

341 that it was within $\pm 20\%$ of the nominal network sampling duration; if not, it was discarded. And second,
342 an appropriate temporal completeness criterion was applied to ensure that sufficient air-chemistry or
343 precipitation-chemistry measurements were available for each station to calculate representative monthly,
344 seasonal, or annual values for a given period (e.g., Olsen et al., 1990; Kyle et al., 2002; Hand et al., 2012;
345 Benish et al., 2022). For example, a 60% completeness criterion was used to calculate seasonal values from
346 air-chemistry measurements. That is, valid measurements were required for a minimum of 60% of the
347 possible measurement times in the season, such as 55 out of 91 days for daily measurements or 19 out of
348 30 days for one-day-in-three measurements. To calculate annual values a 75% overall completeness
349 criterion was imposed in conjunction with a 60% completeness criterion for each of the constituent seasons
350 (e.g., CCME, 2012; <https://www.epa.gov/outdoor-air-quality-data/about-air-data-reports>). That is, valid
351 measurements were required for a minimum of 75% of the possible measurement times in a year, such as
352 274 out of 365 days for daily gas-phase measurements or 92 out of 121 days for one-day-in-three PM_{2.5}
353 speciation measurements together with four complete seasonal values. Note that the test for annual
354 completeness will screen out those U.S. O₃ monitors that only operate in the “ozone” season (from May to
355 September; see [40 CFR part 58, Appendix D](#)).

356 In the case of precipitation-chemistry measurements two other quantities were used to assess temporal
357 completeness: (a) the completeness of rain/snow gauge measurements of precipitation depth (Percent
358 Precipitation Coverage Length or %PCL); and (b) the completeness of precipitation depth associated with
359 valid sample collection and valid chemical analysis (Percent Total Precipitation or %TP) (Olsen et al.,
360 1990; WMO/GAW, 2004). The Level 3 seasonal and annual completeness measures specified by Olsen et
361 al. (1990) and WMO/GAW (2004) were then applied (seasonal %PCL = 50%, seasonal %TP = 50%; annual
362 %PCL = 90%, annual %TP = 60%), except the %PCL criterion was slightly relaxed to 80%.

363 **Table 2** and **Tables S2b–S2d** show the impacts of these completeness criteria. For example, across North
364 America in 2021/22 a total of 368 stations reported hourly NO₂ in NRT, 1294 reported hourly O₃, and 973
365 reported hourly PM_{2.5}, but NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5} annual mean values meeting the completeness criteria were
366 only available for 305 stations (83%), 755 stations (58%), and 776 stations (80%), respectively (**Table 2**).
367 The lower percentage of U.S. O₃ stations meeting the 75% completeness criterion for annual values was
368 due to filtering out those stations that only operate during the U.S. “ozone season”. For stations measuring
369 other gas-phase species, measurements for VOC species in 2013–2016 had the lowest completeness
370 percentages (**Table S2b**). For networks measuring PM_{2.5} chemical composition, the IMPROVE PM_{2.5}
371 speciation network had the highest completeness percentage in 2013–2016 (93% or more) followed by the
372 CSN and NAPS networks (**Table S2c**). And CAPMoN and NADP, the two national precipitation-
373 chemistry networks, each had about 80% annual completeness for 2013–2016 (**Table S2d**).

374 **S2.5 Model performance metrics and evaluation**

375 A variety of statistical metrics have been used in past studies to evaluate model performance. In fact, Kang
376 et al. (2005) referred to an “overabundance” of such metrics while Yu et al. (2006) referred to a “plethora”.
377 For example, Yu et al. (2006) listed 10 metrics, Borrego et al. (2008) listed 11 metrics, Simon et al. (2012)
378 listed 12 metrics along with their frequency of use in 69 operational evaluation studies, Thunis et al. (2012)
379 listed 20 metrics, and Zhang et al. (2012) listed 43 statistical and categorical metrics. There is general
380 agreement, however, that there is not a best single statistical metric or performance evaluation methodology
381 (e.g., Stanski et al., 1989; Chang and Hanna, 2004; Kang et al., 2005; Zhang et al., 2012). For example, to
382 quote Stanski et al. (1989): “*No single verification measure provides complete information about the quality*
383 *of a product. All give information about one or more aspects of the quality (often referred to as attributes)*
384 *of a forecast product.*” A number of papers have also discussed the shortcomings of various statistical
385 metrics (e.g., Boylan and Russell, 2006; Yu et al., 2006; Chai and Draxler, 2014; Emery et al., 2017; Huang
386 et al., 2021; Hodson, 2022).

387 One practical problem associated with this plethora of available metrics is that the use of different metrics
388 by different studies can make comparison of evaluation results between studies difficult. For example,
389 Kang et al. (2005) proposed the use of four metrics as part of an evaluation protocol for a U.S. national AQ
390 forecasting system: mean bias (MB); normalized mean bias (NMB); root mean square error (RMSE); and
391 normalized mean error (NME) (equivalent to normalized mean absolute error). Agnew et al. (2007), on the
392 other hand, proposed the use of mean fractional bias (MFB), mean fractional error (MFE) (or fractional
393 gross error), Pearson correlation coefficient R, centred RMSE (CRMSE), and NSD (normalized standard
394 deviation or variability ratio; not the same as relative standard deviation/coefficient of variation) as
395 evaluation statistics for an ensemble of European regional AQ forecast models. The use of MFB and MFE
396 was supported by Boylan and Russell (2006). Derwent et al. (2010) recommended NMB and the fraction
397 of predictions within a factor of 2 of observations (FAC2) as statistical screening metrics for evaluating the
398 performance of AQ models, while Thunis et al. (2012) recommended NMB, RMSE, CRMSE, R, and
399 normalized mean standard deviation (NMSD) as a core set of metrics for assessing AQ model performance.
400 Marécal et al. (2015) considered MB, RMSE, mean fractional bias (MFB), mean fractional error (MFE),
401 and R to evaluate an ensemble of European regional AQ forecast models, and more recently, observation
402 mean (\bar{O}), model prediction mean (\bar{M}), NMB, normalized RMSE (NRMSE), and Spearman correlation
403 have been added to this set (Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service, 2023). In an effort to address the
404 wide range of metrics being used by the community and facilitate the comparison of evaluation results
405 across studies, Simon et al. (2012) recommended that scores for a minimum set of seven metrics should be

406 reported for future regulatory model evaluations: \bar{O} , \bar{M} , MB, mean absolute error (MAE) or RMSE, NMB
407 or MFB, NME (same as NMAE) or MFE, and R or coefficient of determination (R^2).

408 Several studies have suggested numerical performance benchmarks, goals, criteria, or standards for various
409 statistical metrics that can be used to provide context for model performance relative to previous studies
410 and to assess whether model performance is acceptable for an intended application. The first of these
411 performance benchmarks was suggested for O_3 , where based on analysis of the performance of early urban
412 photochemical grid models the U.S. EPA recommended that NMB values should fall within the ± 0.15 range
413 and NMAE or normalized mean square error (NMSE) values should fall within the ± 0.30 range for O_3
414 concentrations above a threshold of 60 ppbv (e.g., Russell and Dennis, 2000; Solazzo et al., 2012). Simon
415 et al. (2012) provided an analysis of model performance statistics for O_3 , $PM_{2.5}$ total mass and its chemical
416 components, and SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ wet deposition based on an analysis of 69 peer-reviewed articles
417 published between 2005 and 2012 that included operational evaluations of AQ model simulations over
418 North America. They considered 12 metrics but focused on eight of them, for which they showed frequency
419 distributions of scores of each metric across the 69 studies. Emery et al. (2017) built on the Simon et al.
420 (2012) study by analyzing 31 of the articles considered by that earlier study plus seven newer articles with
421 operational evaluation scores that had been published between 2012 and 2015 while focusing on ozone and
422 total/component $PM_{2.5}$ and on three metrics (NMB, NMAE, and R). This set of 38 articles included
423 performance evaluations for a total of 11 different AQ models. One innovation of this paper was the
424 determination of pollutant-specific benchmarks for each metric, where the metric values achieved by the
425 top one-third of model performance evaluations were referred to as “goals” and metric values achieved by
426 the top two-thirds of model performance evaluations were referred to as “criteria” (or “acceptable”) values.
427 Metric values lower than criteria levels thus suggest relatively poor model performance. More recently
428 Huang et al. (2021) applied the Emery et al. (2017) approach to China by analyzing over 300 peer-reviewed
429 AQ modelling articles published in the 2006-2019 period that included operational model evaluations of
430 $PM_{2.5}$ total mass and five chemical components. They proposed benchmark goals and criteria for six
431 metrics: NMB, NMAE, R, fractional bias (FB), fractional error (FE), and Index of Agreement (IOA).
432 Values of benchmarks for the first three metrics determined by Huang et al. (2021) were in some cases
433 more stringent than the Emery et al. (2017) values. Zhai et al. (2024) have since extended the work of
434 Huang et al. (2021) to recommend benchmark goals and criteria for NMB, NMAE, and R for four more
435 species: NO_2 , SO_2 , CO , and PM_{10} .

436 Kelly et al. (2019) noted some limitations of the Emery et al. (2017) study on performance benchmarks,
437 including differences in the statistics reported, in the temporal and spatial scales of the statistics, in the type
438 of modelling performed, in the model domains and grid resolutions that were used, and in uneven emphasis

439 on results from different studies. They addressed these limitations by examining a consistent set of model
440 performance statistics for PM_{2.5} and its chemical components that were calculated for the same domain
441 (conterminous U.S.) and same horizontal grid spacing (12 km) using five different versions of the same
442 model (CMAQ) for annual simulations for the nine-year period from 2007 to 2015. They found that
443 performance statistics varied widely by region and season, raising concerns about the adequacy of a single
444 set of national benchmarks. Emery et al. (2017) also raised concerns about statistics based on excessive
445 spatial or temporal aggregation due to larger influences from compensating effects, and for this reason they
446 excluded articles considered by Simon et al. (2012) that reported statistical metrics over “super-regional”
447 (> 1000 km) scales. While this may be a valid concern, “super-regional” statistics should still have value
448 for the comparison of model performance across different species or model versions or years.

449 Several other performance benchmarks have also been proposed. For the European operational regional
450 AQ forecast ensemble, quarterly RMSE performance targets have been proposed for forecasts of daily
451 maximum NO₂, daily maximum O₃, and daily mean PM_{2.5} surface concentrations of 25 µg·m⁻³, 18 µg·m⁻³,
452 and 18 µg·m⁻³, respectively (Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service, 2023). One last performance
453 benchmark tailored specifically for AQ forecasting applications has been proposed by Vitali et al. (2023)
454 based on RMSE and MFE metrics. Following common practice in the evaluation of weather forecasts (e.g.,
455 Mittermaier, 2008), a persistence model is used as the benchmark, where observations from the previous
456 day are used as forecast values for all forecast days.

457 **S3 Results**

458 **S3.1 Analysis and operational evaluation of AQ-relevant meteorological predictands**

459 **Figure S8** shows the spatial distribution of predicted seasonal-mean 2-meter dry-bulb temperature for each
460 season for 2013–2016 and 2021/22, while **Figs. S9** and **S10** show the corresponding spatial distributions of
461 seasonal mean 10-meter wind speed and precipitation, respectively. Variations between seasons are evident
462 for each year for all three of these fields but are particularly pronounced for dry-bulb temperature. Since
463 biogenic emissions depend directly on surface temperature, the impact of seasonal variations in surface
464 temperature on these emissions is evident in **Table S1** and in **Figs. S21**, **S150**, and **S179** for isoprene (and
465 also **S19** as ETHE is assumed to be a product of isoprene oxidation (Moran et al., 2026)). One feature of
466 note in **Fig. S9** is the occurrence of consistently higher mean wind speeds over the U.S. Great Plains states
467 and Canadian Prairie provinces in all seasons compared to the rest of the continent. A similar result was
468 shown by Vautard et al. (2012) for observed 2006 annual mean wind speeds. Seasonal mean wind speeds
469 over the oceans also display marked differences in **Fig. S9** between seasons. Given the strong dependence
470 of sea-salt emissions on wind speed (Moran et al., 2026), the impact of seasonal variations in wind speed

471 on sea salt levels is also evident in **Figs. 14** and **S30**. For precipitation Fig. 5 from Gilliam et al. (2021),
472 which compares seasonal precipitation patterns over the U.S. in 2016 based on forecasts from two other
473 NWP models and an objective analysis, can be compared to **Fig. S10**. All three NWP models capture some
474 features like high coastal precipitation over the Pacific Northwest states in winter and low precipitation
475 levels over the U.S. desert southwest in summer, but none of the models fully capture the high observed
476 summer precipitation over the northern tier of U.S. midwestern states.

477 Some interannual variations can also be seen for all three meteorological fields in **Figs. S8-S10** over the
478 five years, but these are less pronounced than the interseasonal variations. However, some impacts of
479 interannual variations in dry-bulb temperature and 10 m wind speed are visible in monthly time series of
480 biogenic species (e.g., **Fig. S150**) and sea salt (**Fig. S157**), respectively. Domain-wide analyses of
481 precipitation measurements for these four years also reveal noticeable interannual differences (see **Table 6**
482 and **Figure S161a**), which in turn contribute to interannual differences in domain-wide monthly wet
483 deposition (e.g., June 2013 in **Figs. S162-S164**).

484 Summaries of annual, seasonal, and regional evaluation statistics for weekly precipitation forecasts for
485 2013–2016 are provided by precipitation-chemistry network (CAPMoN, NADP, combined) in **Tables S6A**,
486 **S6S**, and **S10**, respectively. **Table S6A**, which presents annual summary statistics for weekly precipitation
487 forecasts for the CAPMoN and NADP networks individually as well as for the combined networks, is an
488 expansion of **Table 6**, which only shows annual summary statistics for 2013–2016 for the combined
489 networks. It is worth noting that while some CAPMoN annual scores in **Table S6A** such as MB, NMB,
490 and NSD are comparable to those for NADP, others are significantly better. For example, annual RMSE
491 scores have a range of 11.4 to 14.0 mm·week⁻¹ for CAPMoN vs. 18.1 to 21.3 mm·week⁻¹ for NADP, annual
492 NMAE scores have a range of 0.35 to 0.39 for CAPMoN vs. 0.50 to 0.55 for NADP, annual FAC2 scores
493 have a range of 0.73 to 0.78 for CAPMoN vs. 0.54 to 0.56 for NADP, and annual R scores have a range of
494 0.77 to 0.84 for CAPMoN vs. 0.71 to 0.78 for NADP. This is one example of a recurring pattern that the
495 evaluation statistics for an individual network or region can be qualitatively different from those for the
496 combined networks or combined regions, and it should be kept in mind when interpreting the most highly
497 aggregated performance statistics (i.e., annual and all-network or all-station).

498 Seasonal summary statistics for weekly precipitation forecasts for 2013–2016 are presented in **Table S6S**
499 for the CAPMoN and NADP networks individually as well as for the combined networks. Note that for
500 the combined networks the summer has the highest observed seasonal-mean weekly precipitation value,
501 but for the CAPMoN network the autumn has the highest observed seasonal-mean value for three years
502 while for the NADP network it is split between the spring and summer. And similar to the annual scores

503 in **Table S6A**, seasonal RMSE, NMAE, FAC2, and R scores in **Table S6S** were significantly better for
504 CAPMoN than for NADP. On the other hand the range for seasonal NMB values over the four years was
505 comparable across the network groupings: the range for CAPMoN was -0.05 to 0.15, for NADP it was -0.13
506 to 0.15, and for the combined networks it was -0.12 to 0.15. Another feature of **Table S6S** for all three
507 network groupings is that winter consistently has the lowest RMSE, CRMSE, and NMAE values (except
508 for CAPMoN RMSE in 2016) and highest FAC2 and R values while summer has the highest RMSE,
509 CRMSE, and NMAE values and lowest FAC2 and R values. The probable explanation is that synoptic-
510 scale precipitation, which is more predictable, is likeliest to occur in the winter whereas small-scale
511 convective precipitation, which is harder to predict, is likeliest to occur in the summer (e.g., Appel et al.,
512 2011; Gilliam et al., 2021). Benish et al. (2022) observed similar seasonal behaviour in R scores for the
513 WRF NWP model.

514 **Figures S121-S124** show the spatial variation across North America of station-specific annual values of
515 MB, NMB, CRMSE, and R for weekly precipitation forecasts at CAPMoN and NADP stations for each of
516 the four years. Looking at **Figs. S121 to S123** we can see that there are also considerable spatial variations
517 in the scores by measurement site. Many of the largest overpredictions of weekly precipitation at individual
518 stations occurred in the Rocky Mountain region of the western U.S. whereas underpredictions were
519 common in the southeastern and central U.S. (**Fig. S121**). On the other hand, many of the largest annual
520 CRMSE values occurred in the southeastern U.S. (**Fig. S123**), whereas annual R scores tended to be similar
521 everywhere (**Fig. S124**).

522 **Figure S161** shows plots of time series of monthly mean observed and predicted weekly precipitation
523 values plus monthly NMB, FAC2, and R statistics for 2013–2016 for the combined networks. The monthly
524 mean observed and predicted weekly precipitation values mostly clustered in the 15–25 mm·week⁻¹ range
525 for all four years, but both the observed and predicted values for June 2013 were close to 30 mm·week⁻¹.
526 Both observed and predicted monthly mean values of weekly precipitation tended to be higher in the
527 summer and lower in the winter (with the exception of December). In contrast the time series of monthly
528 mean FAC2 and R statistics for weekly precipitation forecasts presented in **Fig. S161** show lower values in
529 summer and higher values in winter, while the monthly NMB time series vary considerably by year for the
530 summer months, with overpredictions in 2013 and 2014 vs. underpredictions in 2015 and 2016.

531 Another temporal analysis, monthly density scatterplots of weekly precipitation forecasts for the combined
532 networks, is presented in **Fig. S190**. One advantage of scatterplots is that they show the totality of all
533 measurement-model pairs rather than some integral measure of those pairs. The scatterplots in **Fig. S190**
534 show noticeably greater scatter (and error) in July vs. the other months, consistent with higher RMSE and

535 CRMSE values and lower FAC2 values in summer (Table S6S; see also Fig. S161). As noted above this
536 greater scatter in July is likely due to the greater challenge of predicting less-organized convective rainfall,
537 which is most common in the summer, and is consistent with the July minimum in monthly FAC2 shown
538 in Fig. S161.

539 Lastly, Table S10 compares annual statistics by region for 2013–2016 by network (CAPMoN, NADP,
540 combined) for predictions of weekly precipitation. The four regions considered correspond to the four
541 continental quadrants shown in Fig. S7. This table in effect provides an aggregated summary of the
542 geographic variations by station in model performance for precipitation that are evident in Figs. S121-S124.
543 If we compare the NADP scores for the western U.S. vs. the eastern U.S., the same pattern occurs for each
544 year: observed annual mean precipitation is lower in the western U.S. than the eastern U.S., annual NMB
545 and NMAE scores are higher (worse) for the western U.S. (cf. Fig. S122), annual FAC2 scores are lower
546 (worse), but annual RMSE scores are lower and, surprisingly, annual R scores are higher (cf. Fig. S124).
547 Appel et al. (2011) also found that bias and error tended to be higher for the western U.S. than for the
548 eastern U.S. for five years of simulations with the MM5 model for 2002-2006. Note one caution for
549 interpretation of Table S10: values of N suggest that NADP has roughly double the number of stations in
550 the eastern U.S. vs. the western U.S. and that CAPMoN has roughly ten times the number of stations in
551 eastern Canada vs. western Canada (see also Fig. S6c).

552 S3.2 Operational evaluation of three key air quality predictands

553 S3.2.1 NO₂ and ozone

554 2021/22 operational forecasts of NO₂ and O₃

555 Table S3A is an expansion of Table 3, where the “A” in the table number denotes “annual”. It lists values
556 of 12 annual evaluation statistics for RAQDPS-OP023 hourly NO₂ and O₃ VMR forecasts for the 2021/22
557 period for the AirNow and NAPS networks individually and combined. While the majority of AirNow and
558 NAPS annual scores in Table S3A were comparable, several for NO₂ were significantly different. In
559 particular, the NO₂ observed annual mean VMR value (\bar{O}) was 7.5 ppbv for AirNow vs. 5.5 ppbv for NAPS,
560 the annual mean NMB score was -0.29 for AirNow vs. -0.05 for NAPS, and the annual mean NSD value
561 was 0.76 for AirNow vs. 0.98 for NAPS. The values of these three statistics in Table 3 for NO₂ for the
562 combined networks were midway between the values for the individual networks. Given that AirNow
563 stations are located in the U.S. and NAPS stations are located in Canada, a likely explanation for the worse
564 NMB score and lower NSD for AirNow is that the U.S. NO_x emissions used by the RAQDPS-OP023 for
565 the 2021/22 forecasts may have been too low whereas the Canadian NO_x emissions were more

566 representative of 2021/22 conditions. In order to detect this possible issue, however, evaluation statistics
567 for the individual networks must be computed and then compared as shown here.

568 **Table S3S** lists *seasonal* values of the same 12 statistics as **Table S3A** for NO₂ and O₃ for the 2021/22
569 period for the AirNow and NAPS networks individually and combined. (The trailing “S” in the table
570 number denotes “seasonal”.) Both observed and predicted seasonal mean NO₂ levels were highest in winter
571 and lowest in summer while both observed and predicted seasonal mean O₃ levels were highest in spring
572 and lowest in autumn, consistent with the model fields in **Fig. 5** and the combined network time series in
573 **Figs. 6-7**. It is also clear from **Table S3S** that model performance varied seasonally. For example, all-
574 station seasonal NMB scores for NO₂ ranged from -0.22 in winter to -0.13 in summer (consistent with
575 **Fig. 6**), NMAE scores ranged from 0.52 in winter to 0.60 in spring and summer, and R scores ranged from
576 0.56 in summer to 0.66 in winter (consistent with **Fig. 6**). For O₃, all-station seasonal NMB scores ranged
577 from -0.14 in summer to 0.05 in winter (consistent with **Fig. 7**), NMAE scores ranged from 0.25 in spring
578 to 0.31 in summer, and R scores ranged from 0.66 in spring to 0.75 in summer and autumn (consistent with
579 **Fig. 7**).

580 The discussion of **Table S3A** above noted differences for NO₂ for 2021/22 in annual values of \bar{O} , NMB,
581 and NSD between the U.S. and Canadian networks. Similar differences are evident in **Table S3S**, where
582 the range in seasonal \bar{O} values for NO₂ in 2021/22 was 5.3 to 10.6 ppbv for AirNow vs. 3.7 to 8.2 ppbv for
583 NAPS, the range for seasonal mean NMB scores was -0.33 to -0.23 for AirNow vs. -0.15 to 0.03 for NAPS,
584 and the range in seasonal mean NSD values was 0.71 to 0.81 for AirNow vs. 0.93 to 1.15 for NAPS. These
585 differences are also consistent with the conjecture that the U.S. NO_x emissions used for the 2021/22
586 forecasts were biased low whereas the Canadian NO_x emissions were more representative. Note also that
587 the yearly increase of U.S. O₃ monitors in the “warm” season (**Table 2**) is not evident in the seasonal N
588 values for AirNow in **Table S3S** due to the screening of observations by station for annual temporal
589 completeness that was performed before data pairing (**Sect. S2.4**).

590 Comparing the all-station seasonal NMB, NMAE, and R scores for the five years from **Table S3S** to
591 recommended benchmark scores as was done in the paper for the annual scores, we see that for NO₂ all but
592 one (19 out of 20) of the all-station seasonal NMB scores and all of the seasonal R scores as well as the five
593 winter NMAE scores met the “acceptable” benchmarks (i.e., above 33rd percentile) recommended for NO₂
594 by Zhai et al. (2024) for NMB, NMAE, and R scores (± 0.30 , 0.55, and 0.50). For most seasons the more
595 stringent benchmark goals for NMB and R (± 0.20 and 0.60) were met as well. Similarly, for O₃ all of the
596 all-station seasonal scores for NMB except four of the spring scores and all of the seasonal scores for R as
597 well as the spring 2022 NMAE score met the acceptable benchmarks recommended for O₃ by Emery et al.

598 (2017) for NMB, NMAE, and R scores (± 0.15 , 0.25, and 0.50). As well, for all five winters the more
599 stringent benchmark goal for NMB (± 0.05) and for all five summers and autumns the more stringent
600 benchmark goal for R (0.75) were met as well for O₃.

601 Time series of five other all-station monthly statistics (observed and predicted median, MB, FAC2, and
602 NSD) are shown in **Figs. S137** and **S138** for 2021/22 for NO₂ and O₃, respectively. These two figures
603 complement **Figs. 6** and **7**. The time series for monthly median NO₂ and O₃ VMRs are similar to the time
604 series for monthly mean VMRs in **Figs. 6** and **7**, respectively, although the monthly median VMR values
605 for NO₂ are about 30% smaller than the monthly mean VMR values. Monthly MB values for both NO₂ and
606 O₃ in **Figs. S137** and **S138** show considerable variation in contrast to the fairly narrow bands of values for
607 monthly NMB in **Figs. 6** and **7**, whereas the small range of monthly FAC2 scores in **Figs. S137** and **S138**
608 stands in contrast to the larger range in monthly CRMSE scores in **Figs. 6** and **7**. Monthly FAC2 scores
609 for NO₂ (**Fig. S137**) are also consistently lower than those for O₃ (**Fig. S138**), and monthly NSD scores for
610 NO₂ are generally smaller than those for O₃.

611 Monthly density scatterplots, which show distributions of individual measurement-model pairs, are highly
612 disaggregated and can provide a useful complement to the above time series of all-station monthly statistics.
613 **Figures S169** and **S170** compare monthly density scatterplots of hourly surface NO₂ and O₃ VMRs,
614 respectively, for both Canadian and U.S. measurements for the four mid-season months of 2021/22.
615 Inspection of the scatterplots for NO₂ shown in **Fig. S169** support some of the conclusions drawn from
616 **Fig. 6**: observed and predicted hourly NO₂ VMRs have a winter maximum and summer minimum, the
617 model underpredicts in all months, and only minor month-to-month variations in FAC2 scores are evident
618 (cf. **Table S3S**). One other characteristic that can be seen uniquely in **Fig. S169** is the obvious precision
619 limitation of NO₂ measurements, almost all of which were reported as whole numbers. Similarly, the four
620 monthly density scatterplots for O₃ shown in **Fig. S170** suggest that April has the highest monthly \bar{O} , \bar{M} ,
621 and FAC2 values and most negative monthly NMB value and July has the largest CRMSE, SDO, and SDM
622 values (cf. **Figs. 6** and **S138**). Note that in preparing these density scatterplots the annual completeness
623 criterion was first applied, which removed all of the measurement-model pairs from those U.S. O₃ monitors
624 that only operate during the U.S. ozone season (so that monthly N values are comparable in **Fig. S170**).

625 **Figures 9** and **10** show annual-mean diurnal time series for all stations of observed and predicted NO₂ and
626 O₃ surface VMRs, respectively, for the 2021/22 period. **Figures S165** and **S166** show the corresponding
627 seasonal-mean diurnal time series. There were considerable variations between seasons for the diurnal time
628 series of both species. Seasonal-mean hourly NO₂ was underpredicted in the winter and autumn at all hours
629 and in the spring for all but one hour (cf. **Table S3S**) but was overpredicted at night in the summer

630 (Fig. S165). As in Fig. 9, observed and predicted NO₂ peaks were aligned for all four seasons and were
631 close to morning and evening rush hours. This good agreement in timing suggests that the diurnal temporal
632 allocation applied to pollutant emissions during emissions processing was representative. Hourly CRMSE
633 values for NO₂ predictions were smallest near noon (LT) in all seasons (cf. Fig. 9). Hourly R values for
634 NO₂ also had a minimum near noon and a maximum at 07 LT in spring and summer as well as a wider
635 range than in the other two seasons. O₃ forecasts had small seasonal-mean hourly NMB values in winter
636 and autumn and consistent negative NMB values at all hours in spring and summer (Fig. S166). Hourly
637 CRMSE values for O₃ predictions, like those for NO₂, were smallest near noon in winter, spring, and autumn
638 but shifted to 07 LT in summer, while R values tended to be highest during the afternoon for all four seasons.

639 Figure S168 provides a spatial disaggregation of Figs. 9 and 10 by showing annual-mean diurnal time
640 series for 2021/22 stratified by *region* (the continental quadrants shown in Fig. S7). For NO₂ the agreement
641 between observed and predicted annual-mean diurnal time series was closest for the two Canadian
642 quadrants whereas hour-by-hour differences were consistently negative and larger for the two U.S.
643 quadrants. Figure 12 showed similar differences between the four regions for time series of monthly means
644 of hourly NO₂ VMR. Figure S168 thus supports the discussion of Fig. 12 (and Table S3A), which
645 suggested that the U.S. NO_x emissions used by the RAQDPS-OP023 for the 2021/22 forecasts may have
646 been biased low. Interestingly, the western U.S. had the highest observed annual-mean hourly NO₂ values
647 in Fig. S168, which is not consistent with the preponderance of NO_x emissions in the eastern U.S. (Fig. S1);
648 sampling bias emphasizing western urban centers may be one explanation of this inconsistency. For O₃
649 annual-mean hourly values for 2021/22 were slightly overpredicted for the eastern U.S. but underpredicted
650 at all hours for the other three quadrants. Observed and predicted daytime annual-mean O₃ peaks were
651 highest for the western U.S. followed by the eastern U.S.

652 Table S7 presents *regional* annual evaluation statistics of NO₂ and O₃ surface VMRs for 2021/22 for the
653 four continental quadrants. Like Fig. 12 these statistics displayed some regional differences. For example,
654 observed but not predicted, annual mean NO₂ values were higher for the two U.S. quadrants than the two
655 Canadian quadrants. Annual NMB values for NO₂ were negative for all four regions but were markedly
656 larger for the two U.S. regions, again consistent with the U.S. NO_x emissions used in the RAQDPS-OP023
657 for 2021/22 being too low. For O₃, on the other hand, observed and predicted annual means and annual
658 CRMSE and R values were highest for the western U.S. while annual NMB was only positive for the eastern
659 U.S. (consistent with Fig. S168).

660

661 2013–2016 hindcasts of NO₂ and O₃

662 In addition to 2021/22 annual scores **Table S3A** also lists values of 12 annual evaluation statistics for hourly
663 NO₂ and O₃ VMR hindcasts for the 2013–2016 period for the AQS and NAPS networks individually and
664 combined (i.e., all stations). While there are many similarities between years in this table, especially
665 amongst the 2013–2016 scores, some differences are also evident between the 2013–2016 scores and the
666 2021/22 scores. For example, for NO₂ annual NMB all of the 2013–2016 scores were positive whereas the
667 2021/22 value was strongly negative. Annual RMSE, NMAE, FAC2, R, and NSD scores for NO₂ were
668 also all lower for 2021/22 than for 2013–2016, which represented an improvement for RMSE and NMAE
669 but not for the others. Annual NMB, RMSE, NMAE, FAC2, and NSD scores for O₃ were also all smaller
670 for 2021/22, which again was a mixed result.

671 The spatial distributions of annual station values of four statistics (MB, NMB, CRMSE and R) for
672 2013–2016 are shown for hourly NO₂ in **Figs. S37** to **S40** (see **Fig. 2** for corresponding 2021/22 plots) and
673 for hourly O₃ in **Figs. S41** to **S44** (see **Fig. 3** for 2021/22). One general comment regarding **Figs. S37** to
674 **S44** is the remarkable consistency from year to year in the spatial distributions of the four statistics. There
675 are also many similarities but some differences as compared to **Figs. 2** and **3**. For example, for NO₂ annual
676 NMB more positive values were evident for the 2013–2016 period than for 2021/22, consistent with
677 **Table S3A**, but lower annual NMB values were still more prevalent in the west for all five years (**Fig. S38**
678 vs. **Fig. 2b**). Annual R values for NO₂ appear to be higher overall for 2013–2016 than for 2021/22 (**Fig. S40**
679 vs. **Fig. 2d**), which is also consistent with **Table S3A**. Annual MB and NMB values for O₃ were generally
680 negative at western stations but positive at eastern stations, particularly at coastal stations, for all five years
681 (**Figs. 2a,b, S41, S42**), again consistent with **Table S3A**.

682 **Figures S11** and **S12** show predicted spatial distributions of *seasonal* mean NO₂ and O₃ surface VMR fields
683 for 2013–2016 and 2021/22 for all four seasons. It is evident from these two figures that seasonal patterns
684 were broadly similar between years but displayed larger variations between seasons. Predicted domain-
685 wide seasonal NO₂ levels were highest in winter and lowest in summer while predicted domain-wide
686 seasonal O₃ levels were highest in spring and lowest in summer or autumn. The same held true over land
687 for the set of station locations (e.g., **Fig. S140**), with the exception of the lowest seasonal O₃ levels, which
688 were predicted (and observed) to occur in the winter for three years and in the autumn for two years
689 (**Table S3S** and **Fig. S141**). It should be kept in mind, though, that a large portion of North America,
690 especially over Canada, lacks AQ monitors so sampling representativeness is an issue, especially when
691 comparing network-mean quantities to domain-mean quantities. One other feature of **Fig. S11** for the

692 winter season in particular was the predicted year-to-year decreases in annual NO₂ VMR levels due to NO_x
693 emission decreases that were noted for **Fig. 13** were even more visible in some of the seasonal plots.

694 In addition to 2021/22 seasonal scores **Table S3S** also lists values of 12 seasonal evaluation statistics for
695 hourly NO₂ and O₃ VMRs for the 2013–2016 period for the AQS and NAPS networks individually and
696 combined. All-station seasonal monthly \bar{O} and \bar{M} values for NO₂ for all five years were highest in winter
697 and lowest in summer, while for O₃ the all-station seasonal monthly \bar{O} and \bar{M} values were highest in spring.
698 It is clear from this table that model skill varied considerably and consistently between seasons for the
699 2013–2016 annual hindcasts. For example, for NO₂ the worst all-station seasonal scores for RMSE and
700 CRMSE but the best all-station seasonal scores for NMB, NMAE, FAC2, and R occurred in the winter for
701 all four years, while the exact opposite was true for the summer (cf. **Fig. S140**). The same was true of the
702 scores for the two individual networks with just three exceptions in 2013. It is also worth noting that the
703 decrease in North American annual NO_x emissions from 2013 to 2021/22 was reflected in monotonic
704 decreases in all-station predicted seasonal mean values of NO₂ for all four seasons. For O₃ the highest
705 observed and predicted all-station seasonal mean VMR values occurred in the spring for all four hindcast
706 years along with the worst all-station seasonal scores for NMB and R and the best seasonal scores for
707 NMAE and FAC2 (cf. **Fig. S141**). The same was true of the O₃ scores for the AQS network with three
708 exceptions but was less true for the NAPS network. Peak all-station and AQS seasonal CRMSE values for
709 O₃ occurred in the summer but in the spring for NAPS.

710 Comparing some of these 2013–2016 seasonal scores in **Table S3S** to benchmark scores, with one
711 exception (summer 2013) all of the all-station seasonal NMB values for NO₂ fell within the acceptable
712 benchmark of ± 0.30 recommended by Zhai et al. (2024) and most fell within the more stringent benchmark
713 goal of ± 0.20 . Only all-station winter NMAE values for NO₂ met the acceptable benchmark of 0.55, but
714 all of the all-station seasonal R values for NO₂ exceeded the benchmark goal of 0.60. For O₃ all of the all-
715 station seasonal NMB values except those for spring fell within the acceptable benchmark of ± 0.15
716 recommended by Emery et al. (2017). No all-station seasonal NMAE score for O₃, on the other hand, met
717 the acceptable benchmark of 0.25, but all of the all-station seasonal R values for O₃ were well above the
718 acceptable benchmark goal of 0.50 and two met the benchmark goal of 0.75. Similar findings applied to
719 the individual network scores for the AQS and NAPS networks.

720 **Figures S140** and **S141** present time series of observed and predicted *monthly* means of hourly NO₂ and
721 O₃ VMRs plus monthly NMB, FAC2, and R scores for 2013–2016 and 2021/22 for all measurement stations
722 in the model domain (cf. **Figs. 6** and **7** for 2021/22 alone). Both observed and predicted NO₂ monthly mean
723 VMRs were highest in winter and lowest in late spring and summer for all five years, with the highest NMB

724 values and lowest FAC2 and R values (i.e., least good performance) found from April to September (**Fig.**
725 [S140](#)). Interestingly, almost all monthly NMB values were positive for 2013–2016 but were uniformly
726 negative for 2021/22. For O₃ the model underpredicted the observed springtime maximum in April and
727 May by about 20%, even though FAC2 values were highest during the spring months (**Fig. S141**). Monthly
728 R values for O₃, on the other hand, were lowest in spring and modestly higher in summer and autumn. The
729 most important message, from these two figures, however, is the similarity between statistical scores for all
730 five years, which suggests that evaluations of this set of five annual simulations do reveal systematic model
731 errors.

732 The sets of all-station hourly NO₂ and O₃ VMR measurement-model pairs used to generate **Figs. S140** and
733 [S141](#) were also separated into urban and rural subsets (see **Sect. 2.5**) for which the same monthly statistics
734 were also calculated. As can be seen in **Figs. S209** and [S210](#), there were some very large differences
735 between the time series of monthly NO₂ statistics for these two subsets. Observed and predicted all-station
736 monthly mean NO₂ VMR values were much lower for rural stations than urban stations, monthly NMB
737 values were positive for most months for both subsets but were roughly twice as large in the summer months
738 for the urban subset, and monthly FAC2 and R values were higher for urban stations. Differences can also
739 be seen for O₃ in **Figs. S211** and [S212](#) between the two subsets but they are reversed for the most part.
740 Observed and predicted all-station monthly mean O₃ VMR values were roughly 5 ppbv higher for rural
741 stations than urban stations, monthly NMB values were similar in magnitude and negative for most months
742 for both subsets, and monthly FAC2 values were lower but monthly R values were higher for urban stations.

743 **Figures S169** and [S170](#) compare monthly density scatterplots of hourly surface NO₂ and O₃ VMRs for the
744 four mid-season months of 2013–2016 as well as 2021/22. The density scatterplots for the same month
745 show strong similarities between years in both figures as do the variations between months, especially for
746 O₃. The sets of monthly density scatterplots also provide visual support for some of the conclusions for
747 **Table S3S**, including higher observed and predicted NO₂ levels in winter and autumn, O₃ underpredictions
748 in spring, and peak O₃ CRMSE values in summer. The limited precision for reported NO₂ measurements
749 (usually limited to whole numbers) is also evident for all five years.

750 Lastly, **Table S7** compares regional annual statistics of NO₂ and O₃ surface VMR for 2013–2016 as well
751 as 2021/22 for the four continental quadrants. This table thus provides an aggregated summary of the
752 geographic variations in model performance evident in **Figs. S37-S44** for 2013–2016. Observed and
753 predicted annual mean NO₂ VMR values were higher for the two U.S. regions than the two Canadian
754 regions for 2013–2016, while annual NMB and FAC2 values for NO₂ were highest for the eastern U.S. for
755 all five years. Note that annual NMAE and R values for NO₂ fell in tight ranges (0.55–0.60 and 0.64–0.70,

756 respectively) for all four regions for 2013–2016. Some systematic regional variations in scores were even
757 more evident for O₃. The western U.S. had the highest observed annual mean O₃ VMRs followed by the
758 eastern U.S. for all five years, but the model hindcasts for 2013–2016 switched this order. Moreover, the
759 largest negative annual NMB values for O₃ occurred for the two western regions for all five years with a
760 range from -0.20 to -0.13, suggestive of problems with the O₃ lateral boundary conditions used by the
761 RAQDPS-OP023 on the western boundary (also suggested by **Fig. 12**). The largest annual CRMSE values
762 for O₃ were consistently those for the western U.S., followed in descending order by the eastern U.S.,
763 western Canada, and eastern Canada. Western Canada also had the lowest (worst) annual FAC2 and R
764 values for O₃ for all five years whereas eastern Canada had the highest annual FAC2 values and the western
765 U.S. had the highest annual R values for all five years.

766 **S3.2.2 PM_{2.5} total mass**

767 2021/22 operational forecasts of PM_{2.5} total mass

768 **Table S3A** is an expansion of **Table 3**. It lists values of 12 annual evaluation statistics for RAQDPS-
769 OP023 hourly PM_{2.5} surface concentration forecasts for 2021/22 for the AirNow and NAPS networks both
770 individually and combined. The separate AirNow and NAPS annual scores in **Table S3A** for hourly PM_{2.5}
771 forecasts were comparable to the combined scores for 2021/22, including annual NMB values of -0.32 for
772 AQS and -0.29 for NAPS vs. -0.31 for the combined networks.

773 **Table S3S** lists *seasonal* values of the same 12 statistics as **Table S3A** for RAQDPS-OP023 hourly PM_{2.5}
774 forecasts for the 2021/22 period for the AirNow and NAPS networks both individually and combined.
775 Seasonal NMB values were negative for all four seasons, with a large all-station seasonal NMB minimum
776 of -0.51 in the summer increasing to a maximum of -0.13 in the winter. The corresponding seasonal NMB
777 values for AQS and NAPS individually fell in similar ranges: -0.49 to -0.15 and -0.61 to -0.04, respectively.
778 Other statistics also showed marked seasonal variations. The summer had the worst scores overall for AQS
779 only, NAPS only, and all stations, including the highest MB, CRMSE, and NMAE values and the lowest
780 FAC2, R, and NSD values. With the exception of summer, all of the all-station seasonal NMB scores for
781 hourly PM_{2.5} did meet the “acceptable” benchmark of ±0.30 recommended by Emery et al. (2017), but none
782 of the all-station seasonal NMAE scores met the acceptable benchmark of 0.50, and only the NAPS winter
783 and spring R scores and all-station winter R scores met the acceptable benchmark of 0.40.

784 All-station monthly time series of five additional statistics (observed and predicted *median* PM_{2.5}
785 concentration, MB, FAC2, and NSD) for 2021/22 are shown in **Figure S139**, which complements **Fig. 8**.
786 Appel et al. (2008) have argued that the median is a better measure of the central tendency of PM_{2.5}
787 concentration, which is generally not normally distributed. Like the time series of observed and predicted

788 monthly means shown in **Fig. 8**, the time series of observed and predicted monthly median PM_{2.5}
789 concentration had peaks in both winter and summer. Observed and predicted monthly median values,
790 however, were lower than the corresponding monthly mean values, which is consistent with a log-normal
791 distribution, and the gap between observed and predicted monthly median values in the winter (but not
792 summer) was even larger than the gap for monthly mean values (**Fig. 8**). The lowest all-station monthly
793 MB value (about $-7 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) occurred in August as did the lowest NSD value, while monthly FAC2 values
794 were slightly lower in spring and summer than the rest of the year. The observed winter median PM_{2.5}
795 concentration peak may be due to reduced vertical mixing over large emissions sources such as cities and
796 to reduced wet removal, whereas the observed summer peak may be due to high PM_{2.5}-POM levels
797 associated with summer wildfire emissions (not in model) and hghPM_{2.5}-SOM levels associated with
798 summer emissions of biogenic precursors (see **Sect. 3.3.2** and **Figs. S25–S27, S154, and S155**).

799 **Figure S171** also complements **Figs. 8** and **S139** with another type of monthly analysis. It shows all-station
800 monthly density scatterplots of PM_{2.5} hourly surface concentrations for the four mid-season months of
801 2021/22. A general tendency to model underprediction (e.g., centre of mass below 1:1 line) and low
802 correlation (i.e., limited linearity) is evident in these scatterplots, as is the “quantization” introduced by
803 many stations reporting PM_{2.5} hourly surface concentrations as whole numbers. These density scatterplots
804 also display some differences between the four months in 2021/22 as do the marginal frequency
805 distributions.

806 **Figure 11** shows annual-mean diurnal time series for hourly PM_{2.5} surface concentration for all stations for
807 2021/22. **Figure S167** shows corresponding seasonal-mean diurnal time series for the four seasons.
808 Considerable interseasonal variation is evident. The overall observed magnitude of PM_{2.5} was high in the
809 winter, decreased in the spring, climbed even higher in the summer, and then decreased again in the autumn,
810 consistent with **Fig. 8** and **Table S3S**. Predicted PM_{2.5} seasonal magnitudes, on the other hand, were
811 highest in winter and lowest in spring and summer, again consistent with **Fig. 8** and **Table S3S**. Moreover,
812 as noted in the discussion of **Table S3S**, overall performance was least good for the summer, and the
813 statistics shown in **Fig. S167** support this conclusion: diurnal NMB and CRMSE values were largest for
814 the summer and seasonal R values were the lowest. It is also worth noting that the predicted diurnal range
815 of hourly PM_{2.5} concentrations was larger than the observed diurnal range for all four seasons, and that the
816 observed diurnal range varied by season, from largest in the winter to smallest in the summer. One possible
817 explanation for the seasonal variation of the observed diurnal range is that the winter diurnal cycle is
818 dominated by local emissions with marked diurnal variations and by reduced vertical mixing whereas the
819 summer diurnal cycle is dominated by secondary PM_{2.5} sources and regional transport, which favours
820 reduced variations.

821 **Figure S168** also complements **Fig. 11**. It shows diurnal time series of observed and predicted annual-
822 mean $PM_{2.5}$ hourly surface concentrations for 2021/22 by region for the four continental quadrants shown
823 in **Fig. S7**. The model was biased low for all four regions, but the bias was smallest for eastern Canada and
824 similar for the other three regions (cf. **Table S7**). Observed annual-mean hourly concentration values were
825 similar for the two U.S. regions and higher than the two Canadian regions, which were also similar, whereas
826 predicted annual-mean hourly concentration values for eastern Canada were similar to those for the two
827 U.S. regions and markedly higher than those for western Canada. And as was the case for **Fig. 11**, the
828 predicted diurnal range was larger than the observed range for all four regions, and especially for eastern
829 Canada.

830 Lastly, **Table S7** compares 12 annual statistics for $PM_{2.5}$ hourly surface concentration by region for
831 2021/22. As suggested by **Fig. 12**, annual NMB values are negative for all four regions but are smallest
832 for eastern Canada (-0.19) and largest for western Canada (-0.41). Western Canada also has the second-
833 highest annual CRMSE value, the highest annual NMAE value, and the lowest annual values of FAC2, R,
834 and NSD in 2021/22. A likely explanation for these poor scores is that 2021 was a near-record wildfire
835 year in western Canada (cf. **Table A4**).

836 2013–2016 hindcasts of $PM_{2.5}$ total mass

837 In addition to 2021/22 annual scores **Table S3A** also lists values of 12 annual evaluation statistics for
838 hindcasts of hourly $PM_{2.5}$ for the 2013–2016 period for the AQS and NAPS networks individually and
839 combined. The annual scores for AQS and NAPS are comparable overall, although AQS scores are better
840 for NMAE and FAC2. In addition, NAPS scores for CRMSE, NMAE, and R are markedly worse for 2016
841 compared to 2013–2015 even though 2016 was a low wildfire year in Canada (**Table A4**).

842 The spatial distributions of annual station values of four statistics (MB, NMB, CRMSE, and R) for 2013–
843 2016 are shown for hourly $PM_{2.5}$ in **Figs. S45–S48** (cf. **Fig. 4** for 2021/22). Visual inspection of **Figs. S45–**
844 **S48** suggests an overall year-to-year consistency in patterns for each of the four statistics for the four-year
845 period. Annual MB and NMB values, for example, tend to be negative, with few positive values (i.e.,
846 overpredictions), and these tend to be located along the west coast and northeast seaboard (**Figs. S45** and
847 **S46**). Annual CRMSE values tend to be higher on the west coast and along the continental divide, while
848 annual R values tend to be higher on the west coast and in the northeastern U.S. and lower in the
849 southeastern U.S. and the continental interior. There are also some differences between these figures and
850 **Fig. 4**. For example, annual MB and NMB values for 2021/22 appear to be more negative (i.e., worse) than
851 those for 2013–2016, consistent with **Table 3**. Annual CRMSE (and RMSE) values for 2021/22, on the
852 other hand, are lower than those for 2013–2016 (cf. **Fig. 4c** vs. **Fig. S47**).

853 **Figure S13** compares the corresponding predicted spatial distributions of *seasonal* mean PM_{2.5} surface
854 concentration for 2013–2016 and 2021/22 for all four seasons. Like the spatial distributions of seasonal
855 mean NO₂ and O₃ surface VMR presented in **Figs. S11** and **S12**, the seasonal mean PM_{2.5} concentration
856 patterns are broadly similar from year to year but display larger differences each year between seasons. For
857 example, seasonal PM_{2.5} surface concentrations over the Pacific Ocean, where the primary chemical
858 component is sea salt, are largest in the autumn and winter when surface winds are strongest, and smallest
859 in the summer when surface winds are weakest (cf. **Fig. S9**). There is also a regional peak in PM_{2.5} over
860 the southeastern U.S. in the summer that is likely driven by increased biogenic SOM levels due to increased
861 biogenic VOC emissions in the summer (see **Table S1** and **Sec. 3.3.2**). There are some interannual
862 differences evident in **Fig. S13** as well. For example, year-to-year variations are visible over the oceans in
863 all seasons, consistent with interannual differences in seasonal mean surface wind speed (**Fig. S9**), and
864 downward trends in seasonal mean PM_{2.5} levels are visible over North America between 2013 and 2021/22,
865 consistent with the monotonic decrease in both primary PM_{2.5} emissions and SO₂ and NO_x precursor
866 emissions over this period (**Table 1**).

867 In addition to 2021/22 seasonal scores, **Table S3S** lists seasonal values of the same 12 statistics as
868 **Table S3A** for hourly PM_{2.5} for 2013–2016. Marked but consistent seasonal variations are evident in the
869 all-station statistical scores for the four hindcast years. All-station observed seasonal mean PM_{2.5} surface
870 concentrations were highest in the winter for three years (2013, 2014, 2016) and in the summer for 2015
871 and 2021/22, both of which were high wildfire years (see **Table A4**); they were lowest in the spring for
872 four years and in autumn for 2015 (cf. **Fig. S142**). All-station predicted seasonal mean PM_{2.5} surface
873 concentrations, on the other hand, were highest in the winter for all five years and were lowest in the
874 summer for 2013–2016 and second-lowest in 2021/22 (spring was lowest). All-station seasonal NMB
875 values were closest to zero (best) in the autumn for 2013–2016 and winter for 2021/22 but had their largest
876 negative (worst) values in the summer for all five years (-0.14 to -0.51) (cf. **Fig. S142**). All-station seasonal
877 NMAE values, on the other hand, fell in the range 0.63 to 0.79 for the five years with summer minima
878 (best) for 2013–2016 and a spring minimum for 2021/22. All-station seasonal FAC2 values fell in a tight
879 range (0.46 to 0.51) for 2013–2016 but had a slightly lower range (0.43 to 0.49) for 2021/22 (cf. **Fig. S142**).
880 And all-station seasonal R values, which ranged from 0.07 to 0.40 over the five years, were generally
881 highest in the winter (second-highest for 2013) and lowest in the summer, except in 2016 when it was
882 lowest in spring (cf. **Fig. S142**). Note that the large Fort McMurray, Alberta wildfire occurred in May 2016
883 (e.g., Vaillant, 2023). Comparing some of these seasonal scores to the benchmark scores recommended by
884 Emery et al. (2017) for PM_{2.5}, all of the all-station seasonal NMB scores for 2013–2016 except for summers
885 2014 and 2015 met the “acceptable” benchmark of ± 0.30 , but none of the all-station seasonal NMAE scores

886 met the “acceptable” benchmark of 0.50 and only one all-station seasonal R score met the “acceptable”
887 benchmark of 0.40.

888 **Figure S142** compares time series of observed and predicted all-station monthly mean values of PM_{2.5}
889 hourly surface concentration and corresponding monthly NMB, FAC2, and R values for 2013–2016 and
890 2021/22 (cf. **Fig. 8**). The monthly variation of these time series is similar between years, although the time
891 series for 2021/22 are outliers to a degree. The observed monthly mean PM_{2.5} time series had a local
892 maximum in the summer for all five years that was not present in the predicted monthly mean time series;
893 this is due in part to the RAQDPS-OP023 not including wildfire emissions (see **Sect. 4.2**). Monthly NMB
894 values for 2013–2016 were all above -0.10 for the cold-season months but fell below -0.20 for May to
895 August for 2013–2016 and even lower for 2021/22. Monthly FAC2 values ranged from 0.40 to 0.50 for all
896 months, while monthly R values were above 0.30 for the cold-season months but were lower for the summer
897 months.

898 The all-station hourly PM_{2.5} concentration measurement-model pairs used to generate **Fig. S142** were also
899 separated into an urban subset and a rural subset for which the same statistics were calculated. As shown
900 in **Figs. S213** and **S214** there were some striking differences between the time series of monthly PM_{2.5}
901 statistics for these two subsets. Monthly \bar{O} and \bar{M} values were markedly higher for the urban time series
902 (**Fig. S213**) than the rural time series (**Fig. S214**). A possible reason is that on-road mobile emissions of
903 PM_{2.5}, including road dust and vehicle exhaust, are higher in urban areas than in rural areas, which will
904 directly impact local PM_{2.5} concentrations. Moreover, monthly NMB values were actually positive for the
905 urban subset except for the May–August period and all were greater than -0.25. For the rural subset, on the
906 other hand, predicted monthly NMB values all fall below -0.25. Monthly FAC2 scores were also higher
907 for all months for the urban subset but monthly R scores were comparable. This comparison shows that
908 the model PM_{2.5} underprediction is mainly a rural issue, which is a valuable insight.

909 **Figure S171** compares monthly density scatterplots of hourly PM_{2.5} surface concentrations for the four
910 mid-season months of 2013–2016 in addition to 2021/22. Like the domain-scale characterization presented
911 by **Fig. S142**, these monthly density scatterplots were broadly similar from year to year but displayed larger
912 differences between months for each year (as do the marginal frequency distributions). A general tendency
913 to model underprediction and low correlation was also evident in all of these scatterplots.

914 **Table S7** compares regional annual statistics for hourly PM_{2.5} surface concentration hindcasts for 2013–
915 2016 as well as for 2021/22. In effect this table provides an aggregated summary of the geographic
916 variations in model performance evident in **Figs. S45–S48** for the 2013–2016 hindcasts. Regional annual

917 NMB scores for 2013–2016, which had a range from -0.20 to 0.09, were better than those for 2021/22 (-0.41
918 to -0.19). Interestingly, annual NMB values were positive for the western U.S. for the four years but non-
919 positive for the other three regions. Regional annual CRMSE values were lowest for eastern Canada for
920 all four years and highest for the western U.S. except for 2016, the year of the Fort McMurray wildfire, for
921 which western Canada had an unusually high value. Regional annual NMAE values, by contrast, were
922 consistently lowest for the eastern U.S. (0.60–0.63) and highest for western Canada (0.84–0.87). Regional
923 annual FAC2 values were highest for the eastern U.S. (0.54–0.56) and lowest for western Canada (0.37–
924 0.38). Regional annual R values were highest for eastern Canada (0.45–0.47) and lowest for western
925 Canada (0.04–0.26) or the western U.S. (0.24 in 2013). In 2016 SDO also had an extreme value for western
926 Canada of $28.1 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, again possibly related to the Fort McMurray wildfire. Annual overall model
927 performance for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ hourly surface concentration for 2013–2016 was best for eastern Canada and the
928 eastern U.S. and, as in 2021/22, worst for western Canada. In terms of the NMB, NMAE, and R
929 “acceptability” benchmarks for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass surface concentration recommended by Emery et al.
930 (2017), the annual NMB scores for all regions and years met the recommended NMB threshold of ± 0.30 ,
931 none of the annual NMAE scores met the threshold of 0.50, and only the annual R scores for eastern Canada
932 met the threshold of 0.40.

933 Turning to the daily gravimetric $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ measurements for 2013–2016, [Table S5A](#) is an expansion of
934 [Table 5](#). It lists values of 12 all-station annual evaluation statistics for daily $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ forecasts by year for the
935 AQS, IMPROVE, and NAPS networks individually as well as for the combined networks shown in [Table](#)
936 [5](#). One important finding from [Table S5A](#) is that annual \bar{O} and \bar{M} values were all larger for the AQS and
937 NAPS networks than they were for the IMPROVE network. Another important finding relates to model
938 bias. Although the all-station annual NMB values were close to zero, ranging from 0.0 to 0.07, the
939 corresponding values for the individual networks were very different: for AQS and NAPS they were
940 uniformly positive, with ranges from 0.03 to 0.09 and 0.33 to 0.62, respectively, whereas for IMPROVE
941 they were uniformly negative with a range from -0.34 to -0.30. Annual CRMSE values for AQS and NAPS
942 are also uniformly higher than they are for IMPROVE. A likely explanation for these three differences
943 may be linked to differences in a key characteristic of the three networks, specifically that AQS consists of
944 mainly urban (and eastern) stations, IMPROVE consists of mainly rural (and western) stations, and NAPS
945 consists of mainly urban (and northern) stations. Recall that [Figs. S213](#) and [S214](#) showed large differences
946 between statistics for urban and rural stations.

947 [Figs. S194–S197](#) show the spatial distributions of station-specific annual values of four statistics (MB,
948 NMB, CRMSE, and R) for 2013–2016 for daily gravimetric $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass measurements. These figures
949 thus provide a detailed breakdown of some of the domain-level statistics in [Table S5A](#) and are counterparts

950 to **Figs. S45–S48** for hourly continuous PM_{2.5} measurements. Annual MB and annual NMB scores, which
951 should not be affected by temporal aggregation (i.e., hourly vs. daily), were slightly higher for the
952 gravimetric measurements, consistent with **Table S5A** vs. **Table S3A**. Annual NMB scores also tended to
953 be more negative in the western U.S. than the eastern U.S., which is consistent with the majority of
954 IMPROVE monitors being located in western rural areas and the majority of AQS gravimetric monitors
955 being located in eastern urban areas (see **Fig. S6a**). Also, the occurrence of both positive and negative
956 annual NMB values on the west and east coasts in **Fig. S46** may reflect the presence of urban and rural
957 stations in relatively close proximity. Annual CRMSE scores were also lower across the domain for the
958 daily gravimetric measurements (**Fig. S196** vs. **Fig. S47**), while annual R scores were higher across most
959 of the domain but particularly in eastern North America (**Fig. S197** vs. **Fig. S48**). However, both CRMSE
960 and R scores will be affected by temporal aggregation, which may explain in part the better scores in **Figs.**
961 **S196** and **S197** vs. **Figs. S47** and **S48**. Note that many of the lowest annual CRMSE scores are in the
962 western U.S. where IMPROVE monitors predominate, consistent with **Table S5A**.

963 Seasonal and monthly evaluation scores based on the daily gravimetric PM_{2.5} mass measurements are also
964 available for the 2013–2016 hindcasts. **Table S5S** lists seasonal scores for the daily gravimetric PM_{2.5}
965 concentrations, including NMB, CRMSE, NMAE, FAC2, and R, and these scores were generally better
966 than the corresponding seasonal scores for hourly PM_{2.5} concentration measurements (**Table S3S**). For
967 example, seasonal NMB values were less negative for the gravimetric PM_{2.5} measurements than the
968 continuous measurements by roughly 0.10, with values ranging from 0.14 to 0.16 vs. 0.02 to 0.06 for winter,
969 -0.04 to 0.06 vs. -0.12 to -0.03 for spring, -0.19 to -0.04 vs. -0.31 to -0.14 for summer, and 0.05 to 0.17 vs.
970 -0.02 to 0.01 for autumn. This comparison for seasonal NMB scores is actually mixed since the gravimetric
971 scores were only better in the spring and summer, but the comparison for the other four statistics is much
972 more one-sided in favour of the gravimetric measurement scores. If we again consider the NMB, NMAE,
973 and R acceptability benchmarks for PM_{2.5} recommended by Emery et al. (2017), all 16 of the all-station
974 seasonal NMB scores met the NMB threshold of ± 0.30 (vs. 14 for the continuous measurements), all four
975 of the all-station summer NMAE scores met the threshold of 0.50 (vs. zero), and 13 of the 16 all-station
976 seasonal R scores met the threshold of 0.40 (vs. one).

977 As was the case for **Table S5A**, however, the seasonal scores for the individual networks in **Table S5S**
978 display marked differences. For 2013–2016 the minimum AQS seasonal \bar{O} and \bar{M} values (7.1 and
979 $7.0 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, respectively) were both greater than the maximum IMPROVE seasonal \bar{O} and \bar{M} values (6.5
980 and $3.2 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). Seasonal \bar{O} and \bar{M} values for AQS were also consistently highest in the winter whereas
981 seasonal \bar{O} and \bar{M} values for IMPROVE were consistently highest in the summer. Some seasonal NMB

982 values for AQS were negative and some were positive for each year whereas they were consistently negative
983 for IMPROVE and consistently positive for NAPS. Seasonal CRMSE values for AQS were greater than
984 those for IMPROVE for every season except summer 2015, and seasonal FAC2 values for AQS were
985 significantly larger than those for IMPROVE for every season. As noted in the discussion of **Table S5A**,
986 these differences are likely due to the predominantly urban character of the AQS and NAPS networks vs.
987 the predominantly rural character of the IMPROVE network. The AQS and NAPS seasonal scores for
988 gravimetric PM_{2.5} measurements do seem to align with the monthly time series for hourly PM_{2.5}
989 measurements at urban stations (**Fig. S213**) while the IMPROVE seasonal scores for gravimetric PM_{2.5}
990 measurements align with the monthly time series for hourly PM_{2.5} measurements at rural stations
991 (**Fig. S214**).

992 **Figure S198** compares time series of all-station monthly means and monthly NMB, FAC2, and R scores
993 for daily gravimetric PM_{2.5} measurements for 2013–2016, and thus is the counterpart to **Fig. S142** for hourly
994 continuous PM_{2.5} measurements. Two features present in both **Figs. S198** and **S142** are the winter and
995 summer peaks in observed monthly mean PM_{2.5} concentrations (see **Section S3.3.2** for further discussion).
996 As noted in the discussion of **Table S5S** the monthly NMB scores for the daily gravimetric measurements
997 for spring and summer were better but the monthly NMB scores for the winter and autumn had a higher
998 bias for most months than those for the hourly continuous PM_{2.5} measurements. Similarly, the better
999 seasonal FAC2 and R scores for the daily gravimetric PM_{2.5} measurements listed in **Table S5S** vs. the
1000 corresponding scores for the hourly continuous PM_{2.5} measurements listed in **Table S3S** are also echoed in
1001 **Figs. S198** and **S142** by the higher monthly FAC2 and R scores in all months for the gravimetric
1002 measurements.

1003 Lastly, **Fig. S199** compares all-station monthly density scatterplots of daily gravimetric PM_{2.5} surface
1004 concentrations for the 16 mid-season months of 2013–2016. It is thus the counterpart to **Fig. S171** for
1005 hourly continuous PM_{2.5} measurements. The scatterplots in **Fig. S199** are more compact and linear than
1006 those in **Fig. S171**, consistent with the higher monthly FAC2 and R scores and lower CRMSE scores noted
1007 above for the daily gravimetric PM_{2.5} measurements in **Table S5S** and **Fig. S198**.

1008 **S3.3 Expanded evaluation for additional species and processes**

1009 **S3.3.1 Other gases**

1010 **Table S4A** is an expansion of **Table 4** as it gives annual evaluation scores for the AMoN, AQS, CAPMoN,
1011 CASTNET, and NAPS networks individually and combined (i.e., all-station). Note that the AQS scores

1012 for ETHE, HCHO, and ISOP come from the NATTS and PAMS networks (see [Table S2a](#)). We can
1013 examine [Table S4A](#) pollutant by pollutant:

- 1014 • The locations of Canadian and U.S. stations measuring NO are shown in [Fig. S4a](#). NO and NO₂ are
1015 both primary pollutants that are emitted mainly by combustion processes and are very tightly coupled
1016 by ozone chemistry. All-station annual \bar{O} and \bar{M} concentration values for NO are roughly half the NO₂
1017 values. All-station annual NMB values for hourly NO VMR for 2013–2016, which ranged from 0.09
1018 to 0.32, were higher (worse) than those for hourly NO₂ VMR (0.08 to 0.11) as were all-station annual
1019 NMAE scores, which ranged from 1.21 to 1.34 vs. 0.58. All-station annual FAC2 and R scores were
1020 considerably lower (worse) for NO than NO₂: 0.28 to 0.29 vs. 0.57 to 0.59; and 0.41 to 0.42 vs. 0.68,
1021 respectively. Further to the discussion of smoothness for primary and secondary pollutants in
1022 [Sect. 3.2.1](#), it is interesting to note that both observed and predicted all-station annual CV values for
1023 NO for 2013–2016 (3.14 to 3.27; 3.03 to 3.14) from [Table S4A](#) are approximately three times than
1024 those for NO₂ (1.09 to 1.13; 1.03 to 1.10) from [Table S3A](#). The NO field is thus considerably less
1025 smooth than the NO₂ field even though both species are primary pollutants and have the same sources
1026 (except for soil NO emissions). This reduced smoothness in the NO field could be due in part to the
1027 speciation profiles used to process NO_x emissions, which assume that NO constitutes about 90% of
1028 NO_x emissions (e.g., Czader et al., 2015; Matthias et al., 2021; Brimblecombe et al., 2023).
- 1029 • All-station annual non-dimensional scores (NMB, NMAE, FAC2, R) for hourly NO_x VMR tended, as
1030 might be expected, to fall between scores for NO and NO₂ whereas dimensional scores (\bar{O} , \bar{M} , MB,
1031 RMSE, CRMSE) were roughly equal to the sum of the corresponding NO and NO₂ dimensional scores.
- 1032 • The locations of stations measuring HNO₃ are shown in [Fig. S4c](#). HNO₃ is a secondary pollutant and
1033 a termination product of NO_x-O₃ chemistry. As discussed in [Sect. 2.4](#), all annual scores for this
1034 secondary pollutant have been calculated with actual or constructed weekly measurements as
1035 constrained by the CASTNET sampling period ([Table S2a](#)). Annual \bar{O} and \bar{M} VMR values in
1036 [Table S4A](#) were both higher for CASTNET (U.S.) than for CAPMoN (Canada) for all years, consistent
1037 with [Fig. S15](#). All-station annual NMB values for HNO₃ were positive for all four years, with a range
1038 from 0.16 to 0.33 (which mirrors a consistent underprediction of PM_{2.5}-NO₃ discussed in [Sect. 3.3.2](#)).
1039 All-station annual NMAE values ranged from 0.42 to 0.53, annual FAC2 values ranged from 0.75 to
1040 0.81, and annual R values ranged from 0.64 to 0.69. These annual NMAE, FAC2, and R scores, while
1041 for a longer sampling period, were slightly better than the corresponding scores for hourly NO₂ and not
1042 far behind those for hourly O₃ ([Table S3A](#)). For another comparison with O₃, observed and predicted
1043 all-station annual CV values for HNO₃ ranged from 0.73 to 0.76 and 0.69 to 0.76 ([Table S4A](#))

1044 compared with 0.51 to 0.52 and 0.54 to 0.59 for O₃ (Table S3A). These values are all considerably
1045 lower than those for NO₂, consistent with a secondary pollutant.

1046 • The locations of U.S. AMoN stations measuring NH₃ are shown in Fig. S4c while the locations of
1047 Canadian NAPS stations measuring NH₃ are shown in Fig. S6b. NH₃ is a primary pollutant that does
1048 not undergo gas-phase chemistry but does participate in inorganic heterogeneous chemistry. As
1049 discussed in Sect. 2.4, all annual scores for NH₃ have been calculated with actual or constructed
1050 *biweekly* measurements based on the AMoN sampling period (Table S2a). Interestingly, annual \bar{O} and
1051 \bar{M} concentration values for the Canadian network in Table S4A were roughly double those for the U.S.
1052 network but are based on roughly one-sixth the number of stations (Table S2b). All-station annual
1053 NMB scores for NH₃ ranged from -0.42 to -0.47, indicating a significant underprediction for all four
1054 years (which mirrors the consistent overprediction of PM_{2.5}-NH₄ discussed in Sect. 3.3.2). All-station
1055 annual NMAE values ranged from 0.57 to 0.62, suggesting a preponderance of underpredictions when
1056 compared to NMB scores. Lastly, all-station annual FAC2 and R values for NH₃ ranged from 0.47 to
1057 0.57 and from 0.34 to 0.51, respectively, while observed and predicted all-station annual CV values for
1058 NH₃ ranged from 1.68 to 2.07 and 1.29 to 1.43, higher than those for NO₂ and reflective of a primary
1059 species.

1060 • The SO₂ North American monitoring network is broadly similar to that for CO (Demerjian, 2007) and
1061 includes hourly measurements from AQS and NAPS, daily measurements from CAPMoN, and weekly
1062 measurements from CASTNET. SO₂ is a primary pollutant that is emitted mainly by large point sources
1063 such as fossil fuel power plants and non-ferrous smelters. As discussed in Sect. 2.4, all annual scores
1064 for SO₂ have been calculated with actual or constructed weekly measurements as constrained by the
1065 CASTNET sampling period (Table S2a). Note that the four measurement networks are intended for
1066 quite different purposes. AQS and NAPS monitors may be deployed in urban centres or in the vicinity
1067 of large SO₂ point sources whereas CAPMoN and CASTNET monitors were intended to provide
1068 regionally representative measurements and were deliberately located away from large emissions
1069 sources (e.g., Schwede et al., 2011). It is thus not surprising that annual \bar{O} and \bar{M} VMR values in
1070 Table S4A were both markedly higher for AQS and NAPS than for CASTNET and CAPMoN for all
1071 four years. All-station annual NMB values for SO₂ listed in Table 4 were positive for all four years,
1072 with a range from 0.43 to 0.60. This overprediction of SO₂ mirrors underpredictions of PM_{2.5}-SO₄ for
1073 all four years (Sect. 3.3.2). Interestingly, the annual NMB values for the two Canadian networks, which
1074 ranged from 0.77 to 1.19, were markedly higher than those for the two U.S. networks, which ranged
1075 from 0.23 to 0.53. This difference does raise concerns about the magnitude of the Canadian SO₂
1076 emissions used for 2013–2016. All-station annual NMAE values were large and ranged from 0.99 to

1077 1.11, but values for CASTNET were lower (better) than those for the other three networks. All-station
1078 annual FAC2 values for SO₂ ranged from 0.45 to 0.49, but CASTNET values were considerably higher
1079 (better) than the other three networks and annual NMAE values for CAPMoN were only slightly larger
1080 than annual NMB values. All-station annual R values ranged from 0.35 to 0.40, but values for
1081 CAPMoN and CASTNET were marked higher (better) than those for AQS and NAPS, ranging from
1082 0.72 to 0.88. Lastly, observed and predicted all-station annual CV values for SO₂ ranged from 1.42 to
1083 1.72 and 1.28 to 1.61, respectively, comparable to values for NH₃. Zhai et al. (2024) have recommended
1084 NMB, NMAE, and R performance benchmarks for SO₂ predictions. AQS and CASTNET annual NMB
1085 values met the acceptable threshold of ± 0.50 in 2015 and 2016 as did the all-station annual NMB values,
1086 annual NMAE values did not meet even the acceptable threshold of 0.70 except for CASTNET, and
1087 all-station annual R scores met the acceptable threshold of 0.35 for all four years but not the benchmark
1088 goal of 0.55, whereas CAPMoN and CASTNET values all met the benchmark goal.

1089 • The North American monitoring network for CO is quite extensive (**Fig. S4b**). CO is both a primary
1090 and secondary pollutant: like NO and NO₂, it is emitted by combustion processes, including biomass
1091 burning, but it is also a product of methane and VOC oxidation (e.g., Holloway et al., 2000). All-station
1092 annual NMB scores for hourly CO VMR for 2013–2016 had a narrow range from -0.05 to 0.12, but
1093 annual NMB scores were considerably higher for the NAPS network (-0.11 to 0.42) than the AQS
1094 network (-0.04 to 0.08). All-station annual NMAE values ranged from 0.55 to 0.61 but were also higher
1095 for the NAPS network (0.63 to 0.72) than the AQS network (0.52 to 0.60). All-station annual FAC2
1096 scores for CO were quite high and ranged from 0.69 to 0.74 (slightly better than NO₂), whereas annual
1097 R scores were less good, with values from 0.42 to 0.43 for 2013 to 2015 and only 0.14 for 2016 (and
1098 even lower for NAPS). Zhai et al. (2024) have recommended NMB, NMAE, and R performance
1099 benchmarks for CO predictions. All-station annual NMB values were all well within the benchmark
1100 goal of ± 0.25 , all-station annual NMAE values met the benchmark goal of 0.60 for three years (2013
1101 value was 0.61), and all-station annual R scores for 2013–2015 met the acceptable benchmark of 0.40
1102 but not the benchmark goal of 0.60. Lastly, observed and predicted all-station annual CV values for
1103 CO ranged from 0.85 to 0.96 for 2013–2015 and 1.96 for 2016 and from 0.78 to 0.87, respectively, in
1104 between values for HNO₃ and NO₂.

1105 • A limited set of hourly measurements of ethene VMR was available for 2013–2016 from a small
1106 number of PAMS monitors in Texas and Indiana (**Fig. S5**). Ethene (C₂H₄) is a primary pollutant
1107 emitted largely by combustion processes, including mobile sources (e.g., Simon et al., 2010). Annual
1108 \bar{O} VMR values in **Table S4A** for ethene ranged from 0.95 to 1.06 ppbv, considerably lower than annual
1109 \bar{M} VMR values, which ranged from 1.77 to 2.08 ppbv. Annual NMB scores for hourly ETHE VMR

1110 were thus positive and ranged from 0.68 to 1.19, annual NMAE scores ranged from 1.24 to 1.66, annual
1111 FAC2 scores ranged from 0.35 to 0.42, and annual R scores ranged from 0.18 to 0.32. As noted in
1112 **Sect. S2.4**, the model ETHE species is a lumped species that contains several other VOC species
1113 besides ethene, including isoprene oxidation products, so model overpredictions should be expected.
1114 Interestingly, observed annual CV values ranged from 1.65 to 1.99, consistent with a primary pollutant,
1115 but predicted annual CV values had a much lower range of 0.98 to 1.06, closer to a mixed primary-
1116 secondary pollutant like CO and consistent with the multiple-species nature of model ETHE. Note that
1117 a few other studies have also evaluated ethene predictions in North America (e.g., Biswas et al., 2001;
1118 Doraiswamy et al., 2009).

1119 • Daily HCHO measurements are available from many more locations than ethene and isoprene
1120 measurements (**Fig. S5**) but are based on 24-hour canister samples (**Table S2a**). Sources of HCHO
1121 include both primary emissions and secondary production (e.g., Tuazon and Atkinson, 1990; Luecken
1122 et al., 2012; Stroud et al., 2016; Bastien et al., 2019). Annual NMB scores for daily HCHO VMR
1123 ranged from 0.04 to 0.12, annual NMAE scores ranged from 0.56 to 0.66, annual FAC2 scores ranged
1124 from 0.65 to 0.71, and annual R scores ranged from 0.26 to 0.46. Lastly, observed all-station annual
1125 CV values for HCHO ranged from 0.74 to 0.85 for 2014–2016 and 1.51 for 2013 and predicted all-
1126 station annual CV values ranged from 0.90 to 0.94. These scores are comparable to those for CO,
1127 which is another mixed primary-secondary species, but are lower than CV values for ETHE and ISOP,
1128 which are both primary species.

1129 • A limited set of hourly measurements of isoprene VMR was available for 2013–2016 from a small
1130 number of PAMS monitors in Texas and Indiana (**Fig. S5**). Isoprene has some very minor
1131 anthropogenic sources but biogenic emissions are dominant by far (e.g., Abbot et al., 2003). Annual
1132 NMB scores for hourly ISOP VMR are very high and ranged from 2.27 to 2.71 while annual NMAE
1133 scores ranged from 2.81 to 3.20, suggesting a strong tendency to model overprediction. Annual FAC2
1134 scores ranged from 0.18 to 0.19, and annual R scores ranged from 0.37 to 0.50. Lastly, observed and
1135 predicted all-station annual CV values for ISOP were all elevated and ranged from 2.00 to 2.13 and
1136 1.82 to 2.16, respectively, higher than any other species considered here except NO. Note that a few
1137 other studies have also used ambient surface measurements to evaluate isoprene predictions in North
1138 America (e.g., Biswas et al., 2001; Doraiswamy et al., 2009; Carlton and Baker, 2011).

1139 To provide a station-level view of the domain-level values reported in **Table S4A**, the spatial distributions
1140 of station-specific annual values of four statistics (MB, NMB, CRMSE, and R) for 2013–2016 are shown
1141 in **Figs. S49-S52** for NO, **Figs. S53-S56** for HNO₃, **Figs. S57-S60** for NH₃, **Figs. S61-S64** for SO₂,
1142 **Figs. S65-S68** for CO, **Figs. S69-S72** for ETHE, **Figs. S73-S76** for HCHO, and **Figs. S77-S80** for ISOP.

1143 Note that ETHE and ISOP measurements are available for the smallest number of stations (**Fig. S5**).
1144 Reviewing these figures, we can see the following features:

- 1145 • Station-specific annual NMB values for hourly NO predictions (**Fig. S50**), like those for NO₂
1146 (**Fig. S38**), display considerable local variation, suggesting a strong dependence on the spatial
1147 distribution of NO_x emissions (cf. **Figs. S1a** and **S14**). Annual CRMSE values are lower in the
1148 continental interior for both NO and NO₂ (**Figs. S51** and **S39**) whereas station-specific annual R values
1149 are generally lower for NO than for NO₂ across the domain (**Fig. S52** vs. **Fig. S40**), consistent with
1150 Table **S4A**.
- 1151 • Station-specific annual NMB values for weekly HNO₃ predictions tend to have a mix of signs
1152 (**Fig. S54**) despite the all-station annual mean positive biases (**Table S4A**), while station-specific
1153 annual R values are fairly uniform (**Fig. S56**).
- 1154 • Station-specific annual NMB values for biweekly NH₃ predictions are biased low at most stations
1155 across the continent (**Fig. S58**) and annual R values tend to be higher in the east and lower in the interior
1156 of the continent (**Fig. S60**).
- 1157 • Station-specific annual statistics for weekly SO₂ predictions, on the other hand, display more complex
1158 spatial patterns. Station-specific annual MB, NMB, and CRMSE values for SO₂ are highest in the
1159 eastern U.S. and the Canadian province of Alberta (**Figs. S61-S63**); annual R scores also tend to be
1160 highest over the eastern U.S. (**Fig. S64**), but values vary considerably from year to year.
- 1161 • Station-specific annual NMB scores for hourly CO predictions have some large negative values in
1162 California but tend to increase moving eastwards (**Fig. S66**); many of the largest station-specific annual
1163 CRMSE values for CO are found in urban areas (**Fig. S67**) as are annual R values (**Fig. S68**).
- 1164 • Station-specific annual NMB scores for hourly ETHE predictions are all positive for stations in Indiana
1165 and Texas (**Fig. S70**), and annual R values are all low (**Fig. S72**).
- 1166 • Station-specific annual NMB scores for daily HCHO predictions tend to be negative in the western
1167 U.S. but positive in the eastern U.S. (**Fig. S74**), while annual CRMSE values tend to be highest along
1168 the eastern seaboard (**Fig. S75**) and annual R values are quite high in the eastern U.S., and especially
1169 in urban areas (**Fig. S76**).
- 1170 • Lastly, station-specific annual NMB scores for hourly ISOP predictions are all positive for stations in
1171 Indiana and Texas (**Fig. S78**) whereas annual R values have a wide range (**Fig. S80**).

1172 **Figures S14–S21** complement **Figs. S11** and **S12** as they show the predicted spatial distributions of
1173 *seasonal* mean surface VMRs for 2013–2016 and 2021/22 for eight of the other gas-phase species: NO,
1174 HNO₃, NH₃, SO₂, CO, ETHE, HCHO, and ISOP. There is considerable variety evident in the spatial
1175 distributions and seasonal cycles shown in **Figs. S14–S21** between the different species. For example, the
1176 predicted seasonal cycle for NO shown in **Fig. S14** with a winter maximum and summer minimum, is
1177 similar to that for NO₂ (**Fig. S11**), as is the decrease in wintertime NO VMR from 2013 to 2021/22
1178 associated with NO_x emission decreases (**Table 1**). The seasonal spatial distributions of HNO₃ (**Fig. S15**),
1179 NH₃ (**Fig. S16**), ETHE (**Fig. S19**), HCHO (**Fig. S20**), and ISOP (**Fig. S21**) for each year are all predicted
1180 to have their highest values in the summer season, although not for the same reasons. Higher temperatures
1181 in summer favour HNO₃ over PM_{2.5}-NO₃ for the gas-particle partitioning of nitrate (cf. **Fig. S23**), whereas
1182 NH₃, and ISOP levels in summer are directly driven by high emissions (fertilizer application and summer
1183 peaks in animal populations for NH₃, and biogenic emissions for ISOP; see **Table S1**). ETHE, as a lumped
1184 species, and HCHO are indirectly driven by isoprene emissions via subsequent oxidation of isoprene (e.g.,
1185 Tuazon and Atkinson, 1990; Abbot et al., 2003; Palmer et al., 2003; Luecken et al., 2012; Table 3 of Moran
1186 et al., 2026), which explains the similarities in summer between **Figs. S19, S20, and S21**. In contrast,
1187 seasonal SO₂ values are highest in the winter (**Fig. S17**), not due to strong seasonal variations in emissions
1188 (cf. **Table S1**) but rather to reduced gas-phase SO₂-to-H₂SO₄ conversion owing to shorter days and lower
1189 solar insolation. As well, seasonal SO₂ levels in this figure can clearly be seen to decline from 2013 to
1190 2021/22, consistent with the 60% decrease in North American SO₂ emissions over this nine-year period
1191 (**Table 1**). Lastly, the spatial distribution of CO (**Fig. S18**), like O₃ (**Figs. 5 and S12**), is very dependent on
1192 seasonal variations in background levels, which for CO peak in the spring in the Northern Hemisphere (e.g.,
1193 Shindell et al., 2006; Fortems-Cheiney et al., 2011), in CO anthropogenic and BB emissions, which peak
1194 in the summer (**Table S1**; Zhou et al., 2017), in oxidation of biogenic VOC emissions, which peaks in the
1195 summer (Holloway et al., 2000; Duncan et al., 2007), and in air pollution potential, which peaks in the
1196 winter (e.g., Holzworth, 1967).

1197 **Table S4S** extends the 2013–2016 seasonal statistics reported in **Table S3S** for NO₂ and O₃ to nine other
1198 gas-phase species predicted by the RAQDPS-OP023 (cf. **Table S4A**). The predicted season associated
1199 with peak \bar{M} values for seven of the eight species shown in **Figs. S14–S21** (winter for NO, SO₂, and CO,
1200 summer for HNO₃, NH₃, HCHO, and ISOP) agreed with the observed season of peak \bar{O} values in
1201 **Table S4S**. The one exception was ETHE. Again, this is not surprising since the ethene observations
1202 correspond to a single species and are not influenced by biogenic emissions in the way that the model
1203 lumped ETHE species is. However, this confounding biogenic source should have the least impact in the
1204 winter, and in fact winter NMB values for ETHE for 2013–2016 ranged from -0.06 to 0.13 vs. summer

1205 NMB values that ranged from 1.71 to 3.21. This suggests that winter-season evaluations for ETHE still
1206 have some value for assessing model predictions of anthropogenic ethene, and in fact the winter values for
1207 ETHE of seasonal NMAE (0.65 to 0.70), FAC2 (0.57 to 0.62), and R (0.44 to 0.51) were quite good.

1208 Looking further at [Table S4S](#), a comparison of the seasonal statistics for each of these gas-phase species
1209 reveals different behaviours and greater model skill for some species and seasons compared to others. For
1210 example, four species had all-station seasonal NMB values of the same sign for all seasons and years, i.e.,
1211 a consistent bias: seasonal NMB values for HNO₃ ranged from 0.0 to 0.59, those for NH₃ ranged from -
1212 0.22 to -0.74, those for SO₂ ranged from 0.21 to 0.81, and those for ISOP ranged from 1.55 to 5.23. For
1213 all-station seasonal NMAE values, CO had the lowest range (0.49 to 0.70) and ISOP had the highest range
1214 (2.13 to 5.89). For all-station seasonal FAC2 values, HNO₃ had the highest range (0.66 to 0.87) followed
1215 by CO (0.66 to 0.79) while ISOP had the lowest range (0.14 to 0.25). And for all-station seasonal R values,
1216 HNO₃ had the highest range (0.60 to 0.75) and CO had the lowest range (0.09 to 0.46) followed by ETHE
1217 (0.12 to 0.51), ISOP (0.03 to 0.55), and NO (0.28 to 0.44). Note that ISOP also had the highest seasonal
1218 NSD range (1.64 to 4.99), so this species stands out for poor scores.

1219 As noted in the discussion of [Table S4A](#), Zhai et al. (2024) recommended benchmarks for NMB, NMAE,
1220 and R scores for CO and SO₂. With one exception (summer 2013), all of the all-station seasonal NMB
1221 values for CO met the benchmark goal of ± 0.25 , most seasonal NMAE values for CO met the benchmark
1222 goal of 0.60 and all but one (summer 2013) met the acceptable threshold of 0.65, and the winter and autumn
1223 R scores for 2013–2015 met the acceptable threshold of 0.40. For SO₂ only the four all-station spring NMB
1224 values for 2013–2016 plus winter 2015 and summers 2015 and 2016 met the acceptable threshold of ± 0.50 .
1225 No seasonal NMAE values for SO₂ met the acceptable threshold of 0.70, whereas all but four all-station
1226 seasonal R scores met the acceptable (but low) threshold of 0.35.

1227 The discussion of [Table S4A](#) also pointed out that annual statistics for individual networks could be quite
1228 different owing to different network characteristics. In particular, annual statistics for weekly SO₂ VMRs
1229 were similar for AQS and NAPS and different from those for CAPMoN and CASTNET. The same finding
1230 holds for SO₂ for the seasonal statistics in [Table S4S](#) for 2013–2016. The ranges of SO₂ seasonal \bar{O} values
1231 for the AQS and NAPS networks were 0.86–1.71 and 0.97–1.42 ppbv, respectively, markedly higher than
1232 the CAPMoN and CASTNET ranges of 0.08–0.40 and 0.20–0.62 ppbv. For SO₂ seasonal NMB values, on
1233 the other hand, the ranges for AQS and CASTNET, the two U.S. networks, were 0.09–0.68 and -0.02–0.78,
1234 considerably lower than the ranges for CAPMoN and NAPS, the two Canadian networks, of 0.45–1.69 and
1235 0.59–1.74. Again, this difference raises the possibility that the Canadian SO₂ emissions used for the 2013–
1236 2016 hindcast simulations may have been biased high. Another internetwork difference can be seen for

1237 SO₂ seasonal NMAE: the range for CASTNET of 0.37–0.90 was lower than the ranges for AQS (0.74–
1238 1.15), CAPMoN (0.58–1.73), and NAPS (1.11–2.11). The ranges of SO₂ seasonal FAC2 values for AQS
1239 and NAPS of 0.39–0.56 and 0.26–0.46 were somewhat lower than the CAPMoN and CASTNET ranges of
1240 0.20–0.68 and 0.52–0.80. The ranges of SO₂ seasonal R values for AQS and NAPS of 0.25–0.46 and 0.23–
1241 0.51 were also considerably lower than the ranges for CAPMoN and CASTNET of 0.66–0.91 and 0.44–
1242 0.92 even though the sampling periods considered were identical. It was also noted in the discussion of
1243 **Table S4A** that NO and ISOP had the highest observed and predicted annual CV values, so it is of interest
1244 to see how CV values varied by season. For NO the answer is that the variation was surprisingly small.
1245 The largest observed and predicted seasonal CV values for NO for 2013–2016 occurred in the spring, with
1246 ranges of 3.24–3.43 and 3.18–3.34, while the lowest observed and predicted seasonal CV values were 2.58
1247 (winter) and 2.78 (autumn), respectively. For ISOP the seasonal variation was considerably greater than
1248 for NO: the lowest observed seasonal CV values occurred in the summer (1.25–1.36) while the highest
1249 observed seasonal CV values occurred in the winter (2.50–6.50). For predicted seasonal CV values the
1250 variation was smaller, with a minimum value of 1.41 (summer) and a maximum value of 2.03 (spring).

1251 **Figures S143–S150** complement **Figs. S140** and **S141** for NO₂ and O₃ and present time series of all-station
1252 *monthly* statistics for predicted VMRs of NO, HNO₃, NH₃, SO₂, CO, ETHE, HCHO, and ISOP for 2013–
1253 2016. Examining each of these figures in turn, we can see the following similarities and differences
1254 between species:

- 1255 • The monthly NO time series shown in **Fig. S143** are similar to those for NO₂ in **Fig. S140**. Time series
1256 of observed and predicted all-station monthly means for both NO and NO₂ VMR had a summer
1257 minimum and winter maximum (cf. **Figs. S14** and **S11**). Monthly NMB values for NO, on the other
1258 hand, were markedly higher than those for NO₂, and monthly FAC2 and R values for NO were markedly
1259 lower (however, see discussion of **Fig. S172** below regarding NO measurement precision). In addition,
1260 monthly NMB time series for both species displayed monotonic, year-to-year decreases for all months,
1261 consistent with decreasing annual NO_x emissions over this period (**Table 1**), but the decreases for NO
1262 were more pronounced, consistent with about 90% of NO_x emissions assumed to be in the form of NO.
- 1263 • Time series of observed all-station monthly mean HNO₃ VMR peaked in the May to July period for all
1264 four years (**Fig. S144**) but the predicted peak occurred slightly later in the July to September period (cf.
1265 **Fig. S15**). Interestingly, both observed and predicted monthly means of this non-emitted, terminal
1266 species exhibited year-to-year decreases for all months, consistent with decreasing annual NO_x
1267 emissions (**Table 1**). Monthly NMB scores for HNO₃ in **Fig. S144** were positive throughout the year
1268 but peaked in September for all four years. Note that this consistent overprediction may be even higher
1269 given that CASTNET HNO₃ measurements themselves are likely biased high, especially in the summer

1270 (Lavery et al., 2009). Time series of monthly FAC2 values peaked in March to June but had a minimum
1271 in September for all four years, while monthly R values were roughly uniform but slightly higher for
1272 the spring months.

- 1273 • Peak observed all-station monthly mean NH₃ VMR values occurred in the May to July period for all
1274 four years as did the model predicted values (Figs. [S145](#) and [S16](#)). However, the model underpredicted
1275 monthly NH₃ levels throughout the year, but especially in the cold season when the monthly NMB and
1276 FAC2 scores were lowest by a wide margin. Monthly R scores varied widely between years compared
1277 to the other statistics, but note that the monthly sample sizes are small for this species due to the
1278 biweekly measurements (cf. [Table S4S](#)).
- 1279 • The model roughly reproduced the SO₂ seasonal cycle, with highest observed and predicted all-station
1280 monthly mean SO₂ VMR values in the winter and lowest observed values in the late summer vs. lowest
1281 predicted values in April or May (Figs. [S146](#) and [S17](#)). Monthly mean SO₂ levels, however, were
1282 consistently overpredicted, with the smallest overpredictions occurring in April and May and the largest
1283 overpredictions occurring in September or December. Both observed and predicted monthly mean SO₂
1284 levels displayed year-to-year decreases for all months, consistent with decreasing annual SO₂ emissions
1285 from 2013 to 2016 ([Table 1](#)). Monthly FAC2 values for weekly SO₂ were consistent between years
1286 and were highest in January to March and lowest in September. Monthly R scores were fairly constant
1287 for all months and years.
- 1288 • The model also roughly reproduced the CO seasonal cycle, with the highest observed and predicted all-
1289 station monthly mean CO VMR values found in December or January and the lowest observed monthly
1290 mean values in June or July vs. lowest predicted values in May (Figs. [S147](#) and [S18](#)). The time series
1291 of monthly NMB values had similar shapes for the four years but decreased monotonically for each
1292 month for the four years. Note that anthropogenic CO emissions also decreased by 13% from 2013 to
1293 2016 ([Table 1](#)). Time series of monthly FAC2 were very close for the four years, with maximum
1294 values in April or May and minimum values in August. Monthly R values displayed a winter maximum
1295 and summer minimum, but monthly R scores for 2016 were notable outliers (as were the all-station
1296 seasonal R values in 2016 in [Table S4S](#)).
- 1297 • At first glance the time series of monthly statistics for ETHE were not very good, especially for the
1298 summer months (Fig. [S148](#)). The observed monthly means for ETHE had a minimum in June or July
1299 whereas the predicted monthly means were highest in the summer with a maximum in August or
1300 September. Monthly NMB, FAC2, and R values all had their worst values in the summer months.
1301 However, as has already been noted these statistics were based on a comparison of a measured single
1302 VOC species with a model lumped VOC species. In the winter when isoprene emissions are low

1303 (Fig. S150), the model ETHE species is thus more likely to match ethene alone, and in fact for the
1304 winter months, monthly NMB, FAC2, and R values were considerably better: roughly 0.05, 0.60, and
1305 0.50, respectively, for the four years (cf. Table S4S). The good winter scores then suggest that the
1306 anthropogenic ETHE emissions input by the model, which correspond to ethene alone, were also good
1307 for that season.

1308 • The broad HCHO seasonal cycle was reasonably well predicted for all four years, with both observed
1309 and predicted monthly mean HCHO VMR peaks occurring in July and minimum monthly mean values
1310 in the winter months (Fig. S149). The monthly NMB time series, however, indicate that predicted
1311 monthly values were biased high in the warm season but low in the cold season. Monthly FAC2 values
1312 were quite high (~0.70) and had peaks in spring and autumn and troughs in winter and summer, while
1313 monthly R scores were low overall (~0.30) and displayed considerable year-to-year and seasonal
1314 variability.

1315 • Similar to HCHO, the broad ISOP seasonal cycle was captured, with observed monthly mean ISOP
1316 VMR peaks occurring in June or July and predicted monthly peaks occurring in August while the lowest
1317 monthly means occurred in the winter months (Fig. S150). The monthly scores for ISOP were less
1318 good, though noting again that they were based on a small number of measurement stations (cf.
1319 Fig. S78). Monthly NMB scores were lowest in the summer months (although this was when monthly
1320 MB scores were highest; cf. Table S4S) but were above 300% for the rest of the year; the highest
1321 monthly NMB values occurred in March and November for all years, pointing to possible issues with
1322 the treatment of vegetation phenology for biogenic emissions. Monthly FAC2 scores were low (~0.20)
1323 for all months and years, and monthly R scores were close to zero in the winter months but peaked in
1324 September or October.

1325 Another type of monthly analysis is provided by Figs. S172–S179, which compare monthly density
1326 scatterplots of surface NO, HNO₃, NH₃, SO₂, CO, ETHE, HCHO, and ISOP VMRs for 2013–2016 for the
1327 four mid-season months. These figures complement Figs. S169 and S170 for NO₂ and O₃. Examining each
1328 of these eight figures in turn, we can see the following features:

1329 • The monthly density scatterplots for hourly NO VMR in Fig. S172 have higher monthly mean levels
1330 in January and October for all years, consistent with Fig. S143. There is also much more scatter in the
1331 NO scatterplots than the NO₂ scatterplots (Fig. S169). This is consistent with the lower all-station
1332 seasonal FAC2 and R scores and higher seasonal CV values for hourly NO VMR predictions compared
1333 to hourly NO₂ VMR predictions noted above in the discussion of Table S4S. There is also an obvious
1334 “quantization” of the hourly NO measurements in Fig. S172, again similar to Fig. S169, indicating that

1335 the majority of NO monitors report in whole numbers. This is clearly a limitation on measurement
1336 precision when observed monthly mean NO values are less than 4 ppbv for more than half the year
1337 (Fig. S143) compared to 8 ppbv for NO₂ (Fig. S140) and could help to explain why monthly FAC2 and
1338 R scores are markedly lower for NO than NO₂.

1339 • The monthly density scatterplots for all-station weekly HNO₃ VMR in Fig. S173 are broadly similar
1340 across the four seasons and four years, although the higher values in summer are suggested by both the
1341 scatterplots and the observed marginal frequency distributions (cf. Fig. S144). This figure suggests
1342 good model performance overall, which is complemented by the summary statistics in the upper-left
1343 corner of the scatterplots. The blocky appearance of the density scatterplots also points to the relatively
1344 small number of measurement-model pairs that each scatterplot is based on (~400/month; cf.
1345 Table S4S).

1346 • The monthly density scatterplots for all-station biweekly NH₃ concentrations in Fig. S174, on the other
1347 hand, are also broadly similar across years, but they show greater seasonal differences between winter
1348 and autumn vs. spring and summer. The differences in the scatterplots across seasons suggest the lower
1349 all-station monthly mean values, lower monthly NMB values, and lower monthly FAC2 values in the
1350 winter and autumn that are evident in Fig. S145 (and in the seasonal NH₃ values in Table S4S). And
1351 like Fig. S173 the blockiness of Fig. S174 points to the small sample sizes being considered for each
1352 month (~200/month; cf. Table S4S).

1353 • The monthly density scatterplots for all-station weekly SO₂ VMR in Fig. S175 are broadly similar
1354 across both months and years. They do indicate the consistently positive monthly NMB values evident
1355 in Fig. S146, and there is a suggestion of the greater scatter associated with lower warm-season FAC2
1356 values.

1357 • One immediate message from the monthly density scatterplots (and observed marginal frequency
1358 distributions) for hourly CO VMR shown in Fig. S176 is the limited precision (100 ppbv) of many of
1359 the CO measurements (cf. Fig. S172 for NO). Despite this quantization of the measurements, however,
1360 the high all-station monthly FAC2 values (~0.70) shown in Fig. S147 are suggested in this figure by
1361 the large number of measurements falling within the 1:2 and 2:1 lines. The low monthly R values
1362 (~0.30) plotted in Fig. S147 are also suggested by these scatterplots, although it is not obvious in
1363 Fig. S176 that the monthly R values for 2016 were markedly lower than for the other years.

1364 • The monthly density scatterplots for hourly ETHE VMR (Fig. S177) suggest a sizable set of available
1365 monthly measurements (cf. Table S4S). The better performance in the winter and autumn months
1366 shown in Fig. S148, including lower all-station monthly NMB values and higher monthly FAC2 and R

1367 values, is also evident in the differences between the monthly density scatterplots in **Fig. S177** for each
1368 year.

1369 • The blockiness of the monthly density scatterplots for daily HCHO VMR (**Fig. S178**) again suggests
1370 the small number of monthly measurements available (~450/month; cf. **Table S4S**). The peak all-
1371 station monthly \bar{O} and \bar{M} VMR values in the summer and the high FAC2 values (~0.70), limited
1372 linearity, and relatively low R values (~0.30) across months seen in **Fig. S149** are also reflected in
1373 **Fig. S178**.

1374 • Similarly, the monthly density scatterplots for hourly ISOP VMR (**Fig. S179**) echo the summertime
1375 maximum, the large and consistent overpredictions, low FAC2 scores, low wintertime R values, and
1376 exaggerated NSD values seen in **Fig. S150** and **Table S4S**.

1377 **Table S8** complements **Table S7**, which presented annual statistics for NO₂ and O₃ by region for 2013–
1378 2016, by presenting a similar regional analysis for NO, NO_x, HNO₃, NH₃, SO₂, CO, ETHE, HCHO, and
1379 ISOP for the same years. The regions are again the four continental quadrants shown in **Figure S7**. One
1380 limitation of **Table S8**, however, is that measurements of ETHE, HCHO, and ISOP were only available for
1381 the two U.S. regions, and measurements of HNO₃ and NH₃ were only available from one or two stations in
1382 WCA (western Canada) so that statistics for this region are unlikely to be representative. As was the case
1383 for **Table S7**, the statistics presented in **Table S8** show some large regional variations, and a few consistent
1384 patterns are also evident for this four-year period:

1385 • For both NO and NO_x either the WUS (western U.S.) or WCA had the highest observed annual mean
1386 VMR and ECA (eastern Canada) had the lowest observed annual mean VMR for all four years. The
1387 same was true for NO₂ (**Table S7**). As well the EUS (eastern U.S.) had the lowest annual NMAE
1388 values for NO and WCA had the lowest annual R values for all four years.

1389 • For HNO₃ the EUS had the highest observed annual mean VMR and ECA had the lowest observed
1390 annual mean VMR for all four years (excluding WCA). The WUS had the lowest annual NMB and
1391 NMAE values and the EUS had the highest NMB and NMAE values for 2014–2016. In addition, ECA
1392 had the highest annual R value and the EUS had the lowest annual R value for all four years.

1393 • For NH₃ the WUS had the highest observed annual mean VMR whereas ECA had the highest predicted
1394 annual mean VMR, and the EUS had both the lowest observed and predicted annual mean VMR
1395 (excluding WCA). Other patterns for NH₃ were that the WUS had the worst NMB values and ECA
1396 had the best NMB values for all four years, and the EUS had the highest annual FAC2 value and the
1397 WUS had the lowest annual FAC2 value for all four years.

- 1398 • For SO₂ the observed annual mean VMR for the EUS decreased for each year so that this region had
1399 the highest observed annual mean VMR for 2013-2015 but the lowest value for 2016. In contrast, ECA
1400 was predicted to have the highest annual mean VMR for all four years. ECA also had the highest
1401 annual NMB values for SO₂, again suggestive of a possible emissions issue, while WUS had the lowest
1402 annual NMB values for all four years. As well, the EUS had the highest annual FAC2 values for all
1403 four years and WCA had the lowest annual FAC2 values.
- 1404 • For CO the WUS had the highest observed annual mean VMR for the first three years and WCA had
1405 the lowest observed annual mean VMR for all four years. The WUS had the highest predicted annual
1406 mean VMR for all four years. Note that 2016 was anomalous in that observed annual mean VMR for
1407 ECA more than doubled and annual R plummeted to a value of -0.03.
- 1408 • Observed annual ETHE VMRs were comparable for the WUS and EUS for all four years but annual
1409 NMB values were consistently higher for the EUS. The presence of greater biogenic emissions in this
1410 region (e.g., [Fig. S21](#)) could be an explanation for this larger overprediction.
- 1411 • Observed annual mean HCHO VMRs were consistently higher for the WUS than the EUS but the
1412 opposite was true for predicted annual mean HCHO VMRs. As a consequence, annual NMB values
1413 for the WUS were negative for all four years while annual NMB values for the EUS were positive.
- 1414 • Both observed and predicted annual mean ISOP VMRs were consistently higher for the EUS than the
1415 WUS but annual NMB values were higher for the WUS.

1416 **S3.3.2 PM_{2.5} chemical components**

1417 [Table S5A](#) is an expansion of [Table 5](#) since it presents annual evaluation scores for RAQDPS-OP023
1418 predictions of PM_{2.5} chemical components for 2013–2016 for the CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS networks
1419 individually and combined (i.e., all-station) and for predictions of PM_{2.5} dry total mass vs. gravimetric PM_{2.5}
1420 total mass measurements for the AQS, IMPROVE, and NAPS networks individually and combined. Four
1421 features of [Table S5A](#) should be noted when examining this table: (a) all measurements considered for this
1422 table were based on 24-hour filter samples; (b) no statistics are provided for PM_{2.5}-NH₄ for IMPROVE
1423 because the network does not measure this species; (c) N may vary between chemical components for the
1424 same year because not all component values for the same sample were necessarily valid; and (d) no statistics
1425 are provided for CSN daily PM_{2.5} total mass measurements because the set of gravimetric mass
1426 measurements reported by AQS included a subset of monitors co-located with CSN speciation monitors
1427 (e.g., Solomon et al., 2014).

1428 Many but not all statistics in [Table S5A](#) were comparable between the three networks. For example, while
1429 annual $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ concentration was underpredicted for all three networks, annual NMB values for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-}$
1430 NO_3 had a range of -0.36 to -0.48 for IMPROVE vs. 0.65 to 0.95 for NAPS. For the two carbonaceous
1431 components, annual NMB values for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-EC}$ had a range of -0.10 to 0.09 for IMPROVE vs. 0.46 to 0.68
1432 for CSN and 0.61 to 1.09 for NAPS, while annual NMB values for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-TOM}$ had a range of -0.46 to -
1433 0.30 for IMPROVE vs. 0.20 to 0.31 for CSN and 0.52 to 0.80 for NAPS. For $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-CM}$ the network-
1434 dependent biases were even more different: annual NMB values had a range of -0.59 to -0.50 for
1435 IMPROVE vs. 1.23 to 1.59 for CSN and 1.96 to 2.34 for NAPS. $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-EC}$, POM, and CM are all primary
1436 pollutants. Since the majority of CSN and NAPS monitors are located in urban or suburban areas whereas
1437 IMPROVE monitors have largely rural locations, the assumed spatial distribution of combustion emissions
1438 may be one contributing factor to the $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-EC}$ and POM network differences while the assumed spatial
1439 distribution of fugitive dust emissions from paved and unpaved roads may be one contributing factor to the
1440 $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-CM}$ network differences. Lastly, annual NMB values for daily gravimetric $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass were
1441 also quite different between networks, ranging from -0.34 to -0.30 for IMPROVE vs. 0.03 to 0.09 for AQS
1442 and 0.33 to 0.62 for NAPS. Note that NSD values had similar differences between networks, with smaller
1443 values for IMPROVE than for CSN and NAPS.

1444 Emery et al. (2017) recommended two sets of component-dependent benchmarks for NMB, NMAE, and R
1445 scores for predictions of five $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical components: $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$, NO_3 , NH_4 , EC, and TOM. One of
1446 these sets represents “acceptable” scores (above 33rd percentile for a historical multi-model ensemble) while
1447 the other represents “good” scores (above 67th percentile). These benchmarks are more stringent for
1448 $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ and NH_4 and less so for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$, EC, and TOM. Note that no benchmarks for R were
1449 recommended for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$, EC, or TOM, and no benchmarks at all were recommended for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-CM}$ or
1450 SS. All-station annual NMB scores for both $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ and NH_4 in [Table S5A](#) for 2013–2016 met the
1451 recommended acceptable benchmark of ± 0.30 with the exception of 2016 NH_4 (an outlier of 0.85). The
1452 all-station annual NMAE scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ also met the acceptable benchmark of 0.50, whereas the all-
1453 station annual NMAE scores for NH_4 , with a range of 0.59 to 1.23 (2016 again), did not. All-station annual
1454 R scores for these two components all met the acceptable benchmark of 0.40 but not the benchmark goal
1455 of 0.70. For $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$, the third inorganic $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ component, all-station annual NMB scores met the
1456 acceptable benchmark of ± 0.65 for all four years but also the benchmark goal of ± 0.15 for three years (2014
1457 being the exception). All-station annual NMAE scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$, which ranged from 0.63 to 0.71,
1458 were well below the acceptable benchmark of 1.15 and close to the benchmark goal of 0.65. For the two
1459 carbonaceous components the all-station annual NMB scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-EC}$ only met the acceptable
1460 benchmark of ± 0.40 for 2016, but the all-station annual NMB scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-TOM}$ met both the

1461 acceptable benchmark of ± 0.50 and the benchmark goal of ± 0.15 for all four years. For all-station annual
1462 NMAE scores, the $PM_{2.5}$ -EC scores, which ranged from 0.77 to 0.91, were higher than the acceptable
1463 benchmark of 0.75 while the $PM_{2.5}$ -TOM scores, which ranged from 0.68 to 0.75, were also just above the
1464 acceptable benchmark of 0.65. While Emery et al. (2017) did not recommend benchmarks for R for
1465 $PM_{2.5}$ -NO₃, EC, or TOM, note that all-station annual R scores for $PM_{2.5}$ -NO₃ and EC also met the acceptable
1466 benchmark of 0.40 for SO₄ and NH₄ for all four years as did the all-station annual R score for $PM_{2.5}$ -TOM
1467 for 2014.

1468 **Table S5A** also shows an analysis of 2013–2016 observed and predicted all-station mean annual $PM_{2.5}$
1469 chemical composition. For observations the ranking of the seven chemical components in descending order
1470 was $PM_{2.5}$ -TOM, SO₄, NO₃, CM, NH₄, EC, and SS, but the predicted ranking was $PM_{2.5}$ -TOM, CM, SO₄,
1471 NH₄, NO₃, EC, and SS. This qualitative difference in observed and predicted $PM_{2.5}$ chemical composition,
1472 including the model's higher ranking of CM and NH₄, is the result of some of the species-specific biases
1473 noted in the discussion of **Table 5** in **Sect. 3.3.2**. The network-specific biases noted in the discussion of
1474 **Table S5A** for the three networks also result in differences between observed and predicted $PM_{2.5}$
1475 composition for each network. The observed mean annual composition for CSN is basically the same as
1476 the all-station composition while the observed mean annual composition for NAPS agrees for the first three
1477 species but the fourth-ranking species is EC rather than CM. For IMPROVE the observed mean annual
1478 composition is even more different than the all-station composition: TOM, SO₄, CM, NH₄, NO₃, SS, and
1479 EC. There is also more variety between the three networks for predicted $PM_{2.5}$ composition: the predicted
1480 top-four-ranked species for CSN are TOM, CM, NO₃, and SO₄ vs. TOM, CM, SO₄, and NO₃ for NAPS and
1481 TOM, SO₄, SS, and CM for IMPROVE.

1482 The spatial distributions of station-specific annual values of four statistics (MB, NMB, CRMSE, and R) for
1483 seven daily $PM_{2.5}$ chemical components for 2013–2016 are shown in **Figs. S81** to **S108** (cf. **Figs. S45–S48**
1484 for $PM_{2.5}$ total mass). Inspection of these figures suggests that each statistic for each component was
1485 consistent overall from year to year. As well, most scores varied regionally, but stations in the same region
1486 tended to have similar scores for $PM_{2.5}$ -SO₄, NO₃, NH₄, TOM, and SS but less so for $PM_{2.5}$ -EC or CM.
1487 Note that the first four components are either secondary pollutants or have a secondary source ($PM_{2.5}$ -
1488 TOM), while proximity to the (homogeneous) ocean might help to explain the regional coherence of the
1489 $PM_{2.5}$ -SS statistics (as would wintertime application of road salt within the same climate region, although
1490 this emission source was not considered by the RAQDPS-OP023). Urban-rural differences, on the other
1491 hand, might explain the within-region station differences for the last two components. Similarly, the sign
1492 of annual MB and NMB values for individual stations (i.e., underprediction vs. overprediction) tended to

1493 reflect the all-station annual MB and NMB statistics presented in **Table 5** for some components (PM_{2.5}-SO₄,
1494 NO₃, NH₄, SS) but not others (PM_{2.5}-EC, TOM, CM).

1495 Some additional comments can be made about **Figs. S81** to **S108** for individual daily PM_{2.5} chemical
1496 components:

- 1497 • Annual mean PM_{2.5}-SO₄ surface concentration was underpredicted in most of the U.S. but was
1498 overpredicted at some stations in the Rocky Mountain and Pacific Northwest regions; CRMSE and R
1499 scores for PM_{2.5}-SO₄ tended to be higher in the east than the west (**Figs. S81-S84**);
- 1500 • Annual mean PM_{2.5}-NO₃ surface concentration was underpredicted more in the western U.S. than the
1501 eastern U.S.; CRMSE scores were largest in California and the Ohio Valley and Great Lakes regions;
1502 R scores for PM_{2.5}-NO₃ were lower in the western U.S. than the east (**Figs. S85-S88**);
- 1503 • Annual mean PM_{2.5}-NH₄ surface concentration was overpredicted across the southeastern U.S. and
1504 along the west coast, but 2016 was an outlier in terms of overpredictions everywhere; R scores were
1505 lower in the southeastern U.S. than in the Ohio Valley and northeastern U.S.; (**Figs. S89-S92**);
- 1506 • Annual mean PM_{2.5}-EC surface concentration tended to be underpredicted everywhere in the U.S.
1507 outside of urban areas, but all-station annual NMB was ~-0.50 (**Table 5**); large annual MB and CRMSE
1508 values tended to be associated with urban areas, consistent with CSN and NAPS vs. IMPROVE
1509 differences in **Table S5A**; the lowest R scores for PM_{2.5}-EC tended to be found in the Rocky Mountain
1510 and Great Plains regions (**Figs. S93-S96**);
- 1511 • Annual mean PM_{2.5}-TOM surface concentration tended to be underpredicted everywhere in the U.S.,
1512 though with some exceptions in the northeastern U.S.; consistently low NMB values in the western
1513 U.S. might point to missing wildfire emissions more than underpredicted biogenic SOA (cf. **Fig. S27**);
1514 CRMSE scores were smaller over the Rocky Mountain region than elsewhere; R scores for PM_{2.5}-TOM
1515 tended to be smallest in the central U.S. and largest in the northeastern U.S. (**Figs. S97-S100**);
- 1516 • Annual mean PM_{2.5}-CM surface concentration was underpredicted in the western U.S. outside of urban
1517 areas but overpredicted in the northeastern U.S.; CRMSE scores were largest in the southern U.S.; R
1518 scores for PM_{2.5}-CM were very low over the southern and southeastern U.S. and the Mississippi Valley
1519 (**Figs. S101-S104**);
- 1520 • Annual mean PM_{2.5}-SS surface concentration was overpredicted in coastal areas and the southeastern
1521 U.S. but underpredicted in the Great Lakes region; high CRMSE values were found close to the oceans
1522 and very low values were found in the central U.S.; high R scores were found along the west and east
1523 coasts and the southeastern U.S. while very low R scores were found in the northern Plains states and
1524 Canadian Prairies, possibly due to the missing road-salt emissions (**Figs. S105-S108**).

1525 **Figures S22-S30** present plots of predicted spatial distributions of seasonal mean surface concentrations
1526 for nine PM_{2.5} chemical components for 2013–2016 and 2021/22. They thus add temporal detail to **Fig. 14**
1527 and chemical detail to **Fig. S13**. Like **Fig. S13** the patterns of the chemical components were broadly
1528 similar for each season from year to year, but strong and consistent seasonal variations were evident within
1529 each year for most of these components, with the possible exception of PM_{2.5}-EC (**Fig. S25**). Also, similar
1530 to **Fig. 15** the season in which peak domain-scale concentrations were predicted to occur depended on the
1531 component. Predicted peak seasonal concentrations for PM_{2.5}-NO₃, NH₄, POM, CM, and SS occurred in
1532 the winter (**Figs. S23, S24, S26, S29, and S30**) vs. summer peaks for PM_{2.5}-SO₄, SOM, and TOM
1533 (**Figs. S22, S27, and S28**). Note for the PM_{2.5}-NH₄ concentration maximum in the winter that NH₃
1534 emissions also vary strongly by season, but they have a minimum in the winter and a maximum in the
1535 summer (**Table S1**).

1536 Time trends are also visible in the predicted seasonal surface concentrations of several PM_{2.5} components.
1537 Summertime decreases in PM_{2.5}-SO₄ concentrations are very noticeable in **Fig. S22** in response to the 60%
1538 reduction in annual SO₂ emissions from 2013 to 2021/22 (**Table 1**). Similarly, decreases in PM_{2.5}-NO₃
1539 concentrations are visible in **Fig. S23** in all seasons in response to the 36% reduction in annual NO_x
1540 emissions from 2013 to 2021/22. Annual NH₃ emissions, by contrast, decreased by only 6% over this same
1541 period (**Table 1**), but noticeable decreases in PM_{2.5}-NH₄ surface concentrations can also be seen in **Fig. S24**
1542 in all seasons due to reduced availability of both ambient H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ to neutralize ambient NH₃.

1543 **Table S5S** summarizes 2013–2016 *seasonal* evaluation scores of the same 12 statistics as **Table S5A** for
1544 seven PM_{2.5} chemical components for the CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS networks individually and
1545 combined. A comparison of the observed and predicted peak seasonal means in this table agrees with some
1546 but not all of the model predictions shown in **Figs. S22-S30**. Observed and predicted all-station PM_{2.5}-SO₄
1547 seasonal means in **Table S5S** both peak in the summer in all years, consistent with **Fig. S22**. Observed and
1548 predicted all-station PM_{2.5}-NO₃, NH₄, and EC seasonal means all peak in the winter, consistent with
1549 **Figs. S23, S24, and S25**. For both PM_{2.5}-TOM and CM, on the other hand, the observed peak all-station
1550 seasonal means occur in the summer whereas the predicted peak all-station seasonal means occur in the
1551 winter for all four years for PM_{2.5}-TOM and for three years for PM_{2.5}-CM (cf. **Figs. S155 and S156**).
1552 **Figures S28 and S29** provide some support for the observed PM_{2.5}-TOM and CM summer peak means,
1553 suggesting that either sampling bias associated with the location of network stations or winter
1554 overpredictions are possible factors to explain these mismatched all-station seasonal peaks. A comparison
1555 of the observed and predicted peak seasonal means for the individual networks in **Table S5S** provides
1556 support for sampling bias being a contributing factor to this mismatch. For PM_{2.5}-TOM the IMPROVE
1557 observations showed a summer peak and the model predicted a summer peak for all four years, whereas the

1558 CSN observations showed seasonal peaks in the winter (2013, 2014), summer (2015), and autumn (2016)
1559 but the model predicted a winter peak for all four years. For PM_{2.5}-CM the IMPROVE and CSN
1560 observations both showed a summer peak for all four years but the model predicted an autumn or summer
1561 peak for IMPROVE vs. a winter peak for CSN for all four years. Lastly, for PM_{2.5}-SS the observed and
1562 predicted peak all-station seasonal means both occurred in the spring despite the domain-level winter peak
1563 evident in [Fig. S30](#). The explanation for this difference may be the greater penetration of SS inland over
1564 the U.S. Gulf coast, Florida, and the Atlantic coast in the spring that is visible in [Fig. S30](#). Note that the
1565 finding that observed seasonal peaks occur for some PM_{2.5} components in the winter and for others in the
1566 summer can explain the bimodality in observed monthly PM_{2.5} total mass visible in [Figs. S142](#) and [S198](#).
1567 [Table S55](#) also shows when observed all-station seasonal *minima* occur: winter or autumn for PM_{2.5}-SO₄,
1568 summer for PM_{2.5}-NO₃, summer or autumn for PM_{2.5}-NH₄, spring for PM_{2.5}-EC, spring or winter for PM_{2.5}-
1569 TOM, winter for PM_{2.5}-CM, and autumn for PM_{2.5}-SS.

1570 A comparison of the other all-station seasonal statistics in [Table S55](#) for each chemical component also
1571 points to greater model skill for some chemical components and some seasons than others, and wider or
1572 narrower ranges across seasons for a single component and statistic. For example, all-station seasonal NMB
1573 scores for 2013–2016 were uniformly negative for PM_{2.5}-SO₄, with a range from -0.41 to -0.08, whereas
1574 all-station seasonal NMB scores for PM_{2.5}-NO₃, NH₄, TOM, and CM could be either negative or positive,
1575 with ranges from -0.33 to 0.16, -0.11 to 1.29, -0.39 to 0.56, and -0.12 to 2.23, respectively. All-station
1576 seasonal NMB scores for PM_{2.5}-EC and SS, on the other hand, were uniformly positive, with ranges from
1577 0.18 to 0.70 and 0.37 to 1.53. Systematic model biases across seasons for the combined networks were
1578 thus strongest for PM_{2.5}-SO₄, EC, and SS. For all-station seasonal NMAE scores the corresponding ranges
1579 were 0.39 to 0.63 for PM_{2.5}-SO₄, 0.53 to 0.91 for NO₃, 0.52 to 1.59 for NH₄, 0.70 to 1.03 for EC, 0.54 to
1580 1.02 for TOM, 1.04 to 2.71 for CM, and 1.14 to 1.90 for SS. For this measure of forecast error or scatter,
1581 PM_{2.5}-SO₄, NO₃, and TOM had smaller levels of scatter across seasons while PM_{2.5}-SS and CM had higher
1582 levels. For all-station seasonal FAC2 scores the ranges were 0.43 to 0.76 for PM_{2.5}-SO₄, 0.18 to 0.47 for
1583 NO₃, 0.28 to 0.65 for NH₄, 0.51 to 0.62 for EC, 0.46 to 0.57 for TOM, 0.28 to 0.34 for CM, and 0.23 to
1584 0.40 for SS. For this statistic, which measures the lack of scatter and is less affected by outliers, PM_{2.5}-SO₄,
1585 EC, and TOM had higher (better) scores across seasons while PM_{2.5}-SS, CM, and NO₃ had lower scores
1586 (see also [Figs. S151](#) to [S157](#)). And for all-station seasonal R scores the ranges were 0.48 to 0.80 for PM_{2.5}-
1587 SO₄, 0.53 to 0.73 for NO₃, 0.43 to 0.67 for NH₄, 0.40 to 0.68 for EC, 0.03 to 0.54 for TOM, 0.07 to 0.37
1588 for CM, and 0.42 to 0.70 for SS. These ranges for R suggest that PM_{2.5}-SO₄, NO₃, NH₄, EC, and SS tended
1589 to higher R scores and better performance whereas PM_{2.5}-CM and TOM tended to lower R scores (see also
1590 [Figs. S151](#) to [S157](#)).

1591 **Table S55** thus raises a number of concerns for the combined networks. One is the underprediction of
1592 $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ in all seasons (cf. **Fig. S151**). A second is the overprediction of $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-EC}$ and SS in all seasons
1593 (cf. **Figs. S154** and **S157**) and the overprediction of $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NH}_4$ in most seasons (**Fig. S153**). And a third is
1594 the overprediction of $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-TOM}$ in the winter but underprediction in the summer (cf. **Fig. S155**), and the
1595 large overprediction of $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-CM}$ in the winter and autumn (**Fig. S156**). If we look at these biases by
1596 individual network, some are even more pronounced and some differ considerably between networks. First,
1597 observed seasonal concentrations of $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ in **Table S55** were two to three times higher for the CSN
1598 network than the IMPROVE network, but this may be due more to east-west differences in the spatial
1599 distribution of this species (**Fig. S22**) combined with the eastern focus of the CSN network vs. the western
1600 focus of the IMPROVE network (cf. **Figs. S6b**) than to urban-rural differences. Seasonal NMB values for
1601 $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ were generally negative for CSN (-0.43 to 0.0), NAPS (-0.24 to 0.19), and IMPROVE (-0.42
1602 to -0.16), similar to the range for the combined networks (-0.41 to -0.08) and suggesting a widespread and
1603 consistent problem. If we examine some of the other seasonal scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$, we find that for all
1604 three networks the best NMAE, FAC2, and R scores as well as NMB scores were associated with the
1605 summer or autumn, while the worst NMAE, FAC2, and R scores as well as NMB scores were generally
1606 associated with the winter (cf. **Fig. S180**). Seasonal NMB values for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$ were higher for CSN (-
1607 0.29 to 0.19) and NAPS (-0.07 to 3.83) than for IMPROVE (-0.76 to -0.10). Seasonal NMB values for
1608 $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NH}_4$ were mostly positive for CSN (-0.11 to 1.30) and NAPS (-0.10 to 1.28), whereas IMPROVE
1609 did not measure this species. Seasonal NMB values for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-EC}$ were uniformly positive and large for
1610 CSN (0.33 to 0.84) and NAPS (0.44 to 1.35) compared to a lower mixed range for IMPROVE (-0.31 to
1611 0.32). Seasonal NMB values for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-TOM}$ were more positive for CSN (-0.23 to 0.74) and NAPS (0.04
1612 to 1.10) compared to IMPROVE (-0.58 to 0.01). Seasonal NMB values for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-CM}$ were positive and
1613 large for CSN (0.42 to 3.58) and NAPS (1.13 to 4.38) compared to IMPROVE (-0.73 to 0.24). The
1614 consistent overpredictions of $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-EC}$ and CM, which are both primary pollutants, for the urban-focused
1615 CSN and NAPS networks compared to the rural-focused IMPROVE network raise the possibility that issues
1616 with the assumed urban-rural distribution of emissions of these two pollutants could be a contributing
1617 factor.

1618 We can also compare the seasonal NMB, NMAE, and R scores in **Table S55** against the two sets of
1619 benchmarks for five $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ components recommended by Emery et al. (2017). Looking first at the NMB
1620 benchmarks, all 2013–2016 summer and autumn all-station NMB scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ plus winter and
1621 spring 2016 scores met the acceptable threshold of ± 0.30 as did all 2013–2015 winter and spring all-station
1622 NMB scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NH}_4$ plus autumn 2014. All 16 all-station seasonal NMB scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$ for
1623 2013–2016 met the acceptable threshold of ± 0.65 and half met the good benchmark of ± 0.15 . Similarly,

1624 all of the seasonal NMB scores for PM_{2.5}-TOM with the exception of winter 2013 met the acceptable
1625 threshold of ± 0.50 , whereas for PM_{2.5}-EC only the four summer all-station NMB scores plus the spring and
1626 autumn 2016 scores met the acceptable threshold of ± 0.40 . For the NMAE benchmarks, all of the PM_{2.5}-
1627 SO₄ all-station seasonal NMAE scores except those for winter met the acceptable threshold of 0.50, while
1628 all of the PM_{2.5}-NO₃ all-station seasonal NMAE scores met the acceptable threshold for this species of 1.15
1629 and all winters and three springs met the good benchmark of 0.65. By contrast, none of the PM_{2.5}-NH₄ all-
1630 station seasonal NMAE scores met the acceptable threshold of 0.50, for PM_{2.5}-EC only the two all-station
1631 seasonal NMAE scores for summer and autumn 2016 met the acceptable threshold of 0.75, and for
1632 PM_{2.5}-TOM only the four summers met the acceptable threshold of 0.65. And for the R benchmarks all of
1633 the all-station seasonal R scores for PM_{2.5}-SO₄, NO₃, NH₄, and EC met the acceptable threshold of 0.40 for
1634 PM_{2.5}-SO₄ and NH₄, and five seasonal R scores for PM_{2.5}-SO₄ and four for PM_{2.5}-NO₃ met the higher
1635 benchmark of 0.70. As well, seven of the 16 all-station seasonal R scores for PM_{2.5}-TOM met the acceptable
1636 threshold.

1637 **Table S5S-mr** (where “mr” stands for “mass reconstruction”) is closely related to **Table S5S** but is based
1638 on a data subset restricted to mass-complete daily PM_{2.5} speciation measurements from the three PM_{2.5}
1639 speciation networks for 2013–2016, where “mass-complete” means that valid values were available for all
1640 six or seven measured PM_{2.5} chemical components plus gravimetric PM_{2.5} total mass for a given day and
1641 location. This requirement was in addition to the station-specific temporal representativeness or
1642 completeness requirement that was applied to the PM_{2.5} composition measurements (**Sect. S2.4** and
1643 **Table S2c**). Each mass-complete measurement can thus be used for the PM_{2.5} mass reconstruction and
1644 PM_{2.5} residual mass calculations described in **Sect. 3.3.2**. Values of N in **Table S5S-mr** are therefore
1645 smaller than values of N in **Table S5S** due to this additional completeness requirement. Note that
1646 PM_{2.5}-NH₄ scores in this table for IMPROVE were based on daily PM_{2.5}-NH₄ concentration values that
1647 were diagnosed using the formula $0.375 * [PM_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4] + 0.29 * [PM_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3]$, which assumes that sulphate
1648 and nitrate are fully neutralized by NH₃. **Figure 15** was generated using all-station seasonal mean values
1649 taken from **Table S5S-mr**; **Figs. S200-S202** were also based on **Table S5S-mr** but using seasonal mean
1650 values for only CSN measurements, only IMPROVE measurements, and only NAPS measurements,
1651 respectively.

1652 As well as providing seasonal statistics for the seven PM_{2.5} chemical components and PM_{2.5} total mass,
1653 similar to those found in **Table S5S** but based on fewer measurements, **Table S5S-mr** also contains
1654 seasonal mean PM_{2.5} reconstructed mass values based on observations for each of the three individual
1655 networks and combined networks for 2013–2016 as well as corresponding predicted seasonal mean PM_{2.5}
1656 total mass values. The discussion of **Fig. 15** noted that the comparison was mixed for the combined

1657 networks: the seasonal mean PM_{2.5} reconstructed mass values based on observations were lower than the
1658 model PM_{2.5} total mass values in winter and autumn but were higher in spring and summer: all-station
1659 seasonal NMB values ranged from -0.25 in summer to 0.26 in winter. This same comparison, however,
1660 was more one-sided for the individual speciation networks. For CSN, the mainly urban and eastern U.S.
1661 network, seasonal mean PM_{2.5} reconstructed mass values based on observations were lower than predicted
1662 seasonal mean PM_{2.5} mass values in all seasons except summer 2015 (seasonal NMB values ranged
1663 from -0.05 in summer 2015 to 0.58 in winter 2016), whereas for IMPROVE, the mainly rural and western
1664 U.S. network, seasonal mean PM_{2.5} reconstructed mass values based on observations were higher than
1665 predicted seasonal mean PM_{2.5} mass values in all 16 seasons (seasonal NMB values ranged from -0.46 in
1666 summer 2015 to -0.13 in winter 2014). And for the Canadian NAPS PM_{2.5} speciation network, which like
1667 CSN has a majority of urban stations, seasonal mean PM_{2.5} reconstructed mass values based on observations
1668 were lower than predicted seasonal mean PM_{2.5} mass values in all 16 seasons (seasonal NMB values ranged
1669 from 0.27 in winter 2016 to 1.09 in autumn 2015). These different behaviours by network are hidden in
1670 the aggregated statistics but they suggest the potential influence of multiple factors, including urban vs.
1671 rural differences, west vs. east differences, missing wildfire emissions, and underpredictions of biogenic
1672 gas-phase emissions leading to PM_{2.5}-SOM formation.

1673 **Table S5S-mr** also presents seasonal mean PM_{2.5} residual mass values for 2013–2016. The discussion of
1674 **Fig. 15** noted that observed all-station seasonal mean PM_{2.5} residual mass was greater than 0.5 μg·m⁻³ for
1675 summer but was small (and sometimes negative) otherwise, whereas predicted all-station seasonal mean
1676 PM_{2.5} residual mass was greater than 1 μg·m⁻³ for summer but was consistently negative for winter, with
1677 values ranging from -1.47 to -0.90 μg·m⁻³. In addition, observed all-station seasonal mean gravimetric
1678 PM_{2.5} mass peaked in the summer in 2013–2015. However, these seasonal differences are more exaggerated
1679 when the individual speciation networks are considered. For the CSN-only analysis, observed and predicted
1680 seasonal mean PM_{2.5} residual mass values in the summer were again all positive except for the predicted
1681 summer 2016 value, but predicted winter residual mass values were even more negative than the predicted
1682 all-station values, ranging from -4.71 to -2.86 μg·m⁻³, and observed seasonal mean gravimetric PM_{2.5} mass
1683 for CSN peaked in the winter rather than the summer except for 2015 (cf. **Fig. S200**). For the IMPROVE-
1684 only analysis, on the other hand, almost the opposite was true. Observed seasonal mean PM_{2.5} residual
1685 mass values were again largest in the summer (>0.4 μg·m⁻³) and small otherwise, but predicted seasonal
1686 mean PM_{2.5} residual mass values were positive in all seasons and years, with summer values ranging from
1687 1.95 to 3.29 μg·m⁻³ (i.e., large model underpredictions). Observed seasonal mean gravimetric PM_{2.5} mass
1688 for IMPROVE peaked in the summer (cf. **Fig. S201**). Interestingly, the NAPS-only analysis was even more
1689 extreme than the CSN-only analysis: observed seasonal mean PM_{2.5} residual mass values were positive in

1690 all 16 seasons, whereas predicted seasonal mean PM_{2.5} residual mass values were negative in all 16 seasons
1691 considered and observed seasonal mean gravimetric PM_{2.5} mass was largest in three summers (2013–2015)
1692 and one winter (cf. **Fig. S202**).

1693 The negative values of predicted PM_{2.5} residual mass for CSN and NAPS point to model overpredictions in
1694 urban areas and a possible issue with emissions, but what about the consistent positive values of predicted
1695 PM_{2.5} residual mass for IMPROVE linked to consistent model underpredictions in rural areas? The
1696 dominant chemical component in summer in the IMPROVE measurements is PM_{2.5}-TOM (**Fig. S201**); the
1697 model underpredicted this component for all four summers with corresponding large negative seasonal
1698 NMB values for IMPROVE for PM_{2.5}-TOM of -0.47, -0.43, -0.58, and -0.42 (**Table S5S-mr**). Note also
1699 in **Table S5S-mr** that the observed summer means of the PM_{2.5}-EC and TOM components were largest for
1700 summer 2015. According to **Table A4**, for the 2013–2016 period wildfires burned the greatest area in the
1701 U.S. in 2015, and these wildfires were concentrated in California and the Pacific Northwest (Munoz-Alpizar
1702 et al., 2017). Thus, wildfire emissions, which were missing from the model predictions, may have
1703 contributed to the high PM_{2.5}-EC and TOM values measured across the western-focused IMPROVE
1704 network for this season. Examination of **Table S5S** and **Fig. S201** also shows the consistent
1705 underprediction of PM_{2.5}-SO₄ across the IMPROVE network in all seasons and the underprediction of
1706 PM_{2.5}-CM in most seasons, so underpredictions of PM_{2.5}-TOM, SO₄, and CM all contribute to the
1707 underprediction of PM_{2.5} total mass in the rural and western U.S.

1708 **Table S5S-mr** also lists the 2013–2016 seasonal mean *ratios* of observed PM_{2.5} reconstructed mass to
1709 gravimetric PM_{2.5} total mass and predicted PM_{2.5} total mass to gravimetric PM_{2.5} total mass. The observed
1710 2013–2016 all-station mean ratios for the four seasons were 1.00, 0.98, 0.90, and 0.98, indicating very good
1711 agreement on average between the observed PM_{2.5} reconstructed mass and observed gravimetric total mass.
1712 The largest underestimate, 10%, for the summer is consistent with the findings of Malm et al. (2011) and
1713 Hand et al. (2019), which also identified summer as the season with the largest difference. The observed
1714 2013–2016 seasonal mean ratios for the three individual networks were fairly similar to the all-station
1715 ratios: 0.98, 0.98, 0.91, and 0.99 for CSN, 1.04, 0.99, 0.89, and 0.96 for IMPROVE, and 0.97, 0.88, 0.84,
1716 and 0.90 for NAPS. The predicted 2013–2016 all-station mean ratios for the four seasons, by contrast,
1717 showed much more variation: 1.21, 0.95, 0.75, and 1.07, confirming model PM_{2.5} total mass overpredictions
1718 in winter and autumn and large underpredictions in summer. The predicted 2013–2016 seasonal mean
1719 ratios for the three networks again showed much more variation: 1.39, 1.20, 0.96, and 1.34 for CSN, 0.88,
1720 0.66, 0.55, and 0.73 for IMPROVE, and 1.47, 1.54, 1.27, and 1.73 for NAPS. These network-specific
1721 values from **Table S5S-mr** again point to opposing biases associated with urban areas vs. rural areas that
1722 are not visible in the aggregated all-station analysis, but which are visible in differences between **Figs. S200**

1723 and [S202](#) vs. [Fig. S201](#) and are also consistent with the differences between [Figs. S213](#) and [S214](#) for urban
1724 vs. rural stations for hourly PM_{2.5} measurements.

1725 **Figure 15** also provided a comparison of observed and predicted seasonal PM_{2.5} composition in mass units.
1726 It is informative as well to look at the rank order of the observed and predicted PM_{2.5} chemical components
1727 in [Table S5S-mr](#) to compare observed and predicted seasonal mean PM_{2.5} composition. The predicted
1728 seasonal rank order may be impacted by the negative seasonal biases for PM_{2.5}-SO₄ and the positive biases
1729 for PM_{2.5}-EC and SS in all seasons noted in the discussion of [Table S5S](#). The 2013–2016 all-station
1730 observed winter mean PM_{2.5} composition (in descending order) from [Table S5S-mr](#) was PM_{2.5}-TOM, NO₃,
1731 SO₄, NH₄, EC, CM, and SS whereas the 2013–2016 all-station predicted winter mean PM_{2.5} composition
1732 was PM_{2.5}-TOM, NO₃, CM, SO₄, EC, NH₄, and SS. The predicted high contribution from PM_{2.5}-CM was
1733 driven by urban areas, since predicted annual mean PM_{2.5}-CM concentrations were roughly four times the
1734 observed values for the mainly urban CSN and NAPS networks but matched the observed values for the
1735 mainly rural IMPROVE network ([Table S5S-mr](#)). Such urban-rural differences suggest that the observed
1736 and predicted annual mean PM_{2.5} composition should also be examined for the individual networks.
1737 However, the observed ranking of the first four species for the winter season was the same for the three
1738 networks, which points to the high predicted rank of CM as a model issue. Interestingly, for the other three
1739 seasons the top three species for 2013–2016 all-station observed *and* predicted mean PM_{2.5} composition
1740 were TOM, SO₄, and CM, suggesting that the winter season is distinct for the high rank of NO₃ and lower
1741 rank of SO₄. One discrepancy in the predicted 2013–2016 all-station rankings for spring and summer was
1742 SS being in fourth place rather than last place, due to the noted overprediction of PM_{2.5}-SS. Another
1743 discrepancy was the predicted second-place ranking of CM in the autumn, ahead of SO₄ and again linked
1744 to large overpredictions of CM at CSN and NAPS sites.

1745 **Figures S151-S157** present time series of observed and predicted all-station monthly mean concentrations
1746 of seven PM_{2.5} chemical components for 2013–2016 plus corresponding time series of three evaluation
1747 statistics (NMB, FAC2, R). Note that two predicted components, PM_{2.5}-POM and PM_{2.5}-SOM, have been
1748 combined as PM_{2.5}-TOM for comparison with observations ([Fig. S155](#)). These figures complement [Figs.](#)
1749 [S22-S30](#) and [S198](#), [Table S5S](#), and also (chemically) [Figs. S144-S146](#) and [S150](#). Examining each of
1750 [Figs. S151-S157](#) in turn, we note the following features:

- 1751 • For the PM_{2.5}-SO₄ all-station monthly mean concentration time series ([Fig. S151](#)) the predicted summer
1752 maximum was consistent with the observed summer maximum for all years while the predicted
1753 November or January minimum was also consistent with observed minimum values in November or
1754 January. This seasonal cycle, which is the opposite of the observed summer minimum and winter

1755 maximum of the SO₂ monthly mean VMR time series (**Fig. S146**), is consistent with the highest SO₂-
1756 to-H₂SO₄ gas-phase conversion occurring in the summer due to higher OH levels and more daylight
1757 hours. However, all-station monthly NMB values for PM_{2.5}-SO₄ were consistently negative (as were
1758 seasonal NMB values in **Table S55**) whereas all-station monthly NMB values for SO₂ were
1759 consistently positive (**Fig. S146**), suggesting the model underpredicts gas-phase SO₂-to-H₂SO₄
1760 conversion (and not aqueous-phase conversion; cf. **Sect. 4.4**). In addition, both the observed and
1761 predicted all-station monthly mean PM_{2.5}-SO₄ concentration time series, like the all-station SO₂
1762 monthly mean VMR time series, showed a clear monotonic decrease from 2013 to 2016, consistent
1763 with annual SO₂ emission decreases (cf. **Table 1** and **Fig. S22**). Note that all-station monthly NMB,
1764 FAC2, and R values for PM_{2.5}-SO₄ in **Fig. S151** were all worse in the winter than in the warm-season
1765 months, flagging the winter season for particular attention (and consistent with **Table S55**).

- 1766 • Observed and predicted all-station monthly mean PM_{2.5}-NO₃ concentrations, on the other hand, were
1767 highest in the winter and lowest in the summer for all four years (**Figs. S152** and **S23**). This is
1768 consistent with gas-particle partitioning favouring higher PM_{2.5}-NO₃ levels over gaseous HNO₃ in the
1769 cold season (e.g., Malm et al., 2004; Yu et al., 2005), and observed and predicted all-station monthly
1770 mean HNO₃ concentrations were in fact lowest in the winter and highest in the summer (**Figs. S144**
1771 and **S15**). All-station monthly NMB values were negative for most of the year but changed to strongly
1772 positive in September and October for all four years (**Fig. S152**). All-station monthly FAC2 values for
1773 PM_{2.5}-NO₃ were lowest (worst) in June, consistent with the conclusion of Yu et al. (2005) about the
1774 highest uncertainty of predicting PM_{2.5}-NO₃ being for the summer. All-station monthly R values were
1775 roughly constant for all months (**Fig. S152**), but summer R values for the IMPROVE and NAPS
1776 networks were considerably lower than those for CSN (**Table S55**). Note that seasonal PM_{2.5}-NO₃
1777 levels measured by the CSN network were roughly triple those measured by the IMPROVE network in
1778 all seasons (**Table S55**), but again this may be due at least in part to the spatial distribution of PM_{2.5}-
1779 NO₃ (**Fig. S23**) and the eastern focus of the CSN network vs. the western focus of the IMPROVE
1780 network. However, **Table S9-mr** below suggests that urban-rural differences are the dominant factor.
- 1781 • Both observed and predicted all-station monthly mean PM_{2.5}-NH₄ concentrations, like those for PM_{2.5}-
1782 NO₃, were higher in the cold season than the warm season (**Fig. S153**). All-station monthly NMB
1783 values for PM_{2.5}-NH₄, however, were only negative for the winter months (excluding 2016). All-station
1784 monthly FAC2 values and R values for PM_{2.5}-NH₄ were both relatively constant, with 2016 having the
1785 lowest values. Like all-station monthly mean PM_{2.5}-SO₄ concentrations (**Fig. S151**), both observed and
1786 predicted all-station monthly mean PM_{2.5}-NH₄ concentrations showed a clear monotonic decrease from
1787 2013 to 2016, consistent with **Fig. S24**. And as in several other analyses (e.g., **Figs. S89–S90, S147**),
1788 the results for 2016 were something of an outlier.

- 1789 • All-station monthly time series for the two PM_{2.5} carbonaceous components, PM_{2.5}-EC and PM_{2.5}-TOM,
1790 are shown in Figs. [S154](#) and [S155](#), respectively. Both observed and predicted all-station monthly mean
1791 PM_{2.5}-EC concentrations had a spring minimum and winter maximum for all four years (Fig. [S154](#)).
1792 The model had a positive monthly bias for PM_{2.5}-EC year-round, but all-station monthly NMB values
1793 were highest in February and lowest in August for three of the four years (2013–2015). All-station
1794 monthly FAC2 values were fairly constant but had a slight peak in June, and all-station monthly R
1795 values had small dips for all four years in April and July and a large dip for August 2015 (possibly due
1796 to the lack of wildfire emissions; see Sect. 4.2). Note that observed and predicted seasonal PM_{2.5}-EC
1797 values for the mainly urban CSN network were two to five times higher than those for the mainly rural
1798 IMPROVE network (Table [S55](#)), which is consistent with higher urban traffic emissions (cf. Fig. [S25](#)).
1799 Hand et al. (2014) also noted this difference and referred to it as the urban excess. However, predicted
1800 seasonal mean PM_{2.5}-EC values for the mainly urban CSN network were roughly twice the observed
1801 values whereas observed and predicted seasonal mean values for the IMPROVE network in Table [S55](#)
1802 were comparable, flagging the representation of urban PM_{2.5}-EC emissions as a possible concern.
- 1803 • All-station monthly statistics for observed and predicted monthly mean PM_{2.5}-TOM concentrations
1804 (Fig. [S155](#)) were similar to those for PM_{2.5}-EC with three exceptions. One was the summertime peak
1805 present in both observed and predicted PM_{2.5}-TOM time series, which suggests a major contribution
1806 from one or more non-combustion emission sources. Another was the underprediction of PM_{2.5}-TOM
1807 in the warm season vs. the small overpredictions of PM_{2.5}-EC. The third exception were the all-station
1808 monthly R scores, which like those for PM_{2.5}-EC also have dips both in April and in July and August,
1809 but the dips for PM_{2.5}-TOM were more pronounced. While missing wildfire emissions are a possible
1810 explanation for the July–August dip, the April dip might be the result of missing emissions from
1811 prescribed burns, including both forest and agricultural burning (e.g., Pouliot et al., 2017). Urban-rural
1812 differences likely also influenced seasonal mean PM_{2.5}-TOM concentrations, since both observed and
1813 predicted CSN monthly values were roughly three to five times those of IMPROVE, and the model was
1814 biased high in the winter and slightly low in the summer for CSN but was biased low year-round for
1815 IMPROVE (Table [S55](#)).
- 1816 • Model performance was considerably less good for PM_{2.5}-CM. The time series of observed all-station
1817 monthly mean PM_{2.5}-CM concentrations displayed a strong summer peak that was missed by the model
1818 (Fig. [S156](#)). All-station monthly NMB scores were on the order of 200% in the winter for all four
1819 years, all-station monthly FAC2 values were only about 0.30 for all months, and all-station monthly R
1820 values were low year-round but were near zero in the warm season. Note, however, that the model was
1821 biased high for all seasons for CSN (mainly urban stations) but was biased low for many seasons for
1822 IMPROVE (mainly rural stations) (Table [S55](#)). Road dust from paved and unpaved roads is the

1823 dominant anthropogenic source of PM_{2.5}-CM emissions, which suggests that emissions from this source
1824 may have been too high in the simulations, especially in urban areas in the cold season. In particular,
1825 winter NMB values for PM_{2.5}-CM for NAPS ranged from 3.1 to 4.4, raising questions about the efficacy
1826 of the meteorological modulation scheme in the RAQDPS023 (Moran et al., 2026), which should
1827 strongly lower fugitive dust emissions in northern climes in the winter.

1828 • For PM_{2.5}-SS both the observed and predicted all-station monthly peaks occurred in the spring, but the
1829 model was biased high (~100%) year-round for all four years (Fig. S157). All-station monthly FAC2
1830 values showed little year-to-year variation and ranged from 0.20 in the cold season to 0.40 in the warm
1831 season, while all-station monthly R scores were on the order of 0.60 for most months, comparable to R
1832 scores for PM_{2.5}-NO₃ (Fig. S152) and PM_{2.5}-EC (Fig. S154).

1833 Another monthly analysis of PM_{2.5} speciation is provided by Figs. S180 to S186, which compare monthly
1834 density scatterplots of daily concentrations of seven PM_{2.5} chemical components for the four mid-season
1835 months of each year from 2013 to 2016. As already noted in the discussion of Figs. S22-S30, differences
1836 between seasons were more marked than differences between years, and similar behaviour between seasons
1837 vs. between years can also be seen in these scatterplots. This set of density scatterplots also provides visual
1838 confirmation of some other performance evaluation results that were already discussed. For example,
1839 PM_{2.5}-SO₄ predictions show the most scatter in January (Fig. S180), consistent with the low FAC2 values
1840 for this month (Fig. S151) and high CRMSE and NMAE values for this season (Table S5S). The
1841 PM_{2.5}-NO₃ density scatterplots (Fig. S181) display a large predicted relative standard deviation (i.e., CV =
1842 σ_M/\bar{M}) compared to the PM_{2.5}-SO₄ scatterplots. April and July scatterplots for PM_{2.5}-NO₃ indicate model
1843 underpredictions and high scatter at lower observed values, consistent with the time series of monthly NMB
1844 and FAC2 scores in Fig. S152 (and seasonal scores in Table S5S). The monthly density scatterplots for
1845 PM_{2.5}-NH₄ (Fig. S182) show less month-to-month variation than those for PM_{2.5}-SO₄ and PM_{2.5}-NO₃, likely
1846 due to the anti-correlation of PM_{2.5}-SO₄ and PM_{2.5}-NO₃ maxima. The monthly density scatterplots for
1847 PM_{2.5}-EC (Fig. S183) and PM_{2.5}-TOM (Fig. S184) are broadly similar, reflecting the broad similarities
1848 between Figs. S154 and S155. Note that the PM_{2.5}-EC scatterplots have broad marginal distributions,
1849 suggesting a wide range of emission sources of different strengths. The poor performance for PM_{2.5}-CM
1850 noted above in the discussion of Fig. S156 is echoed by Fig. S185, which shows large scatter (i.e., low
1851 FAC2 scores) and limited linearity (i.e., low R scores). Lastly, the scatterplots for PM_{2.5}-SS have the most
1852 scatter and lowest linearity for January (Fig. S186), consistent with Fig. S157. Both observed and
1853 predicted PM_{2.5}-SS size distributions are very broad, consistent with large relative standard deviations.

1854 Table S9 stratifies Table S5A geographically by breaking out annual performance statistics by region for
1855 daily PM_{2.5} chemical components for 2013–2016 for the four quadrants shown in Fig. S7. Regional

1856 differences in these statistics are obvious. For example, annual R scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$ are highest for EUS
1857 and lowest for WCA for all four years, annual FAC2 scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-EC}$ are highest for EUS and lowest
1858 for WCA for all four years, and annual NMB and NMAE scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-CM}$ are lowest for WUS and
1859 annual R scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-CM}$ are highest for ECA for all four years.

1860 The analysis of [Table S9](#) also suggests the value of analogous figures to the seasonal North American and
1861 network perspective on $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ composition of [Figs. 15](#) and [S200–S202](#) that would instead show an annual
1862 regional perspective. To generate these four additional figures, another table, [Table S9-mr](#), was
1863 constructed. This table is closely related to [Table S9](#), but like [Table S5S-mr](#) it was limited to complete
1864 daily $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ speciation and daily gravimetric $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass measurements. Another benefit from [Table](#)
1865 [S9S-mr](#) is that it separates the CSN network into western urban and eastern urban subsets and the
1866 IMPROVE network into western rural and eastern rural subsets, which provides insight into which of the
1867 west-east and urban-rural differences between these two networks is the more important factor.

1868 [Figures S205–S208](#) show regional differences in annual $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical composition, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ reconstructed
1869 mass, and gravimetric $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass, for each year from 2013–2016 based on the observed and predicted
1870 (a) all-station, (b) CSN-only, (c) IMPROVE-only, and (d) NAPS-only annual-mean $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical
1871 component values, respectively, from [Table S9-mr](#). Looking first at annual $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical composition
1872 in [Fig. S205](#), it is evident that predicted all-station annual chemical composition for WUS and EUS was
1873 very good for all four years, although the known model underprediction of $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ and overprediction
1874 of $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-CM}$ can be discerned for EUS. There was also very good agreement for these two regions between
1875 observed annual $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ reconstructed mass and observed annual gravimetric $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass and between
1876 predicted annual $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass and observed annual gravimetric $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass. However, a different
1877 picture emerges when [Figs. S206](#) and [S207](#), the corresponding CSN-only and IMPROVE-only figures, are
1878 examined. In [Fig. S206](#) for CSN, agreement was also very good for EUS for predicted annual $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
1879 chemical composition and for both annual reconstructed and predicted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass vs. observed
1880 gravimetric $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass for all four years, but for WUS the $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-EC}$, TOM, and CM concentrations
1881 are all significantly overpredicted as is predicted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass. By contrast, in [Fig. S207](#) for IMPROVE,
1882 predicted annual $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$, NO_3 , TOM, and CM concentrations and predicted $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass were all
1883 underpredicted for both U.S. regions while observed $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ residual errors were small for the western U.S.
1884 but somewhat larger and positive for EUS. [Figures S206](#) and [S207](#) thus show that the model overpredicts
1885 annual $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical components for urban U.S. locations in WUS but underpredicts them at rural WUS
1886 and EUS locations, and that the good agreement seen for the two U.S. regions in [Fig. S205](#) results from
1887 compensating errors in these two regions between urban and rural stations.

1888 Turning to the two Canadian regions in **Fig. S205** (and **Fig. S208**), annual PM_{2.5}-EC, TOM, and CM
1889 concentrations were all overpredicted in both regions for all four years as was predicted PM_{2.5} total mass.
1890 In fact the predicted regional carbonaceous component for WCA, which consists of PM_{2.5}-EC and TOM,
1891 was considerably larger than in the other three regions for 2013–2015. This results in an obvious difference
1892 in model performance between WCA and WUS. If we refer back to **Table S9-mr**, however, we see that
1893 the values for WCA were based on very small samples, consisting of measurements from only two stations
1894 (Edmonton McIntyre, Burnaby South) for 2013, two stations (Burnaby South, Abbotsford) for 2014 and
1895 2015, and one station for 2016 (Abbotsford). The WCA regional statistics are thus not regionally
1896 representative, but they do provide information about model performance at specific urban and suburban
1897 locations. We also see in **Fig. S205** that observed PM_{2.5} residual errors were small but positive for both
1898 Canadian regions but were larger than the corresponding values for the two U.S. regions.

1899 Note for **Fig. S205** that the observed annual-mean regional values of gravimetric PM_{2.5} total mass were
1900 highest for EUS and lowest for WUS for all four years, while ECA was second-highest for 2014–2016.
1901 **Table S9S-mr** also lists the 2013–2016 annual mean *ratios* of observed PM_{2.5} reconstructed mass to
1902 gravimetric PM_{2.5} total mass and predicted PM_{2.5} total mass to gravimetric PM_{2.5} total mass for the four
1903 regions. The observed 2013–2016 all-station mean ratios were 0.89, 0.89, 0.99, and 0.94 for WCA, ECA,
1904 WUS, and EUS, respectively, indicating fairly good agreement on average between the observed PM_{2.5}
1905 reconstructed mass and observed gravimetric total mass for the two Canadian regions and good agreement
1906 for the two U.S. regions. The predicted 2013–2016 all-station mean ratios for the four regions showed
1907 considerably more variation: 2.10, 1.35, 1.01, and 0.94. These values are consistent with **Fig. S205**. The
1908 differences between **Figs. S206** and **S207** can also be seen in the CSN-only predicted mean ratios of 1.80
1909 and 1.06 for WUS and EUS vs. the IMPROVE-only predicted mean ratios of 0.64 and 0.71.

1910 **S3.3.3 Precipitation chemistry**

1911 **Table S6A** is an expansion of **Table 6**. It lists values of 12 annual evaluation statistics for weekly
1912 predictions of SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, and NH₄⁺ concentrations in precipitation and wet deposition for 2013–2016 for
1913 the CAPMoN and NADP networks individually and combined. The majority of scores were comparable
1914 between the two networks. For example, observed annual mean SO₄²⁻ weekly concentrations in
1915 precipitation declined in both networks, from 0.81 to 0.57 mg·L⁻¹ in CAPMoN and from 0.81 to 0.62 mg·L⁻¹
1916 in NADP, again consistent with reductions in SO₂ emissions in both Canada and the U.S. (**Table 1**)
1917 However, there are also some differences between the individual CAPMoN and NADP annual scores in
1918 **Table S6A** that tend to favour CAPMoN. Recall that differences in the precipitation scores in this table
1919 between CAPMoN and NADP were already discussed in **Sect. S3.1**. Looking at the other six predictands
1920 in **Table S6A**, annual R scores for SO₄²⁻ weekly concentration in precipitation were somewhat higher for

1921 CAPMoN (0.39–0.50) than NADP (0.24–0.40). Annual NMB scores for SO_4^- weekly wet deposition were
1922 higher for CAPMoN (0.11–0.25) than NADP (-0.08 to 0.04), but annual R scores were higher for CAPMoN
1923 (0.56–0.69) than NADP (0.48–0.57). Annual NMAE scores for NO_3^- weekly concentration in precipitation
1924 were lower for CAPMoN (0.43–0.49) than NADP (0.53–0.58) and annual R scores were higher for
1925 CAPMoN (0.51–0.69) than NADP (0.45–0.50). Annual NMAE scores for NO_3^- weekly wet deposition
1926 were also lower for CAPMoN (0.42–0.47) than NADP (0.53–0.56) and annual R scores were also
1927 considerably higher for CAPMoN (0.71–0.76) than NADP (0.44–0.57). Significant differences in scores
1928 were also apparent for NH_4^+ weekly concentration in precipitation: annual NMB scores were lower for
1929 CAPMoN (0.0–0.15) than NADP (0.26–0.44), annual NMAE scores were lower for CAPMoN (0.59–0.67)
1930 than NADP (0.80–0.99), and annual R scores were higher for CAPMoN (0.54–0.71) than NADP (0.36–
1931 0.46). Lastly, annual R scores for NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition were higher for CAPMoN (0.66–0.70) than
1932 NADP (0.46–0.57).

1933 **Figures S109–S136** show the spatial distributions of station-specific annual values of four statistics (MB,
1934 NMB, CRMSE, and R) for 2013–2016 for the combined CAPMoN and NADP networks for predictions of
1935 SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ weekly concentrations in precipitation, weekly precipitation, and SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and
1936 NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition. Some regional differences are evident in many of these figures. For SO_4^-
1937 weekly concentration in precipitation, station annual MB values are positive overall in eastern Canada and
1938 the northeastern U.S. but tend to be negative elsewhere (**Fig. S109**), while station annual R scores tend to
1939 be lower in the west and higher in the east (**Fig. S112**). For NO_3^- weekly concentration in precipitation,
1940 with the exception of some Great Lakes states the majority of sites have small negative annual MB values
1941 that are larger in the west (**Fig. S113**), while station annual R scores also tend to be lower in the west and
1942 higher in the east (**Fig. S116**). For NH_4^+ weekly concentration in precipitation, on the other hand, the
1943 majority of stations have positive annual MB values (**Fig. S117**), while the highest annual R scores are
1944 found in the west (**Fig. S120**).

1945 Wet deposition is arguably harder for the model to predict since it requires accurate predictions of both
1946 precipitation amounts and ion concentrations in precipitation. As noted by Moran et al. (2026),
1947 precipitation forecasts are made by the GEM meteorological model and are not affected by chemistry.
1948 **Section S3.1** provides a discussion of precipitation evaluation statistics in **Table S6A** and **Figs. S121–S124**.
1949 The spatial distributions of station annual MB values for SO_4^- weekly wet deposition (**Fig. S125**) and NO_3^-
1950 weekly wet deposition (**Fig. S129**) have similarities to those for weekly precipitation (**Fig. S121**), including
1951 underpredictions over the southeastern U.S., but they are more similar to **Figs. S109** and **S113** for SO_4^- and
1952 NO_3^- concentrations in precipitation. Station annual R values for SO_4^- and NO_3^- weekly wet deposition
1953 (**Figs. S128** and **S132**) also tend to be lower in the west and higher in the east and are lower than those for

1954 weekly precipitation (**Fig. S124**; see also **Table S6A**). The spatial distributions of station annual MB values
1955 for NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition. (**Fig. S133**) looks similar to **Fig. S129** for NO_3^- weekly wet deposition,
1956 but with reduced biases over the southeastern U.S.

1957 **Figures S31-S33** show the predicted spatial distributions of *seasonal* mean SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ weekly
1958 concentrations in precipitation over North America for 2013–2016 and 2021/22, while **Figs. S34-S36** and
1959 **S10** show the predicted spatial distributions of seasonal mean SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition
1960 and precipitation. Seasonal mean SO_4^- weekly concentrations in precipitation (**Fig. S31**) did not display
1961 interseasonal variations as large as those for seasonal mean $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ daily concentration in air (**Fig. S22**),
1962 but year-to-year decreases in seasonal mean SO_4^- weekly concentration in precipitation can be seen from
1963 2013 to 2021/22 in winter, spring, and summer. Seasonal mean NO_3^- weekly concentrations in precipitation
1964 (**Fig. S32**) did display more pronounced variations between seasons, especially between winter and
1965 spring/autumn, and year-to-year decreases were also evident for winter and spring. The spatial distributions
1966 of seasonal mean NO_3^- weekly concentration in precipitation, however, were quite distinct from the spatial
1967 distributions of seasonal mean $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$ daily concentrations in air (**Fig. S23**), which were much more
1968 compact. The reason is that $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$ and HNO_3 concentrations in air both contribute to NO_3^- weekly
1969 concentration in precipitation, so that **Fig. S23** for $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$ needs to be combined with **Fig. S15** for HNO_3
1970 to provide a representative comparison with **Fig. S32**. The spatial distributions of seasonal mean NH_4^+
1971 weekly concentration in precipitation (**Fig. S33**) were a bit surprising in that elevated levels were predicted
1972 over the U.S. Plains states in the summer and autumn but the highest levels were predicted to occur over
1973 California. There is consistency, however, with the spatial distribution of annual NH_3 emissions shown in
1974 **Fig. S1**, with peak emissions located over the Central Valley of California. The seasonal cycle of NH_4^+
1975 weekly concentration in precipitation can also be seen to be much stronger than year-to-year variations.
1976 Note that $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NH}_4$ and NH_3 concentrations in air both contribute to NH_4^+ weekly concentration in
1977 precipitation, so **Fig. S24** for seasonal mean $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NH}_4$ daily concentration in air and **Fig. S16** for seasonal
1978 mean NH_3 biweekly concentration in air need to be combined for comparison with **Fig. S33**.

1979 Turning to wet deposition, spatial distributions of seasonal mean SO_4^- weekly wet deposition for 2013–
1980 2016 and 2021/22 shown in **Fig. S34** were largest over eastern North America, whereas spatial distributions
1981 of seasonal mean NO_3^- and NH_4^+ wet deposition were large over central North America as well as eastern
1982 North America (**Figs. S35-S36**). Note too that when seasonal mean concentration in precipitation fields
1983 are compared with seasonal mean wet deposition fields (i.e., **Figs. S31** vs. **S34** for SO_4^- , **S32** vs. **S35** for
1984 NO_3^- , and **S33** vs. **S36** for NH_4^+), peaks in the wet deposition fields are shifted eastward. The most extreme
1985 example was NH_4^+ wet deposition in summer. This shift is consistent with predicted spatial distributions of
1986 seasonal precipitation (**Fig. S10**), which tend to increase from west to east. It is clear from these figures

1987 that the spatial distributions of seasonal precipitation were quite different from the distributions for seasonal
1988 concentration in precipitation and wet deposition as the precipitation field is independent of pollutant
1989 emissions, but the seasonal precipitation fields in **Fig. S10** provide the link between **Figs. S31-S33** and
1990 **Figs. S34-S36**.

1991 **Table S6S** complements **Table S6A** by listing seasonal evaluation statistics for predictions of weekly
1992 concentrations in precipitation and weekly wet deposition for 2013–2016 by network,. It is clear from
1993 **Table S6S** that seasonal model skill was consistent overall from year to year but sometimes varied
1994 markedly between seasons. For example, **Figs. S34–S36** suggest that seasonal NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition
1995 had the largest seasonal variation of the three major ions, a finding supported by **Table S6S** for both
1996 observed and predicted all-station seasonal means. It is also helpful to compare scores from **Table S6S**
1997 with **Figs. S158–S160**, which present plots of all-station annual time series of five monthly evaluation
1998 statistics (\bar{O} , \bar{M} , NMB, FAC2, R) for predicted SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ weekly concentrations in precipitation
1999 for 2013–2016, and with **Figs. S162–S164**, which present the corresponding all-station annual time series
2000 of monthly statistics for predicted SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition. All-station seasonal NMB
2001 scores for SO_4^- weekly concentration in precipitation were only negative in three springs and summer 2013
2002 (cf. **Fig. S158**), whereas those for NO_3^- weekly concentration in precipitation and SO_4^- and NO_3^- weekly
2003 wet deposition were negative in both spring and summer for all four years (cf. **Figs. S159, S162, S163**).
2004 By contrast, all-station seasonal NMB scores for NH_4^+ weekly concentration in precipitation and weekly
2005 wet deposition both had pronounced positive peaks in the summer, while scores were negative in winter for
2006 NH_4^+ weekly concentration in precipitation but negative in spring for NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition (cf.
2007 **Figs. S160** and **S164**).

2008 All-station seasonal NMB scores for SO_4^- and NO_3^- weekly concentration in precipitation in **Table S6S** fell
2009 into ranges of -0.20 to 0.36 and -0.26 to 0.14, respectively, while all-station seasonal NMB scores for SO_4^-
2010 and NO_3^- weekly wet deposition fell into ranges of -0.17 to 0.37 and -0.39 to 0.32. The corresponding
2011 ranges for NH_4^+ are -0.25 to 1.25 and -0.07 to 0.46. In comparison, Simon et al. (2012) reported (10%,
2012 90%) quantile values for NMB scores for accumulated seasonal and annual SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ wet
2013 deposition of (-0.09, 0.38), (-0.45, 0.19), and (-0.33, 0.28), respectively. All-station seasonal NMAE scores
2014 for SO_4^- and NO_3^- weekly concentration in precipitation fell into ranges of 0.53–0.82 and 0.47–0.65,
2015 respectively, while all-station seasonal NMAE scores for SO_4^- and NO_3^- weekly wet deposition fell into
2016 very similar ranges of 0.53–0.84 and 0.46–0.61. Simon et al. (2012) suggested top-quartile NMAE scores
2017 for accumulated seasonal SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ wet deposition of 0.61, 0.51, and 0.57, which would be
2018 expected to be larger for weekly statistics. However, all-station summer NMAE scores for NH_4^+ weekly
2019 concentration in precipitation and wet deposition were higher, ranging from 1.10 to 1.57 and from 0.88 to

2020 0.91, respectively. The lowest all-station seasonal FAC2 scores for SO_4^- weekly concentration in
2021 precipitation and weekly wet deposition were usually associated with winter (cf. **Figs. S158** and **S162**),
2022 whereas the lowest all-station seasonal FAC2 scores for NO_3^- and NH_4^+ weekly concentrations in
2023 precipitation and weekly wet deposition were associated with summer (cf. **Figs. S159–S160** and **S163–**
2024 **S164**). For all-station seasonal R scores, on the other hand, the lowest seasonal values were usually
2025 associated with summer for all three species for both weekly concentrations in precipitation and weekly
2026 wet deposition (cf. **Figs. S158–S160, S162–S164**).

2027 The discussion of **Table S6A** noted some differences in annual scores between CAPMoN and NADP that
2028 were hidden in the all-station scores. There were also some comparable differences in **Table S6S** between
2029 CAPMoN and NADP seasonal scores. We can see from **Figs. S158** and **S162** that the highest all-station
2030 monthly NMB values for SO_4^- weekly concentration in precipitation and SO_4^- weekly wet deposition
2031 occurred in the winter for 2013-2016. Seasonal NMB values for SO_4^- weekly concentration in precipitation
2032 in **Table S6S** were highest in the winter for both networks, but they were higher for CAPMoN (0.38–1.14)
2033 than for NADP (0.05–0.28). The same was true for wintertime overpredictions of SO_4^- weekly wet
2034 deposition, where the range for CAPMoN was 0.40–0.65 vs. a lower range for NADP of 0.15–0.36. This
2035 north-south difference might be useful information for trying to understand the winter overpredictions of
2036 SO_4^- concentration in precipitation and SO_4^- wet deposition. For NO_3^- weekly concentration in
2037 precipitation and NO_3^- weekly wet deposition, **Figs. S159** and **S163** showed that the highest all-station
2038 monthly R values occurred in the winter. Seasonal R scores for NO_3^- weekly concentration in precipitation
2039 in **Table S6S** were also highest in winter for both networks, but winter CAPMoN values had a range of
2040 0.72-0.84 whereas the range of NADP values was 0.56–0.63. Similarly, seasonal R scores for NO_3^- weekly
2041 wet deposition were highest in winter for both networks, but CAPMoN values had a range of 0.78–0.81 vs.
2042 0.52–0.67 for NADP. And for NH_4^+ weekly concentration in precipitation and NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition,
2043 **Figs. S160** and **S164** showed that the highest all-station monthly NMB values and lowest monthly R values
2044 occurred in the summer. Seasonal NMB scores for NH_4^+ weekly concentration in precipitation in
2045 **Table S6S** were also highest in the summer for both networks, but summer CAPMoN values had a range
2046 of 0.11–0.48 vs. 0.77–1.33 for NADP. If NH_3 emissions were too high in the summer, then this difference
2047 in network NMB scores suggests that the issue might be more serious in the U.S. Seasonal NMAE values
2048 for NH_4^+ weekly concentration in precipitation were also highest in summer for both networks, but summer
2049 CAPMoN values had a range of 0.69–0.88 vs. 1.14–1.65 for NADP. Seasonal R scores for NH_4^+ weekly
2050 concentration in precipitation in **Table S6S** were generally lowest in the summer for both networks, but
2051 summer CAPMoN values had a range of 0.42–0.66 whereas NADP values had a lower range of 0.26–0.40.

2052 Lastly, seasonal R values for NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition were generally lowest in the summer for both
2053 networks, but summer CAPMoN values had a range of 0.63–0.68 vs. 0.46–0.51 for NADP.

2054 Examining **Figs. S158–S160** further, we see that monthly NMB scores for SO_4^- and NO_3^- weekly
2055 concentrations in precipitation ranged for most months from -0.30 to 0.30, whereas weekly NH_4^+
2056 concentration in precipitation was overpredicted in the warm season, reaching peak values from 0.70 to
2057 1.70 in July (**Fig. S160**). All-station monthly FAC2 scores were lowest (worst) in winter for SO_4^- weekly
2058 concentration in precipitation but also had a secondary minimum in the summer (**Fig. S158**), whereas
2059 monthly FAC2 scores for NO_3^- and NH_4^+ weekly concentrations in precipitation were lowest in July
2060 (**Figs. S159–S160**). All-station monthly R scores for weekly concentrations in precipitation for all three
2061 species were higher in the cold season than the warm season. The impact of decreasing annual SO_2
2062 emissions from 2013 to 2016 was also evident in both observed and predicted monthly means of SO_4^-
2063 weekly concentration in precipitation (**Fig. S158**).

2064 As discussed in **Sect. S3.1**, **Fig. S161** presents all-station annual time series of five monthly statistics for
2065 GEM-predicted weekly precipitation for 2013–2016. **Figures S162–S164** present all-station annual time
2066 series of the same five monthly statistics for predicted weekly wet deposition of SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ ,
2067 respectively, for 2013–2016. Observed monthly mean SO_4^- and NO_3^- weekly wet deposition were both
2068 highest in the summer and lowest in the winter (**Figs. S162** and **S163**), but the model predicted roughly
2069 uniform levels for all months, with overpredictions in the cold-season months for all years and
2070 underpredictions in the warm-season months, similar to the all-station monthly NMB scores for SO_4^- and
2071 NO_3^- weekly concentrations in precipitation (**Figs. S158–S159**). The monthly NMB scores for NH_4^+
2072 weekly wet deposition (**Fig. S164**) were quite different, however: the model reproduced the peak deposition
2073 observed in the spring months but had a large positive bias (up to 0.60) in the summer months. The all-
2074 station annual time series of monthly FAC2 values for SO_4^- weekly wet deposition (**Fig. S162**) was similar
2075 to the annual time series for SO_4^- weekly concentration in precipitation (**Fig. S158**), while the all-station
2076 annual time series of monthly FAC2 values for NO_3^- and NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition (**Figs. S163–S164**)
2077 were similar to those for weekly precipitation (**Fig. S161**) and NO_3^- and NH_4^+ weekly concentrations in
2078 precipitation (**Figs. S159–S160**). All-station monthly R values, on the other hand, fell mainly into the 0.40
2079 to 0.60 range for all three ions (**Figs. S162–S164**), but with slightly higher values for NO_3^- weekly wet
2080 deposition. Note that both observed and predicted monthly values of SO_4^- weekly wet deposition show
2081 decreases from 2013 to 2016 (**Fig. S162**), similar to **Fig. S158** for SO_4^- weekly concentration in
2082 precipitation and in agreement with decreasing SO_2 annual emissions over this period (**Table 1**).

2083 In another monthly analysis, **Figs. S187–S193** compare all-station monthly density scatterplots for
2084 predictions of SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ weekly concentrations in precipitation, weekly precipitation, and SO_4^- ,
2085 NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition for the 16 mid-season months of 2013 to 2016. A number of
2086 qualitative features of interest can be seen in these figures. Predictions of SO_4^- weekly concentration in
2087 precipitation for January showed more scatter than for the other three mid-season months (**Fig. S187**),
2088 consistent with the lower seasonal FAC2 scores in the winter listed in **Table S6S** and the lower monthly
2089 FAC2 scores in the winter shown in **Fig. S158**. Predictions of NH_4^+ weekly concentration in precipitation
2090 (**Fig. S189**) displayed more scatter for all months than did those for SO_4^- and NO_3^- weekly concentrations
2091 in precipitation (**Figs. S187–S188**); this is consistent with the lower monthly FAC2 scores for NH_4^+ weekly
2092 concentration in precipitation shown in **Fig. S160** vs. the monthly FAC2 scores for SO_4^- and NO_3^- weekly
2093 concentrations in precipitation plotted in **Figs. S158** and **S159**. The overpredictions of NH_4^+ weekly
2094 concentration in precipitation in summer noted in **Fig. S160** are also evident in **Fig. S189** for July.
2095 Similarly, the overpredictions of NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition in summer evident in **Fig. S164** can also be
2096 seen in **Fig. S193** for July for all four years.

2097 Lastly, **Table S10** compares annual statistics *by region* and by network (CAPMoN, NADP, combined) for
2098 2013–2016 for predictions of SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ weekly concentrations in precipitation, weekly
2099 precipitation, and SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ weekly wet deposition. The regions correspond to the four
2100 continental quadrants shown in **Fig. S7**. In essence this table provides an aggregated summary of the
2101 geographic variations in model performance by measurement station presented in **Figs. S109–S136**. One
2102 interesting feature of this table is that the Canadian CAPMoN network has measurements in the EUS and
2103 the U.S. NADP network has measurements in both ECA and WCA. This is due to the co-location of
2104 samplers from both networks at several locations (see **Fig. S6c**) to assess between-network biases (Sirois
2105 et al., 2000; Wetherbee et al., 2010; Feng et al., 2023) and to support other initiatives. A second feature is
2106 that **Figs. S34–S36** showed that SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ wet deposition was predicted to be considerably
2107 higher over eastern and central North America than western North America. This regional west-east
2108 gradient in wet deposition was confirmed by **Table S10**, in which observed annual mean wet deposition
2109 values from NADP for the EUS were all roughly two or more times greater than those for the WUS. Zhang
2110 et al. (2018) presented similar findings for the WUS vs. EUS for an earlier period. As well **Table S10**
2111 shows that annual NMAE scores for SO_4^- weekly concentration in precipitation for NADP were higher for
2112 the WUS than the EUS for 2013–2016 while annual FAC2 and R scores were lower. Annual NMB scores
2113 for NO_3^- weekly concentration in precipitation for NADP were more negative in the WUS than the EUS,
2114 which is consistent with **Fig. S114**. Lastly, annual NMB values for SO_4^- weekly wet deposition were higher

2115 for the WUS than the EUS, while most annual NMAE scores for SO_4^- , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ weekly wet
2116 deposition fields were higher and annual FAC2 and R scores were lower for the WUS than the EUS.

2117 **S4 Discussion**

2118 **S4.1 Comparison with RAQDPS forecast performance for 2010-2019**

2119 **Figures S215–S219** show corresponding time series plots to **Fig. 19** for all-station seasonal MB, NMB,
2120 NMAE, RMSE, and FAC2 scores for NO_2 , O_3 , and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ for the 2010–2022 time period, respectively. It
2121 can be seen from **Figs. S215** and **S216** that seasonal MB and NMB values for NO_2 for the operational
2122 RAQDPS forecasts increased (worsened) from 2010 to 2019, those for O_3 remained close to zero, whereas
2123 seasonal MB and NMB values for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ decreased, initially improving but then worsening later in the
2124 period. Seasonal cycles were also evident in the MB and NMB time series for the three pollutants.
2125 Maximum seasonal NMB values for NO_2 occurred in the summer and minimum values occurred in the
2126 winter for both the operational forecasts and the RAQDPS-OP023 hindcasts. Seasonal NMB values for O_3
2127 for the operational forecasts behaved like those for NO_2 from 2010 until winter 2016, after which maximum
2128 seasonal NMB values for O_3 occurred in autumn and minimum values occurred in spring. The
2129 superimposed seasonal NMB values for the RAQDPS-OP023 hindcasts, by contrast, had spring minimum
2130 values and winter maximum values (cf. **Table S3S**), and the seasonal shift compared to the operational
2131 forecasts for 2013–2016 can be seen in **Fig. S216**. Note that RAQDPS-OP016, a major model upgrade,
2132 was introduced in September 2016 (**Table A3**). Variations of seasonal MB and NMB scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ were
2133 less cyclical, but from 2015 to 2021 minimum (negative) values of seasonal MB and NMB for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
2134 occurred in the summer when peak BB emissions typically occur (see **Sect. 4.2**). **Figure S216** also shows
2135 species-specific values of “acceptable” and “good” benchmark thresholds for NMB scores recommended
2136 by Emery et al. (2017) for O_3 and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and by Zhai et al. (2024) for NO_2 . Most of the seasonal NMB
2137 scores for all three species met at least the “acceptable” benchmarks, though NO_2 was an exception from
2138 2017 to 2019.

2139 The time series of all-station seasonal NMAE scores shown in **Fig. S217** were also different for each
2140 pollutant for the 2010-2019 period. Seasonal NMAE scores for NO_2 for 2010-2019 showed strong seasonal
2141 variations, with maximum (worst) NMAE scores occurring in the summer and minimum NMAE scores
2142 occurring in the winter, similar to the NMB scores. The seasonal NMAE scores for O_3 also displayed
2143 seasonal variations, though smaller than those for NO_2 , where the lowest NMAE scores occur for the spring
2144 season. Cyclical seasonal variations were even less pronounced for the seasonal NMAE scores for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$.
2145 No trend is obvious for the NO_2 seasonal NMAE scores, but both O_3 and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ seasonal NMAE scores
2146 appear to be trending slowly downwards (i.e., improving). The superimposed RAQDPS-OP023 seasonal

2147 NMAE scores for 2013–2016 are lower (i.e., better) for NO₂ and O₃ but comparable for PM_{2.5}. [Figure S217](#)
2148 also shows the species-specific values of “acceptable” and “good” benchmarks for NMAE scores
2149 recommended by Emery et al. (2017) for O₃ and PM_{2.5} and by Zhai et al. (2024) for NO₂. Only RAQDPS-
2150 OP023 seasonal NMAE scores for NO₂ for 2013–2016 and 2021 winter met the “acceptable” benchmark.

2151 The time series of all-station seasonal RMSE scores shown in [Fig. S218](#) were different as well for each
2152 pollutant for the 2010–2019 period. Seasonal RMSE values for NO₂ displayed relatively small variations
2153 until autumn 2016, after which they increased somewhat. Two possible contributing factors to this increase
2154 are (a) the introduction of RAQDPS016 in September 2016 ([Table A3](#)), which included a change to the
2155 model vertical discretization that effectively decreased the thickness of the lowest model layer, and (b) the
2156 continued reliance on the 2011 U.S. emissions inventory despite large decreases in U.S. NO_x emissions that
2157 occurred after 2011 (e.g., Moran et al., 2018; Foley et al., 2023). For O₃ there was little overall change in
2158 seasonal RMSE values from 2010–2019 but there were cyclical variations, with maximum (worst) values
2159 in summer and minimum (best) values in winter. For the seasonal RMSE time series for PM_{2.5} for the
2160 operational RAQDPS forecasts, however, there was an overall downward trend towards lower values (i.e.,
2161 improvement) over this period. The superimposed RAQDPS-OP023 scores for 2013–2016 are lower
2162 (better) for NO₂ and O₃ but are higher for PM_{2.5}. Note that the spike in the RAQDPS-OP023 seasonal
2163 RMSE score for PM_{2.5} in spring 2016 may have been influenced by very high PM_{2.5} measurements
2164 associated with the Fort McMurray, Alberta wildfire in May 2016 (e.g., Vaillant, 2023) and the lack of
2165 wildfire emissions in the RAQDPS-OP023 (see [Sect. 4.2](#)).

2166 Lastly, time series of all-station seasonal FAC2 scores are shown in [Fig. S219](#). The seasonal FAC2 time
2167 series for NO₂ and O₃ both exhibited cyclical seasonal variations (winter peaks for NO₂, spring peaks for
2168 O₃), and both exhibit a steady improvement with time (i.e., a trend towards higher values). The seasonal
2169 FAC2 time series for PM_{2.5}, on the other hand, showed some slight improvement in the first eight years,
2170 but then scores began to decline toward the end of 2018. Note that a new operational system version,
2171 RAQDPS020, was introduced in September 2018 with changes to both model code and input emissions
2172 ([Table A3](#); Moran et al., 2018). Interestingly, the superimposed RAQDPS-OP023 seasonal FAC2 scores
2173 for 2013–2016 are markedly higher (better) for NO₂, are comparable for O₃ (though with a tighter range),
2174 but again are lower (worse) for PM_{2.5}. One reason for the improvement in NO₂ scores for all five statistics
2175 for the RAQDPS-OP023 hindcasts may have been the use of year-specific NO₂ emissions.

2176 **S4.2 Impact of biomass burning emissions**

2177 Further understanding of the impact of BB emissions in 2021/22 can be obtained from comparisons with
2178 additional figures based on RAQDPS-FW023 forecasts. [Figure S220](#) shows the spatial distributions of

2179 annual mean NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5} hourly surface abundances over North America for the 2021/22 period
2180 predicted by the RAQDPS-FW023, with superimposed coloured “coffee beans” showing observed and
2181 predicted annual values at NRT measurement sites. **Figure S224** shows the corresponding seasonal spatial
2182 distributions predicted by the RAQDPS-FW023 with superimposed observed and predicted seasonal values
2183 at measurement sites. These two figures can be compared directly with **Figs. 1** and **5** for the RAQDPS-
2184 OP023 forecasts. While the RAQDPS-FW023 seasonal panels for NO₂ in **Fig. S224** are virtually
2185 indistinguishable from those for RAQDPS-OP023 in **Fig. 5** and the seasonal panels for O₃ in **Fig. S224** are
2186 very similar to those in **Fig. 5**, the RAQDPS-FW023 seasonal panels for PM_{2.5} in **Fig. S224** are noticeably
2187 different from the RAQDPS-OP023 seasonal panels in **Fig. 5**, especially the summer panels but also the
2188 spring and autumn panels. The multiple jurisdictions impacted by PM_{2.5} emissions from summer wildfires
2189 in 2021 can be seen in **Fig. S224** (northern California, Nevada, Pacific Northwest, northeastern
2190 Saskatchewan, northern Manitoba, and northwestern Ontario), and there is much better agreement with
2191 summer station-level PM_{2.5} concentration measurements than in **Fig. 5**. Another insight is that the annual
2192 mean PM_{2.5} concentration fields presented in **Fig. S220** vs. **Fig. 1** are also quite different, which suggests
2193 that summer seasonal BB emissions can significantly impact annual PM_{2.5} evaluation statistics.

2194 This second insight is supported by comparisons of some other figures. For example, **Fig. S223**, which
2195 shows the spatial distribution of station-specific annual values of MB, NMB, CRMSE, and R for RAQDPS-
2196 FW023 PM_{2.5} forecasts can be compared with **Fig. 4**, which shows the same quantities for RAQDPS-OP023
2197 forecasts. Clear differences are visible between these annual statistics in **Fig. S223**, especially over the
2198 western U.S. and western Canada but also over the eastern U.S.; these differences include reductions in
2199 annual MB and NMB scores and increases in annual R scores. The impact of wildfire emissions on
2200 individual annual station statistics for NO₂ and O₃ can similarly be examined by comparing **Figs. S221** and
2201 **S222** with **Figs. 2** and **3**, respectively, but differences are negligible for NO₂ and small for O₃, consistent
2202 with **Table 7**.

2203 **Figures S225–S227** show time series of observed and predicted all-station monthly mean abundances and
2204 monthly NMB, CRMSE, and R scores for hourly NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5} measurements, respectively, for
2205 RAQDPS-FW023 forecasts for 2021/22. These figures can be compared with **Figs. 6–8** for the RAQDPS-
2206 OP023 forecasts. Again, differences are small for NO₂ and O₃ and restricted to the summer months, but
2207 the time series for monthly mean PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations in **Fig. S227** are obviously different from
2208 those in **Fig. 8** for the warm season but not for the cold season where a low bias persists for both system
2209 versions. In addition, side-by-side comparisons of RAQDPS-FW023 and RAQDPS-OP023 predictions of
2210 monthly mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2021/22 are presented for urban sites only in **Fig. S245** and for rural
2211 sites only in **Fig. S246**. Monthly mean PM_{2.5} concentrations predicted by the RAQDPS-FW023 for the

2212 July to September period are again much better than those predicted by the RAQDPS-OP023 for both urban
2213 and rural stations as are monthly NMB scores. By contrast monthly NMB and R scores for the two systems
2214 are very close for the November to May period but are better for the urban sites than the rural sites (cf.
2215 **Figs. S213** and **S214** for corresponding RAQDPS-OP023 monthly time series for 2013–2016).

2216 **Figures S232–S234** present all-station monthly time series of five other statistics (median O, median M,
2217 MB, FAC2, NSD) for NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5}, respectively, for the 2021/22 RAQDPS-FW023 forecasts.
2218 **Figures S137–S139** present the same statistics for the 2021/22 RAQDPS-OP023 forecasts. The NO₂ and
2219 O₃ monthly time series of MB, FAC2, and NSD predicted by the two forecast system versions are very
2220 similar, though there are some differences for O₃ for the summer months. For PM_{2.5}, by contrast, there are
2221 marked differences in monthly median M, MB, FAC2, and NSD between **Figs. S234** and **S139** from May
2222 to October but little difference the rest of the year. RAQDPS-FW023 median M, MB and FAC2 scores are
2223 better in the summer months than RAQDPS-OP023 scores while NSD scores in the summer flip from
2224 underpredicted to overpredicted. Interestingly, unlike the RAQDPS-FW023 predicted monthly mean PM_{2.5}
2225 concentrations for the summer months shown in **Fig. S227**, predicted monthly median PM_{2.5} concentrations
2226 in **Fig. S234** remain lower than the observed monthly median values in all months, suggesting that when
2227 BB emissions are small, PM_{2.5} concentrations that are dominated by anthropogenic emissions may be biased
2228 low.

2229 **Figures S228–S230** present *diurnal* time series of all-station annual means of hourly abundances and
2230 annual NMB, CRMSE, and R statistics for NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5}, respectively, for the RAQDPS-FW023
2231 forecasts for all of 2021/22; these figures can be compared with **Figs. 9** to **11** for the RAQDPS-OP023
2232 forecasts. Differences are again negligible for NO₂ and small (but improved) for O₃, but they are large for
2233 the diurnal time series of annual means of hourly PM_{2.5} concentration and associated statistics (**Fig. S230**
2234 vs. **Fig. 11**). This is another example of the impact of the inclusion of seasonal BB emissions on annual
2235 evaluation statistics: hour-specific annual MB and NMB values are reduced, hour-specific R values are
2236 increased, but hour-specific CRMSE values are also increased. However, one interesting similarity
2237 between **Fig. S230** and **Fig. 11** is the closeness of early afternoon values of CRMSE, suggesting a minimum
2238 impact of BB emissions at this time of day on this statistic but not on NMB or R, which have both improved.

2239 **Figures S235–S237** and **Figs. S140–S142** present all-station monthly time series of NMB, FAC2, and R
2240 scores for NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5}, respectively, for the two system versions for 2021/22 with scores for the
2241 RAQDPS-OP023 hindcasts for 2013–2016 superimposed on both figure sets. Differences are thus only
2242 possible between the 2021/22 time series, but these figures also show similarities in observed and predicted
2243 seasonal cycles for the five years. No differences can be seen for the 2021/22 NO₂ monthly time series

2244 between [Figs. S235](#) and [S140](#), small differences can be seen for O₃ in the predicted monthly means and
2245 monthly NMB scores from June to October 2021 between [Figs. S236](#) and [S141](#), consistent with [Table 7](#),
2246 and all monthly NMB, FAC2, and R scores for PM_{2.5} in [Fig. S237](#) from June to October 2021 for the
2247 RAQDPS-FW023 are better than those in [Fig. S142](#) for the RAQDPS-OP023 forecasts (and better than the
2248 corresponding 2013–2016 hindcast scores for the same months). Jain et al. (2024) noted that the 2021
2249 wildfire season was record-breaking, and both the observed and predicted July and August monthly mean
2250 PM_{2.5} concentrations for 2021 stand out even against 2015, another high wildfire year ([Table A4](#)).

2251 [Figures S238–S240](#) and [Figs. S165–S167](#) present all-station, *season*-mean diurnal time series of five
2252 evaluation statistics for NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5}, respectively, for 2021/22 for the RAQDPS-FW023 and
2253 RAQDPS-OP023. As was the case for the all-station, annual-mean diurnal time series ([Figs. S228–S230](#),
2254 [Figs. 9–11](#)), the NO₂ and O₃ seasonal diurnal time series predicted by the two versions are very similar,
2255 even for the summer wildfire season ([Fig. S238](#) vs. [Fig. S165](#) for NO₂; [Fig. S239](#) vs. [Fig. S166](#) for O₃),
2256 although some differences in NMB and R can be seen for O₃. The situation, however, is more complex for
2257 PM_{2.5}. While the annual mean PM_{2.5} diurnal time series for North America were markedly different for the
2258 two versions ([Fig. S230](#) vs. [Fig. 11](#)), the PM_{2.5} seasonal diurnal time series for North America shown in
2259 [Fig. S240](#) and [Fig. S167](#) for the two forecast system versions are nearly identical for the winter season,
2260 slightly different for the spring season, and markedly different only for the summer and autumn seasons.
2261 This again shows that the annual differences due to BB emissions are mainly driven by differences for only
2262 two seasons.

2263 Regional comparisons are also informative. [Figures S231](#) and [12](#) present 2021/22 observed and predicted
2264 time series of monthly means of hourly NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5} abundances for four regions for the RAQDPS-
2265 FW023 and RAQDPS-OP023, respectively. As was the case for [Figs. S225–S227](#) and [Figs. 6–8](#) for the
2266 continental scale, the NO₂ regional time series are very similar for the two versions whereas the O₃ and
2267 PM_{2.5} regional time series for the RAQDPS-FW023 are different from those for the RAQDPS-OP023 from
2268 June to October for all four regions, suggesting that wildfire smoke affected all of North America in 2021.
2269 The four monthly time series for regional PM_{2.5} surface concentration in [Fig. S231](#) also display better
2270 agreement with summer observations compared to [Fig. 12](#). One geographic difference is that the
2271 differences for PM_{2.5} are roughly twice as large for WUS and WCA as they are for EUS and ECA, consistent
2272 with the occurrence of record-breaking wildfires in summer 2021 in western North America (Jain et al.,
2273 2024). Similarly, [Figs. S241](#) and [S168](#) present observed and predicted *diurnal* time series of annual means
2274 of hourly NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5} abundances by region for 2021/22 for the two system versions. As was the
2275 case for [Figs. S228–S230](#) and [Figs. 9–11](#) for the continental scale, the NO₂ and O₃ regional time series are
2276 very similar for the two versions whereas the PM_{2.5} regional time series for the RAQDPS-FW023 shown in

2277 **Fig. S241** have significantly higher values for all four regions, but again more so for the two western regions
2278 where the 2021 wildfires were concentrated.

2279 Another source of information about the impact of BB emissions on North American AQ forecasts is the
2280 ongoing WMO GAFIS initiative for intercomparison and evaluation of multiple North American AQ
2281 forecast systems (<https://hpfx.collab.science.gc.ca/~svfs000/na-aq-mm-fe/dist/>; accessed 18 Aug. 2025).
2282 Six AQ forecast systems are included in the intercomparison, three of which are regional systems
2283 (RAQDPS-OP023, RAQDPS-FW023, NAQFC) and three of which are global systems (GEOS-CF, IFS-
2284 CAMS, IFS-SILAM). Five of the six systems include NRT biomass burning emissions, with the RAQDPS-
2285 OP023 being the exception. Monthly statistics, which are calculated for daily *maximum* values based on
2286 NRT AirNow and NAPS hourly measurements of NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5}, have been reported quarterly since
2287 2019. Each GAFIS quarterly report also contains statistics for the previous four quarters, which allows new
2288 quarterly statistics to be compared to the same quarter for the previous year. Thus, if we examine the third-
2289 quarter 2022 report (Manseau et al., 2022b), we can see monthly scores for both the RAQDPS-OP023 and
2290 RAQDPS-FW023 for the 12-month 2021/2022 forecast period as well as scores for two consecutive
2291 summers. Monthly MFB, FAC2, and R scores for NO₂ are very similar for these two systems; those for O₃
2292 are also very similar, with the exception of minor differences in MFB and R scores for summer 2021; but
2293 PM_{2.5} scores for all three statistics, while very similar from November 2021 to April 2022, display large
2294 differences from July to October 2021 and again from May to September 2022, all months favouring the
2295 occurrence of wildfires.

2296 **S4.3 Comparison with other AQ forecast systems**

2297 Chai et al. (2013) presented NAQFC evaluation results for O₃ and NO₂ for one year, 2010, that used
2298 finalized AQS hourly data rather than NRT AirNow hourly data (although a comparison of finalized AQS
2299 and NRT AirNow O₃ data for a sample day had an R² value of 0.995). Overall, they found O₃ to be
2300 overpredicted in the summer and autumn and NO₂ to be overpredicted in all seasons. Tables of MB and
2301 RMSE scores stratified by month and by six U.S. geographic regions showed wide variations in scores by
2302 both time and location. While domain-average annual MB scores for 2010 for the continental U.S. for O₃
2303 and NO₂ were 5.6 and 5.1 ppbv, respectively, monthly MB scores for different regions ranged from -8.1 to
2304 17.6 ppbv for O₃ and from -0.9 to 9.7 ppbv for NO₂. Corresponding domain-average annual RMSE scores
2305 for the continental U.S. for O₃ and NO₂ were 15.4 and 13.4 ppbv, respectively, but monthly RMSE scores
2306 for different regions ranged from 8.3 to 22.5 ppbv for O₃ and from 8.0 to 19.6 ppbv for NO₂. As discussed
2307 in **Sect. 4.1**, evaluation statistics for 2010 are also available for the earliest operational versions of the
2308 RAQDPS so that a direct comparison of MB and RMSE scores is possible (though RAQDPS scores were
2309 seasonal and included Canadian as well as U.S. observations). Comparing NAQFC domain-average

2310 monthly MB scores for a mid-season winter month, January, and a mid-season summer month, July, with
2311 corresponding RAQDPS seasonal MB scores for winter and summer, NAQFC and RAQDPS MB values
2312 for O₃ were 2.9 and -6.6 ppbv, respectively, in January/winter 2010 and 9.8 vs. 3.4 ppbv in July/summer
2313 2010, and NAQFC and RAQDPS MB values for NO₂ were 4.7 vs. -0.6 ppbv in January/winter 2010 and
2314 5.5 vs. 1.1 ppbv in July/summer 2010. The same comparison for domain-average monthly and seasonal
2315 RMSE values for O₃ had NAQFC and RAQDPS values of 12.7 vs. 12.2 ppbv in January/winter 2010 and
2316 17.6 vs. 16.3 ppbv in July/summer 2010, and for NO₂ the domain-average monthly and seasonal RMSE
2317 values were 13.5 vs. 9.9 ppbv in January/winter 2010 and 12.8 vs. 8.1 ppbv in July/summer 2010.

2318 Pan et al. (2014) showed that the U.S. NO_x emissions used by the NAQFC for 2011 forecasts were likely
2319 too large and that reducing them could reduce both O₃ and NO₂ mean overpredictions, though in a
2320 complicated spatiotemporal relationship mediated by meteorology and chemistry. Note that later NAQFC
2321 evaluation papers present O₃ and PM_{2.5} evaluation scores but do not show NO₂ scores because NO₂ is not
2322 an official NAQFC forecast species. However, other groups have since published evaluation results for
2323 NO₂ or NO_x predictions made by the CMAQ model that is used in the NAQFC (e.g., Appel et al., 2017,
2324 2021).

2325 Huang et al. (2017) and Lee et al. (2017) focused on NAQFC PM_{2.5} forecast performance. Both papers
2326 showed that monthly NAQFC PM_{2.5} forecasts from 2009 to 2015 were biased high in the winter months
2327 and low in the summer months, which is the opposite of the RAQDPS for the same period (see [Fig. S215](#)).
2328 Huang et al. (2017) also showed that the predicted diurnal variations of PM_{2.5} MB in January and July were
2329 roughly anticorrelated, whereas RAQDPS-OP023 seasonal mean diurnal variations of PM_{2.5} NMB had the
2330 same shape across the four seasons ([Fig. S167](#)) and resembled the NAQFC January diurnal MB variations.
2331 Lee et al. (2017) provided some monthly evaluation statistics for the NAQFC version released in January
2332 2015 for *daily* PM_{2.5} forecasts for May and July 2014 and January 2015 that can be compared to seasonal
2333 statistics for RAQDPS-OP010 *hourly* forecasts for spring and summer 2014 and RAQDPS-OP011 hourly
2334 forecasts for winter 2015 (see [Table A5](#)). Keeping in mind the differences underlying the same nominal
2335 scores (i.e., different averaging times, inclusion/exclusion of Canadian measurements), MB, NMB, and R
2336 scores were slightly better for the RAQDPS for these three months whereas RMSE values for the RAQDPS
2337 were considerably larger, likely due at least in part to the consideration of hourly vs. daily values,

2338 Chen et al. (2021) presented an evaluation of a 2019 simulation performed with an experimental NAQFC
2339 version with a new meteorological driver but the same version of the CMAQ AQ model (v5.0.2) used by
2340 the operational NAQFC at the time. The authors discussed a number of limitations of this version of the
2341 CMAQ model that were addressed in later versions. The operational NAQFC then underwent a major

2342 upgrade on 20 July 2021, with the implementation of a new meteorological driver, the initial version of the
2343 NOAA-EPA Atmosphere Chemistry Coupler (NACC), a new version of CMAQ (v5.3.1), and new U.S.
2344 emissions files (Campbell et al., 2022). A few domain-wide NMB, NMAE, and R scores are reported in
2345 this paper for the new NACC-CMAQ version of the NAQFC for hourly O₃ for September 2020 and hourly
2346 PM_{2.5} for January 2021. A crude comparison can be made between these monthly scores and the RAQDPS-
2347 OP023 seasonal scores reported in **Table S3S** for autumn 2021 and winter 2021/2022 (i.e., a one-year
2348 offset). The monthly NMB, NMAE, and R scores for the new NAQFC for O₃ for September 2020 were
2349 0.15, 0.33, and 0.72 vs. RAQDPS-OP023 seasonal scores for autumn 2021 of -0.03, 0.28, and 0.75. The
2350 monthly NMB, NMAE, and R scores for the new NAQFC for PM_{2.5} for January 2021 were -0.05, 0.61, and
2351 0.41 vs. RAQDPS-OP023 seasonal scores for winter 2021/22 of -0.13, 0.66, and 0.40. Note that Campbell
2352 et al. (2022) also compared some NAQFC scores for O₃ and PM_{2.5} against the benchmark levels
2353 recommended by Emery et al. (2017).

2354 One other ongoing performance evaluation for multiple operational AQ forecast models is that conducted
2355 for the European operational regional AQ forecast ensemble by the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring
2356 Service (CAMS) (e.g., Marécal et al., 2015; Casciaro et al., 2022; Peuch et al., 2022; Bertrand et al., 2023).
2357 The pollutants considered are NO₂, O₃, PM_{2.5}, CO, SO₂, and PM₁₀, which are obtained from NRT European
2358 hourly surface observations. A wide range of evaluation techniques are applied both daily and quarterly,
2359 including tables of statistics, contoured plots of observations and gridded model output somewhat similar
2360 to **Figs. 1** and **5**, time series, histograms, scatterplots, and Taylor diagrams (Copernicus Atmosphere
2361 Monitoring Service, 2023). Ten statistical metrics are routinely calculated, six of which are also considered
2362 in this study: \bar{O} , \bar{M} , MB, NMB, RMSE, and R. Given the focus on a different continent, it is not appropriate
2363 to make direct comparisons of CAMS regional ensemble evaluation results with the results of this study.
2364 However, some qualitative comparisons are possible. For one example shown in Copernicus Atmosphere
2365 Monitoring Service (2023), domain-average annual R scores for SO₂ and CO in 2022 for 11 AQ forecast
2366 models were considerably lower than those for NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5} (in agreement with **Tables 3** and **4**), but
2367 annual R scores for PM_{2.5} were higher than those for NO₂ (not in agreement with **Table 3**). For domain-
2368 average annual NMB scores for 2021 and 2022, NO₂, SO₂, and CO VMRs were all underpredicted by the
2369 European ensemble by large amounts (see “Overall Evaluation”, <https://cams2-83.aeroyal.met.no/>; last
2370 access 6 Aug. 2025), whereas domain-average annual NMB values for the RAQDPS-OP023 for 2021/22
2371 were small for NO₂ and CO but large and positive for SO₂ (see **Tables 3** and **4**). Marécal et al. (2015) also
2372 showed hourly time series of domain-wide MB, MFB, RMSE, MFE, and R for 96-hour forecasts of O₃ and
2373 PM₁₀ over Europe made by seven regional AQ models for winter and summer 2014. Like the GAFIS North

2374 American evaluations and intercomparisons for six AQ forecast models discussed in **Sect. 4.3** and
2375 **Sect. S4.2**, there is also considerable spread between the seven models for all five metrics.
2376

2377 **Supplement References**

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List of Supplement Tables

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2969 model species for 2021/22 (based on SET4.0.0 input emissions files and modified BEISv3.09 calculations).
2970 The winter season is from December to February, and so on. Note that fugitive PM emissions have been
2971 reduced by transportable-fraction (TF) scaling but not meteorological modulation due to snowcover or
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2975 (AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET, CSN, IMPROVE, NAPS), and precipitation-chemistry evaluation
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2977 Table [S2b](#). Number of U.S. and Canadian air-chemistry measurement stations with complete annual
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2993 NAPS individual networks and combined networks. For dimensional statistics, units are ppmv for CO,
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2995 Table [S4S](#). Summary table of seasonal statistics for other gas-phase chemistry measurements (NO, NO_x,
2996 CO, ETHE, ISOP, HCHO, NH₃, HNO₃, and SO₂) for 2013–2016 for AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET and
2997 NAPS individual networks and combined networks. For dimensional statistics, units are ppmv for CO,
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3003 concentration measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for 2013–2016 for AQS, CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS individual
3004 networks and combined networks. Note that AQS gravimetric measurements include both CSN and non-
3005 CSN locations, and no NH₄ values or scores are provided for the IMPROVE network. [cf. Tables 5 and
3006 S5A]

3007 Table [S5S-mr](#). Summary table of seasonal statistics for daily gravimetric and speciated PM_{2.5} concentration
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3009 that include all PM_{2.5} chemical species and PM_{2.5} total mass for a location and time have been considered.
3010 [cf. Table S5A]

3011 Table [S6A](#). Summary table of annual statistics for weekly precipitation-chemistry measurements for 2013–
3012 2016 for CAPMoN and NAPS individual networks and combined networks. For dimensional statistics,
3013 units are $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ for concentration in precipitation, $\text{mm}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for precipitation, and $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for wet
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3015 with NADP measurements. [cf. Table 6]

3016 Table [S6S](#). Summary table of **seasonal** statistics for weekly precipitation-chemistry measurements for
3017 2013–2016 for CAPMoN and NAPS individual networks and combined networks. For dimensional
3018 statistics, units are $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ for concentration in precipitation, $\text{mm}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for precipitation, and
3019 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for wet deposition. Note that daily CAPMoN measurements have been aggregated to weekly
3020 values for consistency with NADP measurements. [cf. Tables 6 and S6A]

3021 Table [S7](#). Summary table of annual regional statistics for hourly NO_2 VMR (ppbv), O_3 VMR (ppbv), and
3022 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) measurements for 2013–2016 and 2021/22. [cf. Table 3]

3023 Table [S8](#). Summary table of annual regional statistics for other gas-phase chemistry measurements (NO,
3024 NO_x , CO, NH_3 , SO_2 , ETHE, ISOP, HCHO) for 2013–2016. For dimensional statistics, units are ppmv for
3025 CO, $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for NH_3 , and ppbv for other species. [cf. Table 4]

3026 Table [S9](#). Summary table of annual regional statistics for daily speciated $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration and
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3028 [cf. Table 5]

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3030 gravimetric mass measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS speciation sites for 2013–2016.
3031 Only observations that include all $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical species and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass for a location and time have
3032 been considered. [cf. Table S9]

3033 Table [S10](#). Summary table of annual regional statistics for precipitation-chemistry measurements for 2013–
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3035 precipitation, and $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for wet deposition. Note that daily CAPMoN measurements have been
3036 aggregated to weekly values for consistency with NADP measurements. [cf. Table 6]

3037

3038 Table S1. Summary of seasonal anthropogenic and biogenic emissions (ktonnes) for 19 RAQDPS-OP023
 3039 model species for 2021/22 (based on SET4.0.0 input emissions files and modified BEISv3.09 calculations).
 3040 The winter season is from December to February, and so on. Note that fugitive PM emissions have been
 3041 reduced by transportable-fraction (TF) scaling but not meteorological modulation due to snowcover or
 3042 recent rainfall [cf. Table 1].

Species	Absolute Emissions (ktonnes)					Fractional Emissions			
	Annual	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn
SO2	2,683	665	666	692	659	0.248	0.248	0.258	0.246
H2SO4	32	8	8	9	8	0.240	0.246	0.269	0.245
NO	5,633	1,398	1,396	1,442	1,397	0.248	0.248	0.256	0.248
NO2	1,075	265	267	276	267	0.246	0.249	0.257	0.248
HONO	47	11	12	13	12	0.225	0.248	0.277	0.250
CO	36,118	8,794	8,572	10,253	8,499	0.243	0.237	0.284	0.235
C3H8	1,558	422	378	385	374	0.271	0.242	0.247	0.240
ALKA	6,468	1,637	1,569	1,685	1,577	0.253	0.243	0.261	0.244
ETHE	249	83	57	53	57	0.332	0.229	0.212	0.227
ALKE	576	162	136	142	135	0.282	0.237	0.246	0.235
TOLU	576	145	137	156	138	0.251	0.238	0.272	0.239
AROM	761	200	180	201	180	0.263	0.236	0.264	0.237
HCHO	166	55	39	33	38	0.332	0.236	0.201	0.230
ALD2	199	89	43	24	44	0.448	0.214	0.119	0.219
MEK	124	32	30	31	31	0.255	0.246	0.252	0.247
CRES	93	41	20	12	20	0.439	0.212	0.131	0.218
ISOP	5	2	1	1	1	0.312	0.224	0.236	0.229
NH3	4,234	387	1,159	1,747	942	0.091	0.274	0.413	0.222
PM2.5-SO4	99	25	24	26	25	0.250	0.245	0.258	0.247
PM2.5-NO3	18	3	4	6	4	0.177	0.227	0.361	0.235
PM2.5-NH4	16	4	4	5	4	0.226	0.242	0.293	0.239
PM2.5-EC	185	48	45	47	45	0.260	0.244	0.254	0.242
PM2.5-POM	1,003	344	237	192	229	0.343	0.237	0.192	0.228
PM2.5-CM	1,568	328	406	439	396	0.209	0.259	0.280	0.252
PM2.5-noSS	2,889	752	720	715	702	0.260	0.249	0.248	0.243
PMcf-SO4	96	19	23	30	24	0.201	0.243	0.310	0.246
PMcf-NO3	48	5	10	21	11	0.109	0.215	0.444	0.232
PMcf-NH4	21	3	5	9	5	0.126	0.221	0.418	0.235
PMcf-EC	77	15	18	25	19	0.196	0.239	0.324	0.241
PMcf-POM	819	158	197	263	201	0.193	0.241	0.321	0.246
PMcf-CM	6,877	1,430	1,732	1,980	1,735	0.208	0.252	0.288	0.252
PMcf-noSS	7,937	1,630	1,986	2,327	1,994	0.205	0.250	0.293	0.251
NO (biogenic)	1,001	71	216	474	241	0.071	0.216	0.474	0.241
ALKA (biogenic)	8,055	496	1,426	4,385	1,748	0.062	0.177	0.544	0.217
ALKE (biogenic)	9,258	604	1,666	4,953	2,034	0.065	0.180	0.535	0.220
ISOP (biogenic)	35,343	807	6,113	22,867	5,556	0.023	0.173	0.647	0.157
Total NO	6,634	1,469	1,612	1,916	1,638	0.221	0.243	0.289	0.247
Total VOC (anthro)	10,775	2,867	2,590	2,724	2,595	0.266	0.240	0.253	0.241
Total VOC (bio)	52,656	1,907	9,205	32,205	9,338	0.036	0.175	0.612	0.177
Total VOC	63,431	4,774	11,795	34,929	11,933	0.075	0.186	0.551	0.188

3043

3044 Table S2a. Description of AQ network measurement data sets used in this study for gas-phase-chemistry
3045 evaluation (AirNow, AMoN, AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET, NAPS, NATTS, PAMS), particle-phase-
3046 chemistry evaluation (AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET, CSN, IMPROVE, NAPS), and precipitation-chemistry
3047 evaluation (CAPMoN, NADP-NTN).

3048
3049 [See oversized print version in file “Table_S2a.pdf”]

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3051
3052 Table S2b. Number of U.S. and Canadian air-chemistry measurement stations with complete annual
3053 measurements of other gases (NO, NO_x, CO, ETHE, ISOP, HCHO, HNO₃, NH₃, and SO₂) vs. available
3054 measurements by network and year for 2013–2016.

3055
3056 [See oversized print version in file “Table_S2b.pdf”]

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3059 Table S2c. Number of U.S. and Canadian daily PM_{2.5} mass and speciation measurement stations with
 3060 complete annual measurements vs. available measurements by network and year for 2013–2016. Note that
 3061 asterisks mark species that are calculated or estimated from direct measurements.

<i>Year</i>	2013		2014		2015		2016	
	Complete	Available	Complete	Available	Complete	Available	Complete	Available
<i>Variable</i>	<i>Network</i>							
	CSN							
SO4	164	188	158	188	140	173	127	152
NO3	164	187	158	187	140	171	128	150
NH4	164	188	158	188	140	173	129	152
EC	153	191	161	187	128	170	120	149
OM*	153	191	161	187	128	170	120	149
CM*	165	188	159	188	140	173	129	152
SS*	164	188	158	188	140	173	129	152
	IMPROVE							
PM25	151	157	152	156	147	158	143	147
SO4	151	157	151	156	147	158	143	147
NO3	151	157	151	156	147	158	143	147
NH4*	150	156	150	155	146	157	142	146
EC	154	160	154	159	149	161	147	150
OM*	154	160	154	159	148	161	144	150
CM*	150	156	151	155	146	157	142	146
SS*	150	156	151	155	146	157	142	146
	NAPS							
PM25	21	33	19	34	15	32	21	30
SO4	20	31	18	31	17	31	22	29
NO3	20	31	18	31	17	31	22	29
NH4	20	31	18	31	17	31	22	29
EC	10	13	10	13	11	12	10	12
OM*	10	13	10	13	11	12	9	12
CM*	14	26	13	27	13	30	20	29
SS*	20	31	18	31	17	31	22	29
	AQS							
PM25	606	716	612	734	656	734	604	715

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3063

3064 Table S2d. Number of U.S. and Canadian precipitation-chemistry measurement stations with complete
 3065 annual measurements vs. available measurements by network and year for 2013–2016.

Year	2013		2014		2015		2016	
	Complete	Available	Complete	Available	Complete	Available	Complete	Available
<i>Variable</i>								
CAPMoN								
SO ₄ ⁼	25	31	25	30	27	31	26	33
NO ₃ ⁻	25	31	25	30	27	31	26	33
NH ₄ ⁺	25	31	25	30	27	31	26	33
Precip	25	31	25	30	28	31	26	33
NADP								
SO ₄ ⁼	214	263	205	262	225	264	213	267
NO ₃ ⁻	214	263	205	262	225	264	213	267
NH ₄ ⁺	214	263	205	262	225	264	213	267
Precip	246	263	248	262	251	264	244	267

3066
 3067
 3068
 3069 Table S3A. Summary table of annual statistics for hourly NO₂ VMR (ppbv), O₃ VMR (ppbv), and PM_{2.5}
 3070 concentration (µg·m⁻³) measurements for 2021/22 and 2013–2016 for AirNow, AQS, and NAPS individual
 3071 networks and combined networks.

3072
 3073 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S3A.pdf”]
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3075
 3076
 3077 Table S3S. Summary table of seasonal statistics for hourly NO₂ VMR (ppbv), O₃ VMR (ppbv), and PM_{2.5}
 3078 concentration (µg·m⁻³) measurements for 2021/22 and 2013–2016 for AirNow, AQS, and NAPS individual
 3079 networks and combined networks.

3080
 3081 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S3S.pdf”]
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 3084 Table S4A. Summary table of annual statistics for other gas-phase chemistry measurements (NO, NO_x,
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 3086 NAPS individual networks and combined networks. For dimensional statistics, units are ppmv for CO,
 3087 µg·m⁻³ for NH₃, and ppbv for other species.

3088
 3089 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S4A.pdf”]
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 3092 Table S4S. Summary table of seasonal statistics for other gas-phase chemistry measurements (NO, NO_x,
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3094 NAPS individual networks and combined networks. For dimensional statistics, units are ppmv for CO,
3095 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for NH_3 , and ppbv for other species.

3096
3097 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S4S.pdf”]
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3100 Table S5A. Summary table of annual statistics for full set of daily gravimetric and speciated $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
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3102 and combined networks.

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3104 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S5A.pdf”]
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3107 Table S5S. Summary table of seasonal statistics for full set of daily gravimetric and speciated $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
3108 concentration measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for 2013–2016 for AQS, CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS individual
3109 networks and combined networks. Note that AQS gravimetric measurements include both CSN and non-
3110 CSN locations, and no NH_4 values or scores are provided for the IMPROVE network.

3111
3112 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S5S.pdf”]
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3114
3115 Table S5S-mr. Summary table of seasonal statistics for daily gravimetric and speciated $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration
3116 measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS speciation sites for 2013–2016. Only observations
3117 that include all $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical species and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ total mass have been considered.

3118
3119 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S5S-mr.pdf”]
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3122 Table S6A. Summary table of annual statistics for weekly precipitation-chemistry measurements for 2013–
3123 2016 for CAPMoN and NAPS individual networks and combined networks. For dimensional statistics,
3124 units are $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ for concentration in precipitation, $\text{mm}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for precipitation, and $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for wet
3125 deposition. Note that daily CAPMoN measurements have been aggregated to weekly values for consistency
3126 with NADP measurements.

3127
3128 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S6A.pdf”]
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3130
3131 Table S6S. Summary table of seasonal statistics for weekly precipitation-chemistry measurements for
3132 2013–2016 for CAPMoN and NAPS individual networks and combined networks. For dimensional
3133 statistics, units are $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ for concentration in precipitation, $\text{mm}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for precipitation, and
3134 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for wet deposition. Note that daily CAPMoN measurements have been aggregated to weekly
3135 values for consistency with NADP measurements.

3136
3137 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S6S.pdf”]
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3139

3140 Table S7. Summary table of annual regional statistics for hourly NO₂ VMR (ppbv), O₃ VMR (ppbv), and
 3141 PM_{2.5} concentration (µg·m⁻³) measurements for 2021/22 and 2013–2016.

3142

Network Variable	Year	Statistic	AirNow			
			W CA	E CA	W US	E US
NO ₂	2021	N	656,460	541,744	791,849	519,663
		Obs Mean	5.96	5.00	7.87	6.99
		Model Mean	5.57	4.83	5.44	5.23
		MB	-0.39	-0.17	-2.43	-1.76
		NMB	-0.06	-0.03	-0.31	-0.25
		RMSE	5.68	4.73	7.19	6.02
		CRMSE	5.67	4.72	6.77	5.76
		NMAE	0.58	0.57	0.57	0.51
		Fac2	0.52	0.54	0.45	0.59
		R	0.66	0.67	0.65	0.68
		NSD	1.00	0.96	0.72	0.84
		Obs SD	6.88	5.88	8.82	7.71
		Model SD	6.86	5.66	6.34	6.46
AQS + NAPS						
NO ₂	2013	N	618,247	486,347	1,228,555	1,443,143
		Obs Mean	7.33	6.81	8.44	8.05
		Model Mean	7.99	7.61	8.65	9.68
		MB	0.66	0.80	0.21	1.63
		NMB	0.09	0.12	0.02	0.20
		RMSE	6.68	6.27	8.03	6.97
		CRMSE	6.65	6.22	8.03	6.78
		NMAE	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.56
		Fac2	0.55	0.59	0.52	0.65
		R	0.67	0.66	0.67	0.70
		NSD	1.09	1.09	0.97	1.12
		Obs SD	7.82	7.15	9.96	8.14
		Model SD	8.50	7.82	9.67	9.16
NO ₂	2014	N	563,761	536,653	1,308,910	1,447,326
		Obs Mean	7.62	6.23	8.04	8.08
		Model Mean	8.11	6.82	8.28	9.54
		MB	0.50	0.59	0.23	1.46
		NMB	0.07	0.09	0.03	0.18
		RMSE	7.00	5.77	7.80	6.95
		CRMSE	6.98	5.74	7.80	6.80
		NMAE	0.59	0.57	0.60	0.56
		Fac2	0.54	0.58	0.52	0.65
		R	0.64	0.69	0.66	0.70
		NSD	1.06	1.04	0.98	1.11
		Obs SD	7.98	7.11	9.61	8.28
		Model SD	8.47	7.36	9.42	9.23
NO ₂	2015	N	636,283	521,073	1,310,441	1,465,712
		Obs Mean	7.04	6.41	7.97	7.92
		Model Mean	7.46	6.56	8.47	9.20
		MB	0.42	0.15	0.50	1.27

			NMB	0.06	0.02	0.06	0.16	
			RMSE	6.49	5.69	7.61	7.05	
			CRMSE	6.48	5.68	7.60	6.94	
			NMAE	0.60	0.55	0.59	0.57	
			Fac2	0.52	0.59	0.54	0.63	
			R	0.66	0.68	0.68	0.69	
			NSD	1.08	0.99	1.02	1.11	
			Obs SD	7.45	7.11	9.33	8.28	
			Model SD	8.08	7.02	9.55	9.18	
NO ₂	2016	N	663,739	540,105	1,311,976	1,394,253		
		Obs Mean	6.66	5.98	7.60	7.49		
		Model Mean	7.22	6.48	7.92	8.32		
		MB	0.56	0.50	0.32	0.83		
		NMB	0.08	0.08	0.04	0.11		
		RMSE	6.05	5.61	7.22	6.75		
		CRMSE	6.03	5.59	7.21	6.70		
		NMAE	0.59	0.58	0.58	0.57		
		Fac2	0.55	0.58	0.54	0.62		
		R	0.67	0.68	0.69	0.67		
		NSD	1.08	1.06	1.00	1.10		
		Obs SD	7.14	6.72	9.14	7.85		
		Model SD	7.71	7.12	9.11	8.62		
			AirNow					
			W CA	E CA	W US	E US		
O ₃	2021	N	664,803	808,649	2,158,027	2,543,775		
		Obs Mean	25.35	27.45	33.63	28.07		
		Model Mean	21.45	24.57	29.13	28.87		
		MB	-3.90	-2.88	-4.50	0.80		
		NMB	-0.15	-0.10	-0.13	0.03		
		RMSE	10.27	8.78	12.13	10.22		
		CRMSE	9.50	8.30	11.27	10.19		
		NMAE	0.32	0.25	0.28	0.28		
		Fac2	0.78	0.87	0.82	0.85		
		R	0.68	0.72	0.74	0.70		
		NSD	0.90	0.94	0.86	0.90		
		Obs SD	12.51	11.41	16.60	13.81		
		Model SD	11.21	10.77	14.23	12.48		
			AQS + NAPS					
			W CA	E CA	W US	E US		
O ₃	2013	N	558,350	891,065	2,782,415	3,236,775		
		Obs Mean	22.72	27.72	32.74	28.37		
		Model Mean	18.36	24.20	26.06	27.47		
		MB	-4.36	-3.52	-6.68	-0.89		
		NMB	-0.19	-0.13	-0.20	-0.03		
		RMSE	10.98	9.79	13.75	11.43		
		CRMSE	10.07	9.14	12.02	11.40		
		NMAE	0.37	0.27	0.32	0.31		
		Fac2	0.68	0.84	0.74	0.81		
		R	0.68	0.70	0.74	0.71		
		NSD	0.88	1.00	0.96	1.05		
		Obs SD	13.35	11.81	16.86	14.52		

		Model SD	11.71	11.79	16.22	15.18	
O ₃	2014	N	603,390	891,887	2,763,865	3,357,925	
		Obs Mean	23.07	27.22	32.53	27.95	
		Model Mean	19.02	24.21	26.64	27.28	
		MB	-4.05	-3.01	-5.89	-0.68	
		NMB	-0.18	-0.11	-0.18	-0.02	
		RMSE	10.76	9.34	13.22	10.98	
		CRMSE	9.97	8.85	11.84	10.96	
		NMAE	0.36	0.26	0.31	0.30	
		Fac2	0.70	0.85	0.75	0.81	
		R	0.67	0.70	0.73	0.71	
		NSD	0.91	1.00	0.97	1.03	
		Obs SD	12.85	11.40	16.46	14.23	
		Model SD	11.67	11.35	15.98	14.63	
		O ₃	2015	N	598,684	873,598	2,686,374
Obs Mean	22.71			27.34	32.43	27.68	
Model Mean	19.18			24.74	26.53	27.90	
MB	-3.53			-2.60	-5.89	0.22	
NMB	-0.16			-0.10	-0.18	0.01	
RMSE	10.52			9.28	13.16	10.96	
CRMSE	9.91			8.91	11.77	10.96	
NMAE	0.36			0.26	0.31	0.30	
Fac2	0.70			0.85	0.75	0.82	
R	0.69			0.71	0.73	0.72	
NSD	0.91			0.98	0.96	1.04	
Obs SD	13.20			11.80	16.40	14.29	
Model SD	12.00			11.58	15.74	14.82	
O ₃	2016			N	645,035	881,484	2,927,046
		Obs Mean	22.02	26.93	32.87	28.51	
		Model Mean	18.76	24.20	27.30	28.28	
		MB	-3.26	-2.73	-5.57	-0.24	
		NMB	-0.15	-0.10	-0.17	-0.01	
		RMSE	10.40	9.13	12.79	10.71	
		CRMSE	9.87	8.71	11.51	10.71	
		NMAE	0.35	0.25	0.30	0.29	
		Fac2	0.71	0.85	0.77	0.83	
		R	0.66	0.72	0.74	0.72	
		NSD	0.91	1.00	0.96	1.01	
		Obs SD	12.53	11.63	16.14	14.15	
		Model SD	11.36	11.58	15.43	14.35	
		PM _{2.5}	2021			AirNow	
				W CA	E CA	W US	E US
N	715,955			784,024	2,082,924	2,791,972	
Obs Mean	6.57			6.52	8.52	8.44	
Model Mean	3.88			5.31	6.06	5.57	
MB	-2.69			-1.21	-2.45	-2.86	
NMB	-0.41			-0.19	-0.29	-0.34	
RMSE	11.86			7.21	12.11	7.50	
CRMSE	11.56			7.11	11.86	6.93	
NMAE	0.82			0.66	0.72	0.58	

		Fac2	0.33	0.47	0.46	0.50
		R	0.11	0.40	0.20	0.31
		NSD	0.47	1.18	0.61	0.83
		Obs SD	10.91	5.93	11.16	6.42
		Model SD	5.18	6.97	6.78	5.30
			AQS + NAPS			
			W CA	E CA	W US	E US
PM _{2.5}	2013	N	611,227	733,235	2,017,325	2,918,493
		Obs Mean	6.20	7.39	9.07	9.23
		Model Mean	6.23	7.06	9.32	8.06
		MB	0.03	-0.33	0.25	-1.18
		NMB	0.00	-0.04	0.03	-0.13
		RMSE	9.00	8.08	16.27	8.62
		CRMSE	9.00	8.08	16.27	8.54
		NMAE	0.87	0.66	0.85	0.60
		Fac2	0.37	0.50	0.44	0.56
		R	0.26	0.46	0.24	0.35
		NSD	1.18	1.31	1.45	1.24
		Obs SD	6.76	6.55	10.48	6.58
		Model SD	7.99	8.60	15.23	8.19
PM _{2.5}	2014	N	767,962	769,270	2,063,920	3,034,379
		Obs Mean	6.90	7.09	8.11	9.18
		Model Mean	6.02	6.44	8.81	8.07
		MB	-0.88	-0.65	0.71	-1.11
		NMB	-0.13	-0.09	0.09	-0.12
		RMSE	12.29	7.56	14.85	8.85
		CRMSE	12.25	7.53	14.83	8.78
		NMAE	0.87	0.68	0.87	0.61
		Fac2	0.38	0.47	0.45	0.55
		R	0.14	0.45	0.25	0.34
		NSD	0.92	1.32	1.58	1.26
		Obs SD	9.72	6.02	9.00	6.66
		Model SD	8.92	7.95	14.20	8.39
PM _{2.5}	2015	N	664,967	752,444	1,992,001	3,061,794
		Obs Mean	7.06	7.14	8.49	8.89
		Model Mean	5.63	6.58	8.65	7.58
		MB	-1.44	-0.56	0.16	-1.31
		NMB	-0.20	-0.08	0.02	-0.15
		RMSE	14.25	7.44	14.85	8.54
		CRMSE	14.18	7.42	14.85	8.44
		NMAE	0.84	0.66	0.84	0.61
		Fac2	0.38	0.49	0.46	0.54
		R	0.10	0.47	0.23	0.34
		NSD	0.55	1.27	1.29	1.18
		Obs SD	12.98	6.21	10.33	6.67
		Model SD	7.20	7.88	13.36	7.90
PM _{2.5}	2016	N	737,190	753,363	2,100,976	2,879,807
		Obs Mean	6.11	6.01	7.54	8.07
		Model Mean	5.19	6.04	7.69	7.16
		MB	-0.92	0.03	0.15	-0.91

NMB	-0.15	0.00	0.02	-0.11
RMSE	28.60	6.98	12.42	8.39
CRMSE	28.58	6.98	12.42	8.34
NMAE	0.87	0.72	0.84	0.63
Fac2	0.37	0.47	0.44	0.54
R	0.04	0.46	0.26	0.29
NSD	0.23	1.58	1.44	1.15
Obs SD	28.08	4.87	8.12	6.47
Model SD	6.59	7.69	11.72	7.47

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3147 Table S8. Summary table of annual regional statistics for other gas-phase chemistry measurements (NO,
3148 NO_x, CO, NH₃, SO₂, ETHE, ISOP, HCHO) for 2013–2016. For dimensional statistics, units are ppmv for
3149 CO, $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for NH₃, and ppbv for other species.

3150
3151 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S8.pdf”]

3152
3153
3154 Table S9. Summary table of annual regional statistics for daily speciated PM_{2.5} concentration measurements
3155 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for 2013–2016.

3156
3157 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S9.pdf”]

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3159
3160 Table S9-mr. Summary table of annual regional statistics for daily speciated PM_{2.5} concentration and
3161 gravimetric mass measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS speciation sites for 2013–2016.
3162 Only observations that include all PM_{2.5} chemical species and PM_{2.5} total mass for a location and time have
3163 been considered. [cf. Table S9]

3164
3165 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S9-mr.pdf”]

3166
3167
3168 Table S10. Summary table of annual regional statistics for precipitation-chemistry measurements for 2013–
3169 2016. For dimensional statistics, units are $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ for concentration in precipitation, $\text{mm}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for
3170 precipitation, and $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{week}^{-1}$ for wet deposition. Note that daily CAPMoN measurements have been
3171 aggregated to weekly values for consistency with NADP measurements.

3172
3173 [See oversize print version in file “Table_S10.pdf”]

3174

List of Supplement Figures

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3178 Figure [S2](#). Monitoring station locations for (a) NO₂, (b) O₃, and (c) PM_{2.5} hourly measurements for the
3179 **2021/22** period for the NAPS network in Canada and the AirNow network in U.S.

3180 Figure [S3](#). Monitoring station locations for (a) NO₂, (b) O₃, and (c) PM_{2.5} hourly measurements for the
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3184 Figure [S4](#). Monitoring station locations for (a) NO and (b) CO hourly measurements and (c) SO₂ and HNO₃
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3189 Figure [S5](#). Monitoring station locations for the **2013-2016** period for AQS (left) HCHO daily measurement
3190 stations (PAMS, NATTS, S/L) and (right) ETHE and ISOP hourly measurement stations (PAMS).

3191 Figure [S6](#). Monitoring station locations for the **2013-2016** period for (a) AQS, IMPROVE, and NAPS
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3196 Figure [S7](#). Location of four spatial analysis regions: western Canada (WCAN; red); eastern Canada
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3258 Figure [S27](#). Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal PM_{2.5}-SOM concentration**
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3262 fields ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five**
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3276 Figure [S33](#). Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal NH₄⁺ wet concentration**
3277 fields ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five**
3278 **years**: (top row) 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

3279 Figure [S34](#). Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal SO₄⁼ wet deposition** fields
3280 ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**:
3281 (top row) 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22. [cf.
3282 Figures S10 and S31]

3283 Figure [S35](#). Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal NO₃⁻ wet deposition** fields
3284 ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**:
3285 (top row) 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22. [cf.
3286 Figures S10 and S32]

3287 Figure [S36](#). Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal NH₄⁺ wet deposition** fields
3288 ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**:
3289 (top row) 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22. [cf.
3290 Figures S10 and S33]

3291 Figure [S37](#). Spatial distribution of **annual mean bias (MB)** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO₂**
3292 **VMR predictions (ppbv)** at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3293 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 3]

3294 Figure [S38](#). Spatial distribution of **annual normalized mean bias (NMB)** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023
3295 for hourly **NO₂ VMR predictions (fraction)** at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years:
3296 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 3]

3297 Figure [S39](#). Spatial distribution of **annual centred root mean square error (CRMSE)** scores for the
3298 RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO₂ VMR predictions (ppbv)** at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four
3299 consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 3]

3300 Figure [S40](#). Spatial distribution of **annual correlation coefficient (R)** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for
3301 hourly **NO₂ VMR predictions (fraction)** at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3302 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 3]

3303 Figure [S41](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **O₃ VMR**
3304 **predictions (ppbv)** at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3305 and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 4]

3306 Figure [S42](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **O₃ VMR**
3307 **predictions (fraction)** at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3308 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 4]

3309 Figure [S43](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **O₃** VMR
3310 predictions (ppbv) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3311 and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 4]

3312 Figure [S44](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **O₃** VMR
3313 predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3314 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 4]

3315 Figure [S45](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **PM_{2.5}**
3316 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all AQS and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3317 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 5]

3318 Figure [S46](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **PM_{2.5}**
3319 concentration (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3320 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 5]

3321 Figure [S47](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **PM_{2.5}**
3322 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3323 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 5]

3324 Figure [S48](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **PM_{2.5}**
3325 concentration predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3326 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 5]

3327 Figure [S49](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO** VMR
3328 predictions (ppbv) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3329 and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S35]

3330 Figure [S50](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO** VMR
3331 predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3332 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S36]

3333 Figure [S51](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO** VMR
3334 predictions (ppbv) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3335 and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S37]

3336 Figure [S52](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO** VMR
3337 predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3338 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S38]

3339 Figure [S53](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **HNO₃** VMR
3340 predictions (ppbv) at all CAPMoN and CASTNET **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3341 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3342 Figure [S54](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **HNO₃** VMR
3343 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and CASTNET **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3344 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3345 Figure [S55](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **HNO₃**
3346 VMR predictions (ppbv) at all CAPMoN and CASTNET **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3347 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3348 Figure [S56](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **HNO₃** VMR
3349 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and CASTNET **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3350 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3351 Figure [S57](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for biweekly **NH₃** VMR
3352 predictions (ppbv) at all AMoN and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3353 and (d) 2016.

3354 Figure [S58](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for biweekly **NH₃** VMR
3355 predictions (fraction) at all AMoN and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3356 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3357 Figure [S59](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for biweekly **NH₃**
3358 VMR predictions (ppbv) at all AMoN and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3359 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3360 Figure [S60](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for biweekly **NH₃** VMR
3361 predictions (fraction) at all AMoN and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3362 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3363 Figure [S61](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₂** VMR
3364 predictions (ppbv) at all AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET, and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years:
3365 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3366 Figure [S62](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₂** VMR
3367 predictions (fraction) at all AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET, and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years:
3368 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3369 Figure [S63](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₂** VMR
3370 predictions (ppbv) at all AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET, and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years:
3371 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3372 Figure [S64](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₂** VMR
3373 predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3374 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3375 Figure [S65](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **CO** VMR
3376 predictions (ppbm) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3377 and (d) 2016.

3378 Figure [S66](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **CO** VMR
3379 predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3380 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3381 Figure [S67](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **CO** VMR
3382 predictions (ppbm) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3383 and (d) 2016.

3384 Figure [S68](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **CO** VMR
3385 predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3386 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3387 Figure [S69](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ETHE** VMR
3388 predictions (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3389 and (d) 2016.

3390 Figure [S70](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ETHE** VMR
3391 predictions (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3392 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3393 Figure [S71](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ETHE** VMR
3394 predictions (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3395 and (d) 2016.

3396 Figure [S72](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ETHE** VMR
3397 predictions (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3398 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3399 Figure [S73](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **HCHO** VMR
3400 predictions (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3401 and (d) 2016.

3402 Figure [S74](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **HCHO** VMR
3403 predictions (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3404 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3405 Figure [S75](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **HCHO** VMR
3406 predictions (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3407 and (d) 2016.

3408 Figure [S76](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **HCHO** VMR
3409 predictions (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3410 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3411 Figure [S77](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ISOP** VMR
3412 predictions (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3413 and (d) 2016.

3414 Figure [S78](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ISOP** VMR
3415 predictions (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3416 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3417 Figure [S79](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ISOP** VMR
3418 predictions (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
3419 and (d) 2016.

3420 Figure [S80](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ISOP** VMR
3421 (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d)
3422 2016.

3423 Figure [S81](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SO₄**
3424 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3425 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S43]

3426 Figure [S82](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SO₄**
3427 concentration (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3428 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S44]

3429 Figure [S83](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SO₄**
3430 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3431 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S45]

3432 Figure [S84](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SO₄**
3433 concentration predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3434 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S46]

3435 Figure [S85](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NO₃**
3436 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3437 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3438 Figure [S86](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NO₃**
3439 concentration (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3440 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3441 Figure [S87](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NO₃**
3442 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3443 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3444 Figure [S88](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NO₃**
3445 concentration predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3446 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3447 Figure [S89](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NH₄**
3448 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b)
3449 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3450 Figure [S90](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NH₄**
3451 concentration (fraction) at all CSN and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3452 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3453 Figure [S91](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NH₄**
3454 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3455 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3456 Figure [S92](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NH₄**
3457 concentration predictions (fraction) at all CSN and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3458 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3459 Figure [S93](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-EC**
3460 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3461 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3462 Figure [S94](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-EC**
3463 concentration (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3464 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3465 Figure [S95](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-EC**
3466 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3467 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3468 Figure [S96](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-EC**
3469 concentration predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3470 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3471 Figure [S97](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-TOM**
3472 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3473 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3474 Figure [S98](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-TOM**
3475 concentration (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3476 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3477 Figure [S99](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-TOM**
3478 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3479 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3480 Figure [S100](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-TOM**
3481 concentration predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3482 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3483 Figure [S101](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-CM**
3484 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3485 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3486 Figure [S102](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-CM**
3487 concentration (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3488 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3489 Figure [S103](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-CM**
3490 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3491 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3492 Figure [S104](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-CM**
3493 concentration predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3494 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3495 Figure [S105](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SS**
3496 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3497 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3498 Figure [S106](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SS**
3499 concentration (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3500 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3501 Figure [S107](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SS**
3502 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3503 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3504 Figure [S108](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SS**
3505 concentration predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years:
3506 (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3507 Figure [S109](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₄⁼**
3508 concentration-in-precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive
3509 years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3510 Figure [S110](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₄⁼**
3511 concentration-in-precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four
3512 consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3513 Figure [S111](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₄⁼**
3514 concentration-in-precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive
3515 years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3516 Figure [S112](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₄⁼**
3517 concentration-in-precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four
3518 consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3519 Figure [S113](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **NO₃⁻**
3520 concentration-in-precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive
3521 years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3522 Figure [S114](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **NO₃⁻**
3523 concentration-in-precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four
3524 consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3525 Figure [S115](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **NO₃⁻**
3526 concentration-in-precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive
3527 years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3528 Figure [S116](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **NO₃⁻**
3529 concentration-in-precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four
3530 consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3531 Figure [S117](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **NH₄⁺**
3532 concentration-in-precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive
3533 years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3534 Figure [S118](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+
3535 concentration-in-precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four
3536 consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3537 Figure [S119](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+
3538 concentration-in-precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive
3539 years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3540 Figure [S120](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+
3541 concentration-in-precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four
3542 consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3543 Figure [S121](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **precipitation**
3544 predictions (mm) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3545 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3546 Figure [S122](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **precipitation**
3547 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3548 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3549 Figure [S123](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly
3550 **precipitation** predictions (mm) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3551 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3552 Figure [S124](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **precipitation**
3553 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
3554 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3555 Figure [S125](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO_4^- wet
3556 deposition predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3557 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3558 Figure [S126](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO_4^- wet
3559 deposition predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3560 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3561 Figure [S127](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO_4^- wet
3562 deposition predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3563 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3564 Figure [S128](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO_4^- wet
3565 deposition predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3566 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3567 Figure [S129](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NO_3^- wet
3568 deposition predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3569 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3570 Figure [S130](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NO_3^- wet
3571 deposition predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3572 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3573 Figure [S131](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NO_3^- wet
3574 deposition predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3575 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3576 Figure [S132](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NO_3^- wet
3577 deposition predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3578 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3579 Figure [S133](#). Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+ wet
3580 deposition predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3581 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3582 Figure [S134](#). Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+ wet
3583 deposition predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3584 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3585 Figure [S135](#). Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+ wet
3586 deposition predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3587 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3588 Figure [S136](#). Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+ wet
3589 deposition predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
3590 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

3591 Figure [S137](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **median** hourly NO_2
3592 VMR (ppbv) and (b) MB, (c) FAC2, and (d) NSD statistics for **2021/22** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. 6]

3593 Figure [S138](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **median** hourly O_3
3594 VMR (ppbv) and (b) MB, (c) FAC2, and (d) NSD statistics for **2021/22** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. 7]

3595 Figure [S139](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **median** hourly $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
3596 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (b) MB, (c) FAC2, and (d) NSD statistics for **2021/22** for all NRT stations.
3597 [cf. Fig. 8]

3598 Figure [S140](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3599 NO_2 VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for **2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016** for all AQS
3600 and NAPS stations and **2021/22** for all NRT stations.

3601 Figure [S141](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3602 O_3 VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS
3603 and NAPS stations and **2021/22** for all NRT stations.

3604 Figure [S142](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3605 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
3606 for all AQS and NAPS stations and **2021/22** for all NRT stations.

3607 Figure [S143](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3608 NO VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS
3609 and NAPS stations.

3610 Figure [S144](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly
3611 HNO_3 VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all
3612 CAPMoN and CASTNET stations.

3613 Figure [S145](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean bi-
3614 weekly **NH_3 concentration** ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015,
3615 and 2016 for all AMoN and NAPS stations. Note that native AMoN units were kept as insufficient
3616 information was available from the network to convert to VMR units.

3617 Figure [S146](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly
3618 SO_2 VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS,
3619 CAPMoN, CASTNET, and NAPS stations.

3620 Figure [S147](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3621 CO VMR (ppmv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS
3622 and NAPS stations.

3623 Figure [S148](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3624 **ETHE** VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all
3625 PAMS and NAPS stations.

3626 Figure [S149](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3627 **HCHO** VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all
3628 PAMS and NAPS stations.

3629 Figure [S150](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3630 **ISOP** VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all
3631 PAMS and NAPS stations.

3632 Figure [S151](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3633 **PM_{2.5}-SO₄** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and
3634 2016 for all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

3635 Figure [S152](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3636 **PM_{2.5}-NO₃** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and
3637 2016 for all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

3638 Figure [S153](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3639 **PM_{2.5}-NH₄** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and
3640 2016 for all CSN and NAPS stations.

3641 Figure [S154](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3642 **PM_{2.5}-EC** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and
3643 2016 for all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

3644 Figure [S155](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3645 **PM_{2.5}-TOM** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and
3646 2016 for all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

3647 Figure [S156](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3648 **PM_{2.5}-CM** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and
3649 2016 for all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

3650 Figure [S157](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3651 **PM_{2.5}-SS** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and
3652 2016 for all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

3653 Figure [S158](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly
3654 **SO₄⁻** concentration in precipitation ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014,
3655 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

3656 Figure [S159](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly
3657 **NO₃⁻** concentration in precipitation ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014,
3658 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

3659 Figure [S160](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly
3660 **NH₄⁺** concentration in precipitation ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014,
3661 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

3662 Figure [S161](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly
3663 **precipitation** (mm) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all
3664 CAPMoN and NADP stations.

3665 Figure [S162](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly
3666 **SO₄⁻ wet deposition** ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
3667 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

3668 Figure [S163](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly
3669 NO_3^- wet deposition ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
3670 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

3671 Figure [S164](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly
3672 NH_4^+ wet deposition ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
3673 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

3674 Figure [S165](#). Time series of (left column) **diurnal** observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3675 NO_2 VMR (ppbv) for all NRT stations and diurnal NMB, CRMSE, and R statistics for **four seasons**: (top
3676 row) winter 2021/22 (DJF); (second row) spring 2022 (MAM); (third row) summer 2021 (JJA); and
3677 (bottom row) autumn 2021 (SON). Time is in hours LT.

3678 Figure [S166](#). Time series of (left column) **diurnal** observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3679 O_3 VMR (ppbv) for all NRT stations and diurnal NMB, CRMSE, and R statistics for **four seasons**: (top
3680 row) winter 2021/22 (DJF); (second row) spring 2022 (MAM); (third row) summer 2021 (JJA); and
3681 (bottom row) autumn 2021 (SON). Time is in hours LT.

3682 Figure [S167](#). Time series of (left column) **diurnal** observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3683 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ VMR (ppbv) for all NRT stations and diurnal NMB, CRMSE, and R statistics for **four seasons**: (top
3684 row) winter 2021/22 (DJF); (second row) spring 2022 (MAM); (third row) summer 2021 (JJA); and
3685 (bottom row) autumn 2021 (SON). Time is in hours LT.

3686 Figure [S168](#). Time series of **diurnal** observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted annual-mean hourly (left
3687 block) NO_2 VMR (ppbv), (middle block) O_3 VMR (ppbv), and (right block) $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
3688 for **four regions** [see Fig. S7] for 2021/22 for all NRT stations. Blue curves denote observations and orange
3689 curves denote model predictions.

3690 Figure [S169](#). **Monthly density scatterplots of hourly NO_2 VMR predictions** by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
3691 AQS and NAPS measurements or AirNow NRT measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014,
3692 2015, 2016, and 2021/22 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted
3693 frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3694 Figure [S170](#). **Monthly density scatterplots of hourly O_3 VMR predictions** by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. AQS
3695 and NAPS measurements or AirNow NRT measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015,
3696 2016, and 2021/22 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted
3697 frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3698 Figure [S171](#). **Monthly density scatterplots of hourly $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration predictions** by the RAQDPS-
3699 OP023 vs. AQS and NAPS measurements or AirNow NRT measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom)
3700 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, and 2021/22 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed
3701 and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3702 Figure [S172](#). **Monthly density scatterplots of hourly NO VMR predictions** by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
3703 AQS and NAPS measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to
3704 right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the
3705 top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3706 Figure [S173](#). **Monthly density scatterplots of weekly HNO_3 VMR predictions** by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
3707 CAPMoN and CASTNET measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from
3708 left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown
3709 on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3710 Figure [S174](#). **Monthly density scatterplots of biweekly NH_3 concentration predictions** by the RAQDPS-
3711 OP023 vs. AMoN and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for
3712 (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are
3713 shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3714 Figure [S175](#). Monthly density scatterplots of **weekly SO₂** VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
3715 AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET, and CASTNET measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015,
3716 and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3717 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3718 Figure [S176](#). Monthly density scatterplots of hourly **CO** VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
3719 AQS and NAPS measurements (ppmv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to
3720 right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the
3721 top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3722 Figure [S177](#). Monthly density scatterplots of **daily ETHE** VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
3723 AQS measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January,
3724 April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-
3725 hand margins, respectively.

3726 Figure [S178](#). Monthly density scatterplots of daily **HCHO** VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
3727 AQS measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January,
3728 April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-
3729 hand margins, respectively.

3730 Figure [S179](#). Monthly density scatterplots of daily **ISOP** VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
3731 AQS measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January,
3732 April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-
3733 hand margins, respectively.

3734 Figure [S180](#). Monthly density scatterplots of **daily PM_{2.5}-SO₄** concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-
3735 OP023 vs. CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015,
3736 and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3737 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3738 Figure [S181](#). Monthly density scatterplots of daily **PM_{2.5}-NO₃** concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-
3739 OP023 vs. CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015,
3740 and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3741 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3742 Figure [S182](#). Monthly density scatterplots of daily **PM_{2.5}-NH₄** concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-
3743 OP023 vs. CSN and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for
3744 (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are
3745 shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3746 Figure [S183](#). Monthly density scatterplots of daily **PM_{2.5}-EC** concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-
3747 OP023 vs. CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015,
3748 and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3749 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3750 Figure [S184](#). Monthly density scatterplots of daily **PM_{2.5}-TOM** concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-
3751 OP023 vs. CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015,
3752 and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3753 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3754 Figure [S185](#). Monthly density scatterplots of daily **PM_{2.5}-CM** concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-
3755 OP023 vs. CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015,
3756 and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3757 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3758 Figure [S186](#). Monthly density scatterplots of daily **PM_{2.5}-SS** concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-
3759 OP023 vs. CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015,

3760 and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3761 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3762 Figure [S187](#). Monthly density scatterplots of **weekly SO_4^- concentration-in-precipitation** predictions by
3763 the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014,
3764 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3765 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3766 Figure [S188](#). Monthly density scatterplots of weekly **NO_3^- concentration-in-precipitation** predictions by
3767 the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014,
3768 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3769 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3770 Figure [S189](#). Monthly density scatterplots of weekly **NH_4^+ concentration-in-precipitation** predictions by
3771 the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014,
3772 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3773 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3774 Figure [S190](#). Monthly density scatterplots of weekly **precipitation** predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023
3775 vs. CAPMoN and NADP measurements (mm) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from
3776 left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown
3777 on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3778 Figure [S191](#). Monthly density scatterplots of weekly **SO_4^- wet deposition** predictions by the RAQDPS-
3779 OP023 vs. CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
3780 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions
3781 are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3782 Figure [S192](#). Monthly density scatterplots of weekly **NO_3^- wet deposition** predictions by the RAQDPS-
3783 OP023 vs. CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
3784 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions
3785 are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3786 Figure [S193](#). Monthly density scatterplots of weekly **NH_4^+ wet deposition** predictions by the RAQDPS-
3787 OP023 vs. CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
3788 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions
3789 are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

3790 Figure [S194](#). Spatial distribution of **annual mean bias (MB)** for daily **$\text{PM}_{2.5}$** concentration predictions
3791 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) by the RAQDPS-OP023 at all AQS and NAPS **gravimetric measurement stations** for four
3792 consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S45]

3793 Figure [S195](#). Spatial distribution of **annual normalized mean bias (NMB)** for daily **$\text{PM}_{2.5}$** concentration
3794 (fraction) by the RAQDPS-OP023 at all AQS and NAPS **gravimetric measurement stations** for four
3795 consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S46]

3796 Figure [S196](#). Spatial distribution of **annual centred root mean square error (CRMSE)** for daily **$\text{PM}_{2.5}$**
3797 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) by the RAQDPS-OP023 at all AQS and NAPS **gravimetric**
3798 measurement **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S47]

3799 Figure [S197](#). Spatial distribution of **annual correlation coefficient (R)** for daily **$\text{PM}_{2.5}$** concentration
3800 predictions (fraction) by the RAQDPS-OP023 at all AQS and NAPS **gravimetric measurement stations**
3801 for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S48]

3802 Figure [S198](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily
3803 **$\text{PM}_{2.5}$** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
3804 for all AQS and NAPS **gravimetric measurement stations**. [cf. Fig. S142]

3805 Figure [S199](#). Monthly density scatterplots of daily **$\text{PM}_{2.5}$** concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-
3806 OP023 vs. AQS and NAPS **gravimetric measurements** ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015,

3807 and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency
3808 distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively. [cf. Fig. S171]

3809 Figure [S200](#). Stacked bar graphs of observed vs. RAQDPS-OP023-predicted domain-wide **season-mean**
3810 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) based on **CSN** $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ speciation network daily
3811 measurements and hindcasts for four consecutive years. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two
3812 rows below to 2014 and 2015, and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four seasonal bar-graph pairs
3813 (observed and predicted), starting with winter (DJF) on the left, and then spring (MAM), summer (JJA),
3814 and autumn (SON) on the right. [cf. Fig. 15]

3815 Figure [S201](#). Stacked bar graphs of observed vs. RAQDPS-OP023-predicted domain-wide **season-mean**
3816 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) based on **IMPROVE** $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ speciation network daily
3817 measurements and hindcasts for four consecutive years. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two
3818 rows below to 2014 and 2015, and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four seasonal bar-graph pairs
3819 (observed and predicted), starting with winter (DJF) on the left, and then spring (MAM), summer (JJA),
3820 and autumn (SON) on the right. [cf. Fig. 15]

3821 Figure [S202](#). Stacked bar graphs of observed vs. RAQDPS-OP023-predicted domain-wide **season-mean**
3822 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) based on **NAPS** $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ speciation network daily
3823 measurements and hindcasts for four consecutive years. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two
3824 rows below to 2014 and 2015, and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four seasonal bar-graph pairs
3825 (observed and predicted), starting with winter (DJF) on the left, and then spring (MAM), summer (JJA),
3826 and autumn (SON) on the right. [cf. Fig. 15]

3827 Figure [S203](#). Time series of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **monthly** mean variation of eight $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical
3828 component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) area-weighted averaged over the entire domain and 2013 to 2016
3829 simulations. These components are SO_4 , NO_3 , NH_4 , EC, POM, SOM, CM, and SS (shown ordered from
3830 bottom to top in stacked bar graphs). [cf. Fig. 15]

3831 Figure [S204](#). Time series of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted domain-mean **diurnal** (UTC) variation of eight
3832 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) averaged over the entire domain and 2013 to 2016
3833 simulations for each of four seasons: (a) winter; (b) spring; (c) summer; and (d) autumn. These components
3834 are SO_4 , NO_3 , NH_4 , CM, SS, EC, POM, and SOM (shown ordered from bottom to top in stacked bar
3835 graphs). [cf. Fig. 16]

3836 Figure [S205](#). Stacked bar graphs of observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **annual-mean regional**
3837 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for four consecutive years based on combined CSN,
3838 IMPROVE, and NAPS $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ speciation network daily measurements. The top row corresponds to 2013,
3839 the next two rows below to 2014 and 2015, and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four regional bar-
3840 graph pairs (observed and predicted), starting with western Canada on the left, then eastern Canada, western
3841 U.S., and eastern U.S. on the right.

3842 Figure [S206](#). Stacked bar graphs of observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **annual-mean regional**
3843 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for four consecutive years based on CSN-network daily
3844 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ speciation measurements. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two rows below to 2014 and
3845 2015, and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four regional bar-graph pairs (observed and predicted),
3846 starting with western Canada on the left, then eastern Canada, western U.S., and eastern U.S. on the right.
3847 [cf. S205]

3848 Figure [S207](#). Stacked bar graphs of observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **annual-mean regional**
3849 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for four consecutive years based on **IMPROVE**-
3850 network daily $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ speciation measurements. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two rows below
3851 to 2014 and 2015, and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four regional bar-graph pairs (observed and
3852 predicted), starting with western Canada on the left, then eastern Canada, western U.S., and eastern U.S.
3853 on the right. [cf. S205]

3854 Figure [S208](#). Stacked bar graphs of observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **annual-mean regional**
3855 **PM_{2.5}** chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for four consecutive years based on **NAPS**-network
3856 daily **PM_{2.5}** speciation measurements. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two rows below to 2014
3857 and 2015, and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four regional bar-graph pairs (observed and predicted),
3858 starting with western Canada on the left, then eastern Canada, western U.S., and eastern U.S. on the right.
3859 [cf. S205]

3860 Figure [S209](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3861 **NO₂** VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for **2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016** for all AQS
3862 and NAPS **urban** stations. [cf. Fig. S140]

3863 Figure [S210](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3864 **NO₂** VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for **2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016** for all AQS
3865 and NAPS **rural** stations. [cf. Fig. S140]

3866 Figure [S211](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3867 **O₃** VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS
3868 and NAPS **urban** stations. [cf. Fig. S141]

3869 Figure [S212](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3870 **O₃** VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS
3871 and NAPS **rural** stations. [cf. Fig. S141]

3872 Figure [S213](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023- predicted mean hourly
3873 **PM_{2.5}** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
3874 for all AQS and NAPS **urban** stations [cf. Fig. S142]

3875 Figure [S214](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly
3876 **PM_{2.5}** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
3877 for all AQS and NAPS **rural** stations [cf. Fig. S142]

3878 Figure [S215](#). Time series of seasonal mean bias (MB) scores for surface (a) **NO₂** VMR (ppbv), (b) **O₃** VMR
3879 (ppbv), and (c) **PM_{2.5}** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) measurements for all available North American NRT
3880 measurement stations for the periods Jan. 2010–June 2019 and June 2021–May 2022. The solid blue line
3881 denotes scores for the operational RAQDPS at the time while the solid orange line denotes scores for the
3882 RAQDPS-OP023 forecasts and hindcasts.

3883 Figure [S216](#). Time series of seasonal normalized mean bias (NMB) scores for surface (a) **NO₂** VMR
3884 (ppbv), (b) **O₃** VMR (ppbv), and (c) **PM_{2.5}** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) measurements for all available North
3885 American NRT measurement stations for the periods Jan. 2010–June 2019 and June 2021–May 2022. The
3886 solid blue line denotes scores for the operational RAQDPS at the time while the solid orange line denotes
3887 scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 forecasts and hindcasts. The dashed black lines mark the benchmark goal
3888 thresholds from Emery et al. (2017) and Zhai et al. (2024).

3889 Figure [S217](#). Time series of seasonal normalized mean absolute error (NMAE) scores for surface (a) **NO₂**
3890 VMR (ppbv), (b) **O₃** VMR (ppbv), and (c) **PM_{2.5}** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) measurements for all available
3891 North American NRT measurement stations for the periods Jan. 2010–June 2019 and June 2021–May 2022.
3892 The solid blue line denotes scores for the operational RAQDPS at the time while the solid orange line
3893 denotes scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 forecasts and hindcasts. The dashed black lines mark the
3894 benchmark goal thresholds from Emery et al. (2017) and Zhai et al. (2024).

3895 Figure [S218](#). Time series of seasonal root mean square error (RMSE) scores for surface (a) **NO₂** VMR
3896 (ppbv), (b) **O₃** VMR (ppbv), and (c) **PM_{2.5}** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) measurements for all available North
3897 American NRT measurement stations for the periods Jan. 2010–June 2019 and June 2021–May 2022. The
3898 solid blue line denotes scores for the operational RAQDPS at the time while the solid orange line denotes
3899 scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 forecasts and hindcasts.

3900 Figure [S219](#). Time series of seasonal factor-of-2 (FAC2) scores for surface (a) NO₂ VMR (ppbv), (b) O₃
3901 VMR (ppbv), and (c) PM_{2.5} concentration (μg·m⁻³) measurements for all available North American NRT
3902 measurement stations for the periods Jan. 2010–June 2019 and June 2021–May 2022. The solid blue line
3903 denotes scores for the version of the operational RAQDPS that was in service at the time while the solid
3904 orange line denotes scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 forecasts and hindcasts.

3905 Figure [S220](#). Spatial distribution of predicted 2021/22 mean annual abundance fields of hourly (a) NO₂,
3906 (b) O₃, and (c) PM_{2.5} with observed and predicted station annual abundances superimposed (shown as filled-
3907 in divided circles, same colour bar) for **RAQDPS-FW023**. Units are ppbv, ppbv, and μg·m⁻³, respectively.
3908 [cf. Fig. 1]

3909 Figure [S221](#). Spatial distribution of 2021/22 annual (a) MB, (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics at
3910 all NRT stations for hourly NO₂ measurements for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 2]

3911 Figure [S222](#). Spatial distribution of 2021/22 annual (a) MB, (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics at
3912 all NRT stations for hourly O₃ measurements for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 3]

3913 Figure [S223](#). Spatial distribution of 2021/22 annual (a) MB, (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics at
3914 all NRT stations for hourly PM_{2.5} measurements for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 4]

3915 Figure [S224](#). Spatial distribution of predicted 2021/22 mean seasonal abundance fields (from left to right:
3916 winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) of hourly (top row) NO₂, (middle row) O₃,
3917 and (bottom row) PM_{2.5} with observed and predicted seasonal station abundances superimposed (shown as
3918 filled-in divided circles, same colour bar) for **RAQDPS-FW023**. Units are ppbv, ppbv, and μg·m⁻³,
3919 respectively. [cf. Fig. 5]

3920 Figure [S225](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed and predicted mean hourly NO₂ VMRs (ppbv) and
3921 (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for 2021/22 for all NRT stations for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf.
3922 Fig. 6]

3923 Figure [S226](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed and predicted mean hourly O₃ VMRs (ppbv) and
3924 (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for 2021/22 for all NRT stations for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf.
3925 Fig. 7]

3926 Figure [S227](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed and predicted mean hourly PM_{2.5} concentrations
3927 (μg·m⁻³) and (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for 2021/22 for all NRT stations for
3928 **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 8]

3929 Figure [S228](#). Time series of **diurnal** (a) observed and predicted annual-mean hourly NO₂ VMRs (ppbv)
3930 and (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for all of 2021/22 for all NRT stations for **RAQDPS-FW023**.
3931 Time is in hours LT. [cf. Fig. 9]

3932 Figure [S229](#). Time series of **diurnal** (a) observed and predicted annual-mean hourly O₃ VMRs (ppbv) and
3933 (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for all of 2021/22 for all NRT stations for **RAQDPS-FW023**.
3934 Time is in hours LT. [cf. Fig. 10]

3935 Figure [S230](#). Time series of **diurnal** (a) observed and predicted annual-mean hourly PM_{2.5} concentrations
3936 (μg·m⁻³) and (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for all of 2021/22 for all NRT stations for
3937 **RAQDPS-FW023**. Time is in hours LT. [cf. Fig. 11]

3938 Figure [S231](#). Time series of monthly observed and predicted mean hourly (left) NO₂ VMR (ppbv), (centre)
3939 O₃ VMR (ppbv), and (right) PM_{2.5} concentration (μg·m⁻³) in LT for all NRT stations but stratified into **four**
3940 **regions** for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 12]

3941 Figure [S232](#). Time series of monthly statistics (med O, med P, MB, CRMSE, NSD) for hourly NO₂ VMR
3942 (ppbv) for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. S137]

3943 Figure [S233](#). Time series of monthly statistics (med O, med P, MB, CRMSE, NSD) for hourly O₃ VMR
3944 (ppbv) for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. S138]

3945 Figure [S234](#). Time series of monthly statistics (med O, med P, MB, CRMSE, NSD) for hourly PM_{2.5}
3946 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. S139]

3947 Figure [S235](#). Time series of monthly statistics (avg O, avg P, NMB, FAC2, R) for hourly NO₂ VMR (ppbv)
3948 for 2013–2016 for RAQDPS-OP023 and 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. S140]

3949 Figure [S236](#). Time series of monthly statistics (avg O, avg P, NMB, FAC2, R) for hourly O₃ VMR (ppbv)
3950 for 2013–2016 for RAQDPS-OP023 and 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. S141]

3951 Figure [S237](#). Time series of monthly statistics (avg O, avg P, NMB, FAC2, R) for hourly PM_{2.5}
3952 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for 2013–2016 for RAQDPS-OP023 and 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf.
3953 Fig. S142]

3954 Figure [S238](#). Time series of O and M diurnal concentrations of mean hourly NO₂ VMR (ppbv) by **season**
3955 for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT measurement stations. [cf. Fig. S165]

3956 Figure [S239](#). Time series of O and M diurnal concentrations of mean hourly O₃ VMR (ppbv) by **season**
3957 for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT measurement stations. [cf. Fig. S166]

3958 Figure [S240](#). Time series of O and M diurnal concentrations of mean hourly PM_{2.5} concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)
3959 by **season** for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT measurement stations. [cf. Fig. S167]

3960 Figure [S241](#). Time series of O and M diurnal concentrations of annual-mean hourly NO₂ VMR (ppbv), O₃
3961 VMR (ppbv), and PM_{2.5} concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) by **region** for 2021/22 **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. S168]

3962 Figure [S242](#). Monthly density scatterplots of hourly NO₂ VMR predictions vs. AirNow NRT measurements
3963 (ppbv) for 4 mid-season months for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. S169]

3964 Figure [S243](#). Monthly density scatterplots of hourly O₃ VMR predictions vs. AirNow NRT measurements
3965 (ppbv) for 4 mid-season months for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. S170]

3966 Figure [S244](#). Monthly density scatterplots of hourly PM_{2.5} concentration predictions vs. AirNow NRT
3967 measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for 4 mid-season months for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. S171]

3968 Figure [S245](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed and predicted mean hourly PM_{2.5} concentrations
3969 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for 2021/22 for all NRT **urban** stations for both
3970 **RAQDPS-OP023** and **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Figs. 8, S227, S213, S214]

3971 Figure [S246](#). Time series of **monthly** (a) observed and predicted mean hourly PM_{2.5} concentrations
3972 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for 2021/22 for all NRT **rural** stations for both
3973 **RAQDPS-OP023** and **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Figs. 8, S227, S213, S214]

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3975 Figure S1. Spatial distribution of 2013 annual anthropogenic **emissions** (tonnes/grid cell) of (a) NO_x,
 3976 (b) VOC, (c) CO, (d) SO₂, (e) NH₃, and (f) PM_{2.5} and 2013 annual biogenic emissions of (g) monoterpenes,
 3977 (h) isoprene, (i) other VOCs, and (j) NO.

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 3981 Figure S2. Monitoring station locations for (a) NO₂, (b) O₃, and (c) PM_{2.5} hourly measurements for the
 3982 **2021/22** period for the NAPS network in Canada and the AirNow network in U.S.

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 3987 Figure S3. Monitoring station locations for (a) NO₂, (b) O₃, and (c) PM_{2.5} hourly measurements for the
 3988 **2013-2016** period for the NAPS network in Canada (blue symbols) and the AQS network in the U.S.
 3989 (orange symbols). Note that the green triangles in panel (c) indicate non-FRM/FEM monitors (code 88502)
 3990 vs. the hourly FEM monitors (code 88101) denoted by the orange squares.

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 3995 Figure S4. Monitoring station locations for (a) NO and (b) CO hourly measurements and (c) SO₂ and HNO₃
 3996 measurements from the CAPMoN daily air-chemistry network in Canada and the CASTNET weekly air-
 3997 chemistry network in the U.S., and NH₃ measurements from the AMoN biweekly passive-sampler network
 3998 in the U.S. for the **2013-2016** period (indicated by blue circles, orange squares, and green triangles,
 3999 respectively). Note that many AMoN stations are co-located with CASTNET stations.

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 4003 Figure S5. Monitoring station locations for the **2013–2016** period for AQS (left) HCHO daily measurement
 4004 stations (PAMS, NATTS, S/L) and (right) ETHE and ISOP hourly measurement stations (PAMS).
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 4009 Figure S6. Monitoring station locations for the **2013–2016** period for (a) AQS, IMPROVE, and NAPS
 4010 daily $PM_{2.5}$ gravimetric mass (indicated by triangles, squares, and circles, respectively), (b) CSN,
 4011 IMPROVE, and NAPS networks for 24-hour $PM_{2.5}$ speciation (indicated by circles, squares, and triangles,
 4012 respectively); and (c) CAPMoN daily and NADP-NTN weekly precipitation-chemistry networks (indicated
 4013 by circles and squares, respectively).
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4017 Figure S7. Location of four spatial analysis regions: western Canada (WCAN; red); eastern Canada
4018 (ECAN; green); western U.S. (WUSA; blue); and eastern U.S. (EUSA; gray). The filled black circles
4019 denote the locations of National Air Pollution Surveillance (NAPS) network NO_2 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, and O_3 stations in
4020 Canada and air quality stations reporting to the AirNow program in the U.S. in 2015.

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4023 Figure S8. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal 2 m temperature** fields (°C); from left
 4024 to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row)
 4025 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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4029 Figure S9. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal 10 m wind speed** fields ($\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$); from
 4030 left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second
 4031 row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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4034 Figure S10. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal precipitation** fields (mm); from left
 4035 to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row)
 4036 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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4040 Figure S11. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal NO₂** VMR fields (ppbv); from left to
 4041 right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON] for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row)
 4042 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22. [cf. Fig. 5]

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4045 Figure S12. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal O₃** VMR fields (ppbv); from left to
 4046 right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row)
 4047 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22. [cf. Fig. 5]

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4050 Figure S13. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal PM_{2.5}** total mass concentration fields
 4051 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row)
 4052 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22. [cf. Fig. 5]

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 4055 Figure S14. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal NO** VMR fields (ppbv); from left to
 4056 right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row)
 4057 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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Figure S15. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal HNO₃** VMR fields (ppbv); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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Figure S16. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal NH₃** VMR fields (ppbv); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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 4070 Figure S17. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal SO₂** VMR fields (ppbv); from left to
 4071 right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row)
 4072 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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4075 Figure S18. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal CO** VMR fields (ppbv); from left to
 4076 right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row)
 4077 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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 4080 Figure S19. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal ETHE** VMR fields (ppbv); from left
 4081 to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row)
 4082 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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4085 Figure S20. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal HCHO** VMR fields (ppbv); from left
 4086 to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row)
 4087 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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 4090 Figure S21. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal ISOP** VMR fields (ppbv); from left
 4091 to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row)
 4092 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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4095 Figure S22. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal $PM_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$ concentration** fields
 4096 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row)
 4097 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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 4100 Figure S23. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal PM_{2.5}-NO₃ concentration** fields
 4101 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row)
 4102 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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 4105 Figure S24. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal $PM_{2.5}-NH_4$ concentration** fields
 4106 ($\mu g \cdot m^{-3}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row)
 4107 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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4110 Figure S25. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal PM_{2.5}-EC concentration** fields (μg·m⁻³); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013;
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 4112 (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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 4115 Figure S26. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal PM_{2.5}-POM concentration** fields
 4116 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row)
 4117 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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 4120 Figure S27. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal PM_{2.5}-SOM concentration** fields
 4121 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row)
 4122 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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 4125 Figure S28. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal PM_{2.5}-TOM concentration** fields
 4126 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row)
 4127 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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 4130 Figure S29. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal PM_{2.5}-CM concentration** fields
 4131 ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row)
 4132 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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 4135 Figure S30. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal PM_{2.5}-SS concentration** fields ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013;
 4136 (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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Figure S31. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal $\text{SO}_4^{=}$ wet concentration** fields ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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 4145 Figure S32. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal NO_3^- wet concentration** fields
 4146 ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row)
 4147 2013; (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.
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4150 Figure S33. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal NH_4^+ wet concentration** fields ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$); from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013;
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 4152 (second row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22.

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4155 Figure S34. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal SO₄²⁻ wet deposition** fields (mg·m⁻²);
 4156 from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second
 4157 row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22. [cf. Figures S10 and S31]

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 4160 Figure S35. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal NO₃⁻ wet deposition** fields (mg·m⁻²);
 4161 from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second
 4162 row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22. [cf. Figures S10 and S32]
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 4165 Figure S36. Spatial distribution of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted **mean seasonal NH₄⁺ wet deposition** fields (mg·m⁻²);
 4166 from left to right: winter [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) for **five years**: (top row) 2013; (second
 4167 row) 2014; (third row) 2015; (fourth row) 2016; and (bottom row) 2021/22. [cf. Figures S10 and S33]
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4170 Figure S37. Spatial distribution of **annual** mean bias (MB) scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly NO₂ VMR
 4171 predictions (ppbv) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4172 (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 3]

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4174 Figure S38. Spatial distribution of **annual** normalized mean bias (NMB) scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly
 4175 NO₂ VMR predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4176 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 3]

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Figure S39. Spatial distribution of **annual** centred root mean square error (**CRMSE**) scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO₂** VMR predictions (ppbv) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 3]

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4184 Figure S40. Spatial distribution of **annual** correlation coefficient (**R**) scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly NO₂
 4185 VMR predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
 4186 and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 3]

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4189 Figure S41. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **O₃** VMR predictions (ppbv)
 4190 at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 4]

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4193 Figure S42. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **O₃** VMR predictions
 4194 (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf.
 4195 Fig. 4]

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Figure S43. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **O₃** VMR predictions (ppbv) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 4]

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4203 Figure S44. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **O₃** VMR predictions
 4204 (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf.
 4205 Fig. 4]

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4208 Figure S45. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **PM_{2.5}** concentration
 4209 predictions ($\mu g\cdot m^{-3}$) at all AQS and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4210 (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 5]

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4213 Figure S46. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **PM_{2.5}** concentration
 4214 (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf.
 4215 Fig. 5]

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4218 Figure S47. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **PM_{2.5}** concentration
 4219 predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4220 (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 5]

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4223 Figure S48. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **PM_{2.5}** concentration
 4224 predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4225 (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. 5]

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4228 Figure S49. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO** VMR predictions
 4229 (ppbv) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf.
 4230 Fig. S35]

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4233 Figure S50. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO** VMR predictions
 4234 (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf.
 4235 Fig. S36]

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4238 Figure S51. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO** VMR predictions
 4239 (ppbv) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf.
 4240 Fig. S37]

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4243 Figure S52. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **NO** VMR predictions
 4244 (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf.
 4245 Fig. S38]

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Figure S53. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly HNO_3 VMR predictions (ppbv) at all CAPMoN and CASTNET **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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 4252 Figure S54. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **HNO₃** VMR predictions
 4253 (fraction) at all CAPMoN and CASTNET **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4254 (d) 2016.
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4257 Figure S55. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **HNO₃** VMR
 4258 predictions (ppbv) at all CAPMoN and CASTNET **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
 4259 and (d) 2016.

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Figure S56. Comparison of spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **HNO₃** VMR predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and CASTNET **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4267 Figure S57. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for biweekly NH_3 VMR predictions
 4268 (ppbv) at all AMoN and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4271 Figure S58. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for biweekly NH₃ VMR predictions
 4272 (fraction) at all AMoN and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4275 Figure S59. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for biweekly NH_3 VMR
 4276 predictions (ppbv) at all AMoN and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4277 (d) 2016.

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4280 Figure S60. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for biweekly NH_3 VMR predictions
 4281 (fraction) at all AMoN and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4284 Figure S61. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₂** VMR predictions
 4285 (ppbv) at all AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET, and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
 4286 and (d) 2016.

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4289 Figure S62. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₂** VMR predictions
 4290 (fraction) at all AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET, and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4291 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4294 Figure S63. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₂** VMR predictions
 4295 (ppbv) at all AQS, CAPMoN, CASTNET, and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015;
 4296 and (d) 2016.

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 4299 Figure S64. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₂** VMR predictions
 4300 (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4301 (d) 2016.
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4304 Figure S65. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **CO** VMR predictions
 4305 (ppbm) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4308 Figure S66. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **CO** VMR predictions
 4309 (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4312 Figure S67. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **CO** VMR predictions
 4313 (**ppbm**) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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Figure S68. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for hourly **CO** VMR predictions (fraction) at all AQS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4320 Figure S69. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ETHE** VMR predictions
 4321 (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4324 Figure S70. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ETHE** VMR predictions
 4325 (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4328 Figure S71. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ETHE** VMR
 4329 predictions (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4330 (d) 2016.

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Figure S72. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ETHE** VMR predictions (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4337 Figure S73. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **HCHO** VMR predictions
 4338 (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4341 Figure S74. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **HCHO** VMR predictions
 4342 (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4345 Figure S75. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **HCHO** VMR
 4346 predictions (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4347 (d) 2016.

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Figure S76. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **HCHO** VMR predictions (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4354 Figure S77. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ISOP** VMR predictions
 4355 (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4358 Figure S78. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ISOP** VMR predictions
 4359 (fraction) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4362 Figure S79. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ISOP** VMR predictions
 4363 (ppbv) at all PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4366 Figure S80. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **ISOP** VMR (fraction) at all
 4367 PAMS and NAPS **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4370 Figure S81. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SO₄** concentration
 4371 predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4372 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S43]

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4375 Figure S82. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SO₄** concentration
 4376 (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4377 (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S44]

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4380 Figure S83. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SO₄**
 4381 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
 4382 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S45]

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4385 Figure S84. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SO₄** concentration
 4386 predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4387 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S46]

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4390 Figure S85. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NO₃** concentration
 4391 predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4392 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4395 Figure S86. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NO₃** concentration
 4396 (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4397 (d) 2016.

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4400 Figure S87. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NO₃**
 4401 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
 4402 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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Figure S88. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NO}_3$ concentration predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4410 Figure S89. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NH₄** concentration
 4411 predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4412 (d) 2016.

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Figure S90. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NH₄** concentration (fraction) at all CSN and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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Figure S91. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-NH₄** concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4424 Figure S92. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NH}_4$ concentration
 4425 predictions (fraction) at all CSN and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4426 (d) 2016.

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4429 Figure S93. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily $PM_{2.5}$ -EC concentration
 4430 predictions ($\mu g \cdot m^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4431 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4434 Figure S94. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-EC** concentration
 4435 (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4436 (d) 2016.

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4439 Figure S95. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-EC** concentration
 4440 predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4441 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4444 Figure S96. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-EC** concentration
 4445 predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4446 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4449 Figure S97. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-TOM** concentration
 4450 predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4451 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4454 Figure S98. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-TOM** concentration
 4455 (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4456 (d) 2016.

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4459 Figure S99. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-TOM**
 4460 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
 4461 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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Figure S100. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-TOM** concentration predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4469 Figure S101. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-CM** concentration
 4470 predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4471 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4474 Figure S102. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-CM** concentration
 4475 (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4476 (d) 2016.

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4479 Figure S103. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-CM**
 4480 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
 4481 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4484 Figure S104. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-CM** concentration
 4485 predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4486 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4489 Figure S105. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SS** concentration
 4490 predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4491 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4494 Figure S106. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **$PM_{2.5-SS}$** concentration
 4495 (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4496 (d) 2016.

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4499 Figure S107. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SS**
 4500 concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
 4501 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4504 Figure S108. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for daily **PM_{2.5}-SS** concentration
 4505 predictions (fraction) at all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4506 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4509 Figure S109. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO_4^- concentration-in-
 4510 precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4511 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4514 Figure S110. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **SO₄⁻** concentration-in-
 4515 precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4516 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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2013 annual CRMSE for weekly SO_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1}) 2014 annual CRMSE for weekly SO_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1})

2015 annual CRMSE for weekly SO_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1}) 2016 annual CRMSE for weekly SO_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1})

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4519 Figure S111. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO_4 concentration-
4520 in-precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
4521 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4524 Figure S112. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO₄⁻ concentration-in-
 4525 precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4526 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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2013 annual MB for weekly NO_3^- concentration in precip (mg L^{-1}) 2014 annual MB for weekly NO_3^- concentration in precip (mg L^{-1})

2015 annual MB for weekly NO_3^- concentration in precip (mg L^{-1}) 2016 annual MB for weekly NO_3^- concentration in precip (mg L^{-1})

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4529 Figure S113. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NO_3^- concentration-in-
4530 precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
4531 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4534 Figure S114. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **NO₃⁻** concentration-in-
 4535 precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4536 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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2013 annual CRMSE for weekly NO_3^- concentration in precip (mg L^{-1}) 2014 annual CRMSE for weekly NO_3^- concentration in precip (mg L^{-1})

2015 annual CRMSE for weekly NO_3^- concentration in precip (mg L^{-1}) 2016 annual CRMSE for weekly NO_3^- concentration in precip (mg L^{-1})

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4539 Figure S115. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NO_3^- concentration-
4540 in-precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
4541 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4544 Figure S116. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NO₃⁻ concentration-in-
 4545 precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4546 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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2013 annual MB for weekly NH_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1}) 2014 annual MB for weekly NH_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1})

2015 annual MB for weekly NH_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1}) 2016 annual MB for weekly NH_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1})

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4549 Figure S117. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+ concentration-in-
4550 precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
4551 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4554 Figure S118. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH₄⁺ concentration-
 4555 in-precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
 4556 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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2013 annual CRMSE for weekly NH_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1}) 2014 annual CRMSE for weekly NH_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1})

2015 annual CRMSE for weekly NH_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1}) 2016 annual CRMSE for weekly NH_4 concentration in precip (mg L^{-1})

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4559 Figure S119. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+ concentration-
4560 in-precipitation predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
4561 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4564 Figure S120. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+ concentration-in-
 4565 precipitation predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014;
 4566 (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4569 Figure S121. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **precipitation** predictions
 4570 (mm) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4573 Figure S122. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **precipitation**
 4574 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4575 (d) 2016.

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4578 Figure S123. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **precipitation**
 4579 predictions (mm) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4580 (d) 2016.

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4583 Figure S124. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **precipitation** predictions
 4584 (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016.

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4587 Figure S125. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO_4^- wet deposition
 4588 predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4589 (d) 2016.

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4592 Figure S126. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO₄²⁻ wet deposition
 4593 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4594 (d) 2016.

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4597 Figure S127. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO₄⁻ wet deposition
 4598 predictions (mg·m⁻²) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4599 (d) 2016.

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 4602 Figure S128. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly SO₄⁻ wet deposition
 4603 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4604 (d) 2016.
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4607 Figure S129. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NO₃⁻ wet deposition
 4608 predictions (mg·m⁻²) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4609 (d) 2016.

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 4612 Figure S130. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NO₃⁻ wet deposition
 4613 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4614 (d) 2016.
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4617 Figure S131. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly **NO₃⁻** wet deposition
 4618 predictions (mg·m⁻²) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4619 (d) 2016.

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4622 Figure S132. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NO₃⁻ wet deposition
 4623 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4624 (d) 2016.

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4627 Figure S133. Spatial distribution of **annual MB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+ wet deposition
 4628 predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4629 (d) 2016.

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4632 Figure S134. Spatial distribution of **annual NMB** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH₄⁺ wet deposition
 4633 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4634 (d) 2016.

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4637 Figure S135. Spatial distribution of **annual CRMSE** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+ wet deposition
 4638 predictions ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4639 (d) 2016.

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4641
 4642 Figure S136. Spatial distribution of **annual R** scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 for weekly NH_4^+ wet deposition
 4643 predictions (fraction) at all CAPMoN and NADP stations for four consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and
 4644 (d) 2016.
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4648 Figure S137. Time series of **monthly** (a) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted and observed **median** hourly **NO₂** VMR (ppbv)
 4649 and (b) MB, (c) FAC2, and (d) NSD statistics for **2021/22** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. 6]

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4653 Figure S138. Time series of **monthly** (a) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted and observed **median** hourly **O₃** VMR (ppbv)
 4654 and (b) MB, (c) FAC2, and (d) NSD statistics for **2021/22** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. 7]

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4658 Figure S139. Time series of **monthly** (a) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted and observed **median** hourly **PM_{2.5}**
 4659 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (b) MB, (c) FAC2, and (d) NSD statistics for **2021/22** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. 8]

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 4664 Figure S140. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **NO₂** VMR
 4665 (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for **2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016** for all AQS and NAPS stations
 4666 and **2021/22** for all NRT stations.

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 4669 Figure S141. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **O₃** VMR
 4670 (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and NAPS stations
 4671 and **2021/22** for all NRT stations.

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 4674 Figure S142. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **PM_{2.5}**
 4675 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and
 4676 NAPS stations and **2021/22** for all NRT stations.

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 4679 Figure S143. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **NO** VMR
 4680 (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and NAPS stations.

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 4682 Figure S144. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly HNO_3
 4683 VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and
 4684 CASTNET stations.

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 4688 Figure S145. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean bi-weekly NH_3
 4689 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AMoN and
 4690 NAPS stations. Note that native AMoN units were kept as insufficient information is available from the network to
 4691 convert to VMR units.

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 4695 Figure S146. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly SO_2 VMR
 4696 (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS, CAPMoN,
 4697 CASTNET, and NAPS stations.

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 4701 Figure S147. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly CO VMR
 4702 (ppmv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and NAPS stations

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 4704 Figure S148. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily **ETHE** VMR
 4705 ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all PAMS and NAPS stations.

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 4709 Figure S149. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily **HCHO**
 4710 VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all PAMS and NAPS
 4711 stations.

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 4715 Figure S150. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily **ISOP** VMR
 4716 (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all PAMS and NAPS stations.

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 4720 Figure S151. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **PM_{2.5}-SO₄**
 4721 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CSN,
 4722 IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

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 4724 Figure S152. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **PM_{2.5}-NO₃**
 4725 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CSN,
 4726 IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

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 4729 Figure S153. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **PM_{2.5}-NH₄**
 4730 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CSN and
 4731 NAPS stations.

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 4734 Figure S154. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **PM_{2.5}-EC**
 4735 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CSN,
 4736 IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

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 4739 Figure S155. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **PM_{2.5}-**
 4740 **TOM** concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CSN,
 4741 IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

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4743 Figure S156. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **PM_{2.5}-CM**
 4744 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CSN,
 4745 IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

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4748 Figure S157. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **PM_{2.5}-SS**
 4749 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CSN,
 4750 IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

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4753 Figure S158. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly **SO₄²⁻**
 4754 concentration in precipitation ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
 4755 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

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4758 Figure S159. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly **NO₃⁻**
 4759 concentration in precipitation ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
 4760 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

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 4762 Figure S160. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly NH_4^+
 4763 concentration in precipitation ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
 4764 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.
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 4768 Figure S161. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly
 4769 **precipitation** (mm) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and
 4770 NADP stations.
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 4774 Figure S162. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly SO_4^{2-} wet
 4775 deposition ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and
 4776 NADP stations.
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 4780 Figure S163. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly NO_3^- wet
 4781 deposition ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and
 4782 NADP stations.

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4784 Figure S164. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean weekly NH_4^+ wet
 4785 deposition ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and
 4786 NADP stations.

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4790 Figure S165. Time series of (left column) **diurnal** observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **NO₂** VMR
 4791 (ppbv) for all NRT stations and diurnal NMB, CRMSE, and R statistics for **four seasons**: (top row) winter 2021/22
 4792 (DJF); (second row) spring 2022 (MAM); (third row) summer 2021 (JJA); and (bottom row) autumn 2021 (SON).
 4793 Time is in hours LT.

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4797 Figure S166. Time series of (left column) **diurnal** observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly O_3 VMR
 4798 (ppbv) for all NRT stations and diurnal NMB, CRMSE, and R statistics for **four seasons**: (top row) winter 2021/22
 4799 (DJF); (second row) spring 2022 (MAM); (third row) summer 2021 (JJA); and (bottom row) autumn 2021 (SON).
 4800 Time is in hours LT.

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4804 Figure S167. Time series of (left column) **diurnal** observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly **PM_{2.5}** VMR
 4805 (ppbv) for all NRT stations and diurnal NMB, CRMSE, and R statistics for **four seasons**: (top row) winter 2021/22
 4806 (DJF); (second row) spring 2022 (MAM); (third row) summer 2021 (JJA); and (bottom row) autumn 2021 (SON).
 4807 Time is in hours LT.

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4811 Figure S168. Time series of **diurnal** observed and RAQDPS-OP023-predicted annual-mean hourly (left block)
 4812 **NO₂** VMR (ppbv), (middle block) **O₃** VMR (ppbv), and (right block) **PM_{2.5}** concentration (μg·m⁻³) for **four regions**
 4813 [see Fig. S7] for 2021/22 for all NRT stations. Blue curves denote observations and orange curves denote model
 4814 predictions.

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 4818 Figure S169. Monthly density scatterplots of hourly NO₂ VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. AQS and
 4819 NAPS measurements or AirNow NRT measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, and
 4820 2021/22 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are
 4821 shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

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4823 Figure S170. Monthly density scatterplots of hourly O_3 VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. AQS and NAPS
 4824 measurements or AirNow NRT measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, and 2021/22 for
 4825 (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on
 4826 the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

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4833 Figure S172. Monthly density scatterplots of hourly NO VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.AQS and
 4834 NAPS measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April,
 4835 July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins,
 4836 respectively.

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Figure S173. Monthly density scatterplots of weekly HNO₃ VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. CAPMoN and CASTNET measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

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4843 Figure S174. Monthly density scatterplots of **biweekly** NH_3 concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
 4844 AMoN and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right)
 4845 January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-
 4846 hand margins, respectively.

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4848 Figure S175. Monthly density scatterplots of **weekly SO₂ VMR** predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. AQS,
 4849 CAPMoN, CASTNET, and CASTNET measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for
 4850 (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on
 4851 the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

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4853 Figure S176. Monthly density scatterplots of hourly CO VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. AQS and
 4854 NAPS measurements (ppmv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April,
 4855 July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins,
 4856 respectively.

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4858 Figure S177. Monthly density scatterplots of **daily ETHE** VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. AQS
 4859 measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April,
 4860 and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins,
 4861 respectively.

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4863 Figure S178. Monthly density scatterplots of daily **HCHO** VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. AQS
 4864 measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July,
 4865 and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins,
 4866 respectively.

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 4868 Figure S179. Monthly density scatterplots of daily **ISOP** VMR predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. AQS
 4869 measurements (ppbv) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July,
 4870 and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins,
 4871 respectively.

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4873 Figure S180. Monthly density scatterplots of **daily $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-SO}_4$** concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
 4874 CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left
 4875 to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and
 4876 right-hand margins, respectively.

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Figure S181. Monthly density scatterplots of daily $PM_{2.5}-NO_3$ concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu g \cdot m^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

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4883 Figure S182. Monthly density scatterplots of daily $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NH}_4$ concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
 4884 CSN and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right)
 4885 January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-
 4886 hand margins, respectively.

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 4888 Figure S183. Monthly density scatterplots of daily $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-EC}$ concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
 4889 CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left
 4890 to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and
 4891 right-hand margins, respectively.

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4893 Figure S184. Monthly density scatterplots of daily **PM_{2.5}-TOM** concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023
 4894 vs. CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from
 4895 left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top
 4896 and right-hand margins, respectively.

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4898 Figure S185. Monthly density scatterplots of daily PM_{2.5}-CM concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
 4899 CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left
 4900 to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and
 4901 right-hand margins, respectively.

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 4908 Figure S187. Monthly density scatterplots of **weekly SO_4^- concentration-in-precipitation** predictions by the
 4909 RAQDPS-OP023 vs. CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
 4910 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown
 4911 on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

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4913 Figure S188. Monthly density scatterplots of weekly NO_3^- concentration-in-precipitation predictions by the
 4914 RAQDPS-OP023 vs. CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
 4915 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown
 4916 on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

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4918 Figure S189. Monthly density scatterplots of weekly NH_4^+ concentration-in-precipitation predictions by the
 4919 RAQDPS-OP023 vs. CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016
 4920 for (from left to right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown
 4921 on the top and right-hand margins, respectively.

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4923 Figure S190. Monthly density scatterplots of weekly **precipitation** predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. CAPMoN
 4924 and NADP measurements (mm) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right) January,
 4925 April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-hand margins,
 4926 respectively.

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4928 Figure S191. Monthly density scatterplots of weekly SO_4 wet deposition predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
 4929 CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right)
 4930 January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-
 4931 hand margins, respectively.

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4933 Figure S192. Monthly density scatterplots of weekly NO_3^- wet deposition predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs.
 4934 CAPMoN and NADP measurements ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to right)
 4935 January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and right-
 4936 hand margins, respectively.

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4943 Figure S194. Spatial distribution of **annual** mean bias (**MB**) for daily **PM_{2.5}** concentration predictions ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) by
 4944 the RAQDPS-OP023 at all AQS and NAPS **gravimetric** measurement **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
 4945 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S45]

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4947 Figure S195. Spatial distribution of **annual** normalized mean bias (NMB) for daily $PM_{2.5}$ concentration (fraction) by
 4948 the RAQDPS-OP023 at all AQS and NAPS **gravimetric** measurement **stations** for four consecutive years: (a) 2013;
 4949 (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S46]

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4951 Figure S196. Spatial distribution of **annual** centred root mean square error (CRMSE) for daily **PM_{2.5}** concentration
 4952 predictions ($\mu g \cdot m^{-3}$) by the RAQDPS-OP023 at all AQS and NAPS **gravimetric** measurement **stations** for four
 4953 consecutive years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S47]

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4955 Figure S197. Spatial distribution of **annual** correlation coefficient (**R**) for daily **PM_{2.5}** concentration predictions
 4956 (fraction) by the RAQDPS-OP023 at all AQS and NAPS **gravimetric** measurement **stations** for four consecutive
 4957 years: (a) 2013; (b) 2014; (c) 2015; and (d) 2016. [cf. Fig. S48]

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4961 Figure S198. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean daily **PM_{2.5}**
 4962 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and
 4963 NAPS **gravimetric** measurement **stations**. [cf. Fig. S142]

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4965 Figure S199. Monthly density scatterplots of daily $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration predictions by the RAQDPS-OP023 vs. AQS
 4966 and NAPS gravimetric measurements ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) from (top to bottom) 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for (from left to
 4967 right) January, April, July, and October. Observed and predicted frequency distributions are shown on the top and
 4968 right-hand margins, respectively. [cf. Fig. [S171](#)]

CSN Speciated PM_{2.5} ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)

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4970 Figure S200. Stacked bar graphs of observed vs. RAQDPS-OP023-predicted domain-wide **season-mean** PM_{2.5}
 4971 chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) based on CSN PM_{2.5} speciation network daily measurements and
 4972 hindcasts for four consecutive years. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two rows below to 2014 and 2015,
 4973 and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four seasonal bar-graph pairs (observed and predicted), starting with winter
 4974 (DJF) on the left, and then spring (MAM), summer (JJA), and autumn (SON) on the right. [cf. Fig. 15]

IMPROVE Speciated PM_{2.5} ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)

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Figure S201. Stacked bar graphs of observed vs. RAQDPS-OP023-predicted domain-wide **season-mean** PM_{2.5} chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) based on **IMPROVE** PM_{2.5} speciation network daily measurements and hindcasts for four consecutive years. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two rows below to 2014 and 2015, and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four seasonal bar-graph pairs (observed and predicted), starting with winter (DJF) on the left, and then spring (MAM), summer (JJA), and autumn (SON) on the right. [cf. Fig. 15]

NAPS Speciated $PM_{2.5}$ ($\mu g m^{-3}$)

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4982 Figure S202. Stacked bar graphs of observed vs. RAQDPS-OP023-predicted domain-wide **season-mean** $PM_{2.5}$
 4983 chemical component concentrations ($\mu g \cdot m^{-3}$) based on NAPS $PM_{2.5}$ speciation network daily measurements and
 4984 hindcasts for four consecutive years. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two rows below to 2014 and 2015,
 4985 and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four seasonal bar-graph pairs (observed and predicted), starting with winter
 4986 (DJF) on the left, and then spring (MAM), summer (JJA), and autumn (SON) on the right. [cf. Fig. 15]

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Figure S203. Time series of **RAQDPS-OP023-predicted monthly** mean variation of eight PM_{2.5} chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) area-weighted averaged over the *entire domain* and 2013 to 2016 simulations. These components are SO₄, NO₃, NH₄, EC, POM, SOM, CM, and SS (shown ordered from bottom to top in stacked bar graphs). [cf. Fig. 15]

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Figure S204. Time series of **RAQDPS-OP023-predicted domain-mean diurnal** (UTC) variation of eight PM_{2.5} chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) averaged over the *entire domain* and 2013 to 2016 simulations for each of four seasons: (a) winter; (b) spring; (c) summer; and (d) autumn. These components are SO₄, NO₃, NH₄, EC, POM, SOM, CM, and SS (shown ordered from bottom to top in stacked bar graphs). [cf. Fig. 16]

CSN+IMPROVE+NAPS Speciated PM_{2.5} ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)

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4999 Figure S205. Stacked bar graphs of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted and observed **annual-mean regional** PM_{2.5} chemical
 5000 component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for four consecutive years based on combined CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS PM_{2.5}
 5001 speciation network daily measurements. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two rows below to 2014 and 2015,
 5002 and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four regional bar-graph pairs (observed and predicted), starting with
 5003 western Canada on the left, then eastern Canada, western U.S., and eastern U.S. on the right.

CSN Speciated PM_{2.5} ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)

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Figure S206. Stacked bar graphs of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted and observed **annual-mean regional** PM_{2.5} chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for four consecutive years based on CSN-network daily PM_{2.5} speciation measurements. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two rows below to 2014 and 2015, and the bottom row to 2016. Each row has four regional bar-graph pairs (observed and predicted), starting with western Canada on the left, then eastern Canada, western U.S., and eastern U.S. on the right. [cf. S205]

IMPROVE Speciated $PM_{2.5}$ ($\mu g m^{-3}$)

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5011 Figure S207. Stacked bar graphs of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted and observed **annual-mean regional** $PM_{2.5}$ chemical
 5012 component concentrations ($\mu g \cdot m^{-3}$) for four consecutive years based on **IMPROVE**-network daily $PM_{2.5}$ speciation
 5013 measurements. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two rows below to 2014 and 2015, and the bottom row to
 5014 2016. Each row has four regional bar-graph pairs (observed and predicted), starting with western Canada on the left,
 5015 then eastern Canada, western U.S., and eastern U.S. on the right. [cf. S205]

NAPS Speciated PM_{2.5} ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)

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5017 Figure S208. Stacked bar graphs of RAQDPS-OP023-predicted and observed **annual-mean regional** PM_{2.5}
 5018 chemical component concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) for four consecutive years based on NAPS-network daily PM_{2.5}
 5019 speciation measurements. The top row corresponds to 2013, the next two rows below to 2014 and 2015, and the
 5020 bottom row to 2016. Each row has four regional bar-graph pairs (observed and predicted), starting with western
 5021 Canada on the left, then eastern Canada, western U.S., and eastern U.S. on the right. [cf. S205]

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5023 Figure S209. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly NO_2
 5024 VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for **2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016** for all AQS and NAPS
 5025 **urban** stations. [cf. Fig. S140]

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5029 Figure S210. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly NO_2
 5030 VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for **2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016** for all AQS and NAPS
 5031 **rural** stations. [cf. Fig. S140]

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5035 Figure S211. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly O_3 VMR
 5036 (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for **2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016** for all AQS and NAPS **urban**
 5037 stations. [cf. Fig. S141]

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5043 Figure S212. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly O_3 VMR
 5044 (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and NAPS **rural**
 5045 stations. [cf. Fig. S141]

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5049 Figure S213. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly $PM_{2.5}$
 5050 concentration ($\mu g \cdot m^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and
 5051 NAPS **urban** stations [cf. Fig. S142]

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5055 Figure S214. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) RAQDPS-OP023-predicted mean hourly $PM_{2.5}$
 5056 concentration ($\mu g \cdot m^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and
 5057 NAPS **rural** stations [cf. Fig. S142]

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5059 Figure S215. Time series of seasonal mean bias (MB) scores for surface (a) NO₂ VMR (ppbv), (b) O₃ VMR (ppbv),
 5060 and (c) PM_{2.5} concentration (μg·m⁻³) measurements for all available North American NRT measurement stations for
 5061 the periods Jan. 2010–June 2019 and June 2021–May 2022. The solid blue line denotes scores for the operational
 5062 RAQDPS at the time while the solid orange line denotes scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 forecasts and hindcasts.

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5064 Figure S216. Time series of seasonal normalized mean bias (NMB) scores for surface (a) NO₂ VMR (ppbv), (b) O₃
 5065 VMR (ppbv), and (c) PM_{2.5} concentration (μg·m⁻³) measurements for all available North American NRT measurement
 5066 stations for the periods Jan. 2010–June 2019 and June 2021–May 2022. The solid blue line denotes scores for the
 5067 operational RAQDPS at the time while the solid orange line denotes scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 forecasts and
 5068 hindcasts. The dashed black lines mark the benchmark goal thresholds from Emery et al. (2017) and Zhai et al. (2024).

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5071 Figure S217. Time series of seasonal normalized mean absolute error (NMAE) scores for surface (a) NO₂ VMR
 5072 (ppbv), (b) O₃ VMR (ppbv), and (c) PM_{2.5} concentration (μg·m⁻³) measurements for all available North American
 5073 NRT measurement stations for the periods Jan. 2010–June 2019 and June 2021–May 2022. The solid blue line denotes
 5074 scores for the operational RAQDPS at the time while the solid orange line denotes scores for the RAQDPS-OP023
 5075 forecasts and hindcasts. The dashed black lines mark the benchmark goal thresholds from Emery et al. (2017) and
 5076 Zhai et al. (2024).

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5078 Figure S218. Time series of seasonal root mean square error (RMSE) scores for surface (a) NO₂ VMR (ppbv), (b) O₃
 5079 VMR (ppbv), and (c) PM_{2.5} concentration (μg·m⁻³) measurements for all available North American NRT measurement
 5080 stations for the periods Jan. 2010–June 2019 and June 2021–May 2022. The solid blue line denotes scores for the
 5081 operational RAQDPS at the time while the solid orange line denotes scores for the RAQDPS-OP023 forecasts and
 5082 hindcasts.

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5084 Figure S219. Time series of seasonal factor-of-2 (FAC2) scores for surface (a) NO₂ VMR (ppbv), (b) O₃ VMR (ppbv),
 5085 and (c) PM_{2.5} concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) measurements for all available North American NRT measurement stations for
 5086 the periods Jan. 2010–June 2019 and June 2021–May 2022. The solid blue line denotes scores for the version of the
 5087 operational RAQDPS that was in service at the time while the solid orange line denotes scores for the RAQDPS-
 5088 OP023 forecasts and hindcasts.

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5090 Figure S220. Spatial distribution of predicted 2021/22 mean annual abundance fields of hourly (a) NO₂, (b) O₃, and
 5091 (c) PM_{2.5} with observed and predicted station annual abundances superimposed (shown as filled-in divided circles,
 5092 same colour bar) for RAQDPS-FW023. Units are ppbv, ppbv, and µg·m⁻³, respectively. [cf. Fig. 1]

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5096 Figure S221. Spatial distribution of 2021/22 annual (a) MB, (b) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics at all NRT
 5097 stations for hourly NO₂ measurements for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 2]

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5099 Figure S222. Spatial distribution of 2021/22 annual (a) MB, (b) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics at all NRT
 5100 stations for hourly O₃ measurements for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 3]

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 5102 Figure S223. Spatial distribution of 2021/22 annual (a) MB, (b) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics at all NRT
 5103 stations for hourly $PM_{2.5}$ measurements for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 4]

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5105 Figure S224. Spatial distribution of predicted 2021/22 seasonal-mean abundance fields (from left to right: winter
 5106 [DJF], spring [MAM], summer [JJA], autumn [SON]) of hourly (top row) NO₂, (middle row) O₃, and (bottom row)
 5107 PM_{2.5} with observed and predicted seasonal station abundances superimposed (shown as filled-in divided circles,
 5108 same colour bar) for **RAQDPS-FW023**. Units are ppbv, ppbv, and µg·m⁻³, respectively. [cf. Fig. 5]

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5112 Figure S225. Time series of **monthly** (a) predicted and observed mean hourly NO₂ VMRs (ppbv) and (b) NMB, (c)
 5113 CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for 2021/22 for all NRT stations for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 6]

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5116 Figure S226. Time series of **monthly** (a) predicted and observed mean hourly O₃ VMRs (ppbv) and (b) NMB, (c)
 5117 CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for 2021/22 for all NRT stations for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 7]

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5121 Figure S227. Time series of **monthly** (a) predicted and observed mean hourly PM_{2.5} concentrations (µg·m⁻³) and
 5122 (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for 2021/22 for all NRT stations for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 8]

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5126 Figure S228. Time series of **diurnal** (a) predicted and observed annual-mean hourly NO₂ VMRs (ppbv) and (b) NMB,
 5127 (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for all of 2021/22 for all NRT stations for **RAQDPS-FW023**. Time is in hours LT.
 5128 [cf. Fig. 9]

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 5132 Figure S229. Time series of **diurnal** (a) predicted and observed annual-mean hourly O₃ VMRs (ppbv) and (b) NMB,
 5133 (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for all of 2021/22 for all NRT stations for **RAQDPS-FW023**. Time is in hours LT.
 5134 [cf. Fig. 10]

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 5138 Figure S230. Time series of **diurnal** (a) predicted and observed annual-mean hourly PM_{2.5} concentrations (µg·m⁻³)
 5139 and (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for all of 2021/22 for all NRT stations for **RAQDPS-FW023**. Time is
 5140 in hours LT. [cf. Fig. 11]

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 5144 Figure S231. Time series of monthly predicted and observed annual-mean hourly (left) NO₂ VMR (ppbv), (centre)
 5145 O₃ VMR (ppbv), and (right) PM_{2.5} concentration (µg·m⁻³) in LT for all NRT stations but stratified into **four regions**
 5146 for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. 12]

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5149 Figure S232. Time series of monthly statistics (med O, med P, MB, FAC2, NSD) for hourly NO₂ VMR (ppbv) for
 5150 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. S137]

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5154 Figure S233. Time series of monthly statistics (med O, med P, MB, FAC2, NSD) for hourly O₃ VMR (ppbv) for
 5155 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. S138]

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5159 Figure S234. Time series of monthly statistics (med O, med P, MB, FAC2, NSD) for hourly PM_{2.5} concentration
 5160 (µg·m⁻³) for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT stations. [cf. Fig. S139]

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5164 Figure S235. Time series of monthly statistics (avg O, avg P, NMB, FAC2, R) for hourly NO₂ VMR (ppbv) for 2013–
 5165 2016 for RAQDPS-OP023 and 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. S140]

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5169 Figure S236. Time series of monthly statistics (avg O, avg P, NMB, FAC2, R) for hourly O₃ VMR (ppbv) for 2013–
 5170 2016 for RAQDPS-OP023 and 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. S141]

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5174 Figure S237. Time series of monthly statistics (avg O, avg P, NMB, FAC2, R) for hourly PM_{2.5} concentration (µg·m⁻³)
 5175 for 2013–2016 for RAQDPS-OP023 and 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Fig. S142]

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Figure S238. Time series of O and M diurnal concentrations of mean hourly NO₂ VMR (ppbv) by **season** for 2021/22 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT measurement stations. [cf. Fig. S165]

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5182 Figure S239. Time series of O and M diurnal concentrations of mean hourly O₃ VMR (ppbv) by **season** for 2021/22
 5183 for **RAQDPS-FW023** for all NRT measurement stations. [cf. Fig. S166]

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5185 Figure S240. Time series of O and M diurnal concentrations of mean hourly $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) by season
 5186 for RAQDPS-FW023 for all NRT measurement stations. [cf. Fig. S167]

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 5188 Figure S241. Time series of O and M diurnal concentrations of annual-mean hourly NO₂ VMR (ppbv), O₃ VMR
 5189 (ppbv), and PM_{2.5} concentration (µg·m⁻³) by region for 2021/22 RAQDPS-FW023. [cf. Fig. S168]
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 5192 Figure S242. Monthly density scatterplots of hourly NO₂ VMR predictions vs. AirNow NRT measurements (ppbv)
 5193 for 4 mid-season months for 2021/22 for RAQDPS-FW023. [cf. Fig. S169]
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 5196 Figure S243. Monthly density scatterplots of hourly O₃ VMR predictions vs. AirNow NRT measurements (ppbv) for
 5197 4 mid-season months for 2021/22 for RAQDPS-FW023. [cf. Fig. S170]
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 5200 Figure S244. Monthly density scatterplots of hourly PM_{2.5} concentration predictions vs. AirNow NRT measurements
 5201 (µg·m⁻³) for 4 mid-season months for 2021/22 for RAQDPS-FW023. [cf. Fig. S171]

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5203 Figure S245. Time series of **monthly** (a) predicted and observed mean hourly $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and
 5204 (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for 2021/22 for all NRT **urban** stations for both **RAQDPS-OP023** and
 5205 **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Figs. 8, S227, S213, S214]

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5209 Figure S246. Time series of **monthly** (a) predicted and observed mean hourly $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and
 5210 (b) NMB, (c) CRMSE, and (d) R statistics for 2021/22 for all NRT **rural** stations for both **RAQDPS-OP023** and
 5211 **RAQDPS-FW023**. [cf. Figs. 8, [S227](#), [S213](#), [S214](#)]